

Final
Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
2013–2018

Hawthorne Army Depot

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Prepared for

Hawthorne Army Depot

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**FINAL
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN**

**HAWTHORNE ARMY DEPOT
HAWTHORNE, NEVADA**

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan has been developed by the Hawthorne Army Depot in cooperation with the United States Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service, the Nevada Department of Wildlife, Walker River Paiute Tribe, United States Bureau of Land Management, United States Forest Service, and Nevada State Historic Preservation Office. The signatures below indicate the mutual agreement of the parties concerning the conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources as presented in the plan.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACO	Army contracting officer
AR	U.S. Army Regulation
BLM	U.S. Bureau of Land Management
BMP	best management practice
CC	compliance cleanup
CERCLA	Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act
CFR	<i>Code of Federal Regulations</i>
CIS	capital investment strategy
CWA	Clean Water Act
DoD	Department of Defense
DOE	U.S. Department of Energy
EO	Executive Order
EPA	U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
ESA	Endangered Species Act
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
GBBO	Great Basin Bird Observatory
GIS	geographic information systems
GOCO	government-owned contractor-operated
GPS	global positioning system
HWAD	Hawthorne Army Depot
IAP	Installation Action Plan
ICRMP	Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
IPM	integrated pest management

IPMP	Integrated Pest Management Plan
IRP	Installation Restoration Program
LCT	Lahontan cutthroat trout
MBTA	Migratory Bird Treaty Act
mg/L	milligram per liter
MMRP	Military Munitions Response Program
MOA	Memorandum of Agreement
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
msl	above mean sea level
NAC	Nevada Administrative Code
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NFA	no further action
NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act
NMFS	National Marine Fisheries Service
NDOW	Nevada Department of Wildlife
NNHP	Nevada Natural Heritage Program
NRCS	Natural Resources Conservation Service
NRHP	National Register of Historic Places
NUWC	Naval Undersea Warfare Center
NWGPF	Nevada Working Group of Partners in Flight
OB/OD	open-burn/open-detonation
OM	operations and maintenance
ORCP	Oil Removal Contingency Plan
POL	petroleum oil lubricant
PMU	Population Management Unit

RCRA	Resource Recovery Conservation Act
RPMP	Real Property Master Plan
SHPO	State Historic Preservation Office
SOC	SOC of Nevada, LLC
SPCCP	Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasure Plan
SWPPP	Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan
TDS	total dissolved solids
TNC	The Nature Conservancy
U.S.C.	<i>United States Code</i>
UNR	University of Nevada at Reno
US	U.S. Highway
USACE	U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
USFS	U.S. Forest Service
USFWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
USGS	U.S. Geological Survey
UXO	unexploded ordnance
WADF	Western Area Demilitarization Facility
WAP	Wildlife Action Plan
WRPT	Walker River Paiute Tribe

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ES.1 PURPOSE

The purpose of this Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) is to guide the natural resources management program from 2013 to 2018 and provide a solid foundation for Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD) on which to build the program beyond 2018. Implementing this INRMP will allow HWAD to achieve its goal to ensure the sustainability to test and demilitarize munitions, to maintain equipment, and to provide tenant support while maintaining ecosystem viability. In addition, complying with this INRMP ensures that natural resource conservation measures and Army activities on HWAD land are integrated and consistent with federal stewardship requirements.

ES.2 ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE

Under the Natural Resource Management on Military Lands Act of 1960 (Title 16 of the *United States Code* [U.S.C.] sections 670a *et seq.*), commonly known as the Sikes Act,

The Secretary of Defense shall carry out a program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations. To facilitate the program, the Secretary of each military department shall prepare and implement an integrated natural resources management plan for each military installation in the United States under the jurisdiction of the Secretary. Consistent with the use of military installations to ensure the preparedness of the Armed Forces, the Secretaries of the military departments shall carry out the program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations; the sustainable multipurpose use of the resources, which shall include hunting, fishing, trapping, and nonconsumptive uses; and subject to safety requirements and military security, public access to military installations to facilitate the use.

Per 16 U.S.C. 670a(b) *et seq.*, to the extent appropriate and applicable, this INRMP provides for the following:

- Fish and wildlife management and land management
- Fish and wildlife habitat enhancement or modifications
- Surface water and wetland protection, enhancement, and restoration where necessary for the support of fish, wildlife, or plants
- Integration of, and consistency among, the various activities conducted under the plan
- Establishment of specific natural resource management goals and objectives for the proposed action
- Sustainable use by the public of natural resources to the extent that the use is consistent with the needs of fish and wildlife resources
- Public access to the military installation that is necessary or appropriate for the use described above, subject to the requirements necessary to ensure safety and military security

- Enforcement of applicable natural resource laws (including regulations)
- No net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission of the installation
- Such other activities as the Secretary of the Army determines appropriate

In preparing this INRMP, HWAD has maintained its commitment to ensure that environmental considerations are integral to the mission and has complied with U.S. Army Regulation (AR) 200-1, *Environmental Quality: Environmental Protection and Enhancement*; the Department of the Army's INRMP Policy Memorandum (March 21, 1997) (HQDA 2007), titled *Army Goals and Implementing Guidance for Natural Resources Planning Level Surveys and INRMP* (HQDA 2007); and Title 32 of the *Code of Federal Regulations*, Part 651, *Environmental Analysis of Army Actions*. In addition, this INRMP provides the guidance necessary for HWAD to maintain compliance with the Endangered Species Act, the Clean Water Act, and Executive Order 11990 (Protection of Wetlands). This document reflects HWAD's commitment to conserve, protect, and enhance natural resources necessary to provide support maintenance and storage services for the U.S. Army.

ES.3 SCOPE

The INRMP addresses the geographic area associated with the contiguous properties of HWAD. The INRMP provides management measures developed by considering various alternatives for meeting resource-specific goals and objectives at HWAD.

A separate Environmental Assessment (EA) was prepared evaluating the effects of implementing the INRMP at HWAD (Appendix H). The EA carries the INRMP's selected management measures forward as the proposed action. Preparation and implementation of the INRMP is required by the Sikes Act and is an Army regulatory requirement (AR 200-1), so other alternatives, such as partial implementation of the INRMP, were considered but were dismissed as being infeasible or impracticable; therefore, the EA addresses only the proposed action and the No Action Alternative.

ES.4 SUSTAINABILITY AND THE MILITARY MISSION

Implementation of this INRMP would be expected to maintain the ecological integrity of the landscape and ensure that there is no net loss in the capability of HWAD to test and demilitarize munitions, to maintain equipment, and to provide tenant support while maintaining ecosystem viability to support the military mission. In addition, implementing this INRMP would allow HWAD to continue to promote compatible multiple uses of its land, such as habitat conservation, hunting, and other outdoor recreational pursuits.

ES.5 HIGH-PRIORITY PROJECTS

The projects in this INRMP have been evaluated, and the high-priority projects are included in this section. The projects are prioritized by need, and need is based on a project's importance in moving the natural resources management program closer to successfully achieving its goal. Projects would be conducted subject to the availability of funding. The high-priority projects identified include the following:

Facilities and developed areas

- Reduce the potential of hazardous waste releases from mercury storage by following the Memorandum of Agreement between the Defense National Stockpile Center and the U.S. Army Joint Munitions Command for the Storage of the National Defense Stockpile Inventory Mercury.
- Continue cooperative agreements emergency and fire management with the Mineral County, the town of Hawthorne, WRPT and state and federal agencies.
- Continue geothermal exploration as an alternate power source for the installation.

Vegetation Management

- Continue coordinating with the town of Hawthorne, Mineral County, state and federal agencies regarding wildland fire management and emergency response.

Water Resources and Wetland Management

- Continue maintaining the Mount Grant watershed in an ecologically balanced condition to support a potable water supply to support the military mission.
- Continue water quality monitoring of groundwater and potable water sources.
- Continue conducting unexploded ordnance surveys at Walker Lake to minimize potential hazards.

Wildland Fire and Prescribed Burning Management

- Continue cooperative agreements emergency and fire management with Mineral County, the town of Hawthorne, and state and federal agencies.

Fish and Wildlife Management

- Monitor the success of the introduction of tui chub into Rose Creek Reservoir and potential future introduction to Walker Lake.
- Continue to monitor total dissolved solids levels in Walker Lake to determine if Lahontan cutthroat trout might be reintroduced and if sport fishing could return.
- Continue cooperative agreements with natural resources agencies for wildlife surveys and management assistance.
- Continue to monitor American pikas as an indicator of how wildlife at higher elevations are faring under contemporary climate change, and ascertain what actions may be done to facilitate their persistence and conservation.

Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species Management

- Continue to monitor and conduct surveys for threatened and endangered species and their habit to determine if additional management measures should be introduced at HWAD.
- Implement conservation strategies for the greater sage-grouse by continuing multi-agency coordination with the sage-grouse conservation initiative.

Invasive Species Management

- Develop a management plan to reduce tamarisk from growing and spreading. Previous INRMPs indicated University of Nevada – Reno and the Nevada Department of Agriculture were preparing a management plan along Walker Lake. It is undetermined if this was developed and evaluated under the National Environmental Policy Act process.

Pest Management

- HWAD should continue coordinating with Nevada Department of Wildlife about the management and removal of California black bear on Mount Grant and in the Industrial area. Evaluate whether a formal management plan should be developed.

Cultural Resources

- The cultural resource manager at HWAD consults as required for all projects in accordance with the Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan.

ES.6 GOALS

The goal established by HWAD is for the natural resources management program to maintain ecosystem viability while supporting the military mission. HWAD has identified several objectives necessary to achieve that goal:

- Support the military mission of HWAD
- Maintain the Mount Grant watershed in an ecologically sound condition
- Buffer wildlife areas and industrial areas from the impacts of the military mission
- Provide access and funding for monitoring the condition of the natural resources

The ability to achieve those goals depends directly on the health and condition of the natural resources at the installation. Protecting the ecological and biological integrity of Walker Lake, Mount Grant, industrial areas, and active military areas ensures that those lands will continue to provide biodiverse habitats. Such protection will also preserve outdoor recreational activities at HWAD, such as hunting, sightseeing, and golfing.

ES.7 IMPLEMENTATION

To ensure the preparedness of the Armed Forces and consistent use of the installation, the Sikes Act section 101(b)(1)(I) states that each INRMP must provide for “no net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission of the installation” to the extent appropriate and applicable.

U.S. Department of Defense policy stipulates appropriate management objectives to protect the mission capabilities of installation lands (from which annual projects are developed) should be clearly articulated in the planning process and should be high in INRMP resourcing priorities. The effectiveness of the INRMP in preventing *net loss* must be evaluated annually. Where applicable, mission requirements and priorities identified in the INRMP must be integrated into other environmental programs and policies. It is not the intent that natural resources are to be consumed but are instead sustained for the use of mission requirements. To achieve this, environmental programs and policies must have the goal of preserving the environment for the purpose of the mission.

There might be instances in which a net loss is unavoidable because of the need to fulfill regulatory requirements other than the Sikes Act, such as complying with a Biological Opinion

under the provisions of the Endangered Species Act or protection of wetlands under the provisions of the Clean Water Act.

No net loss in the capability of installation lands to support the military mission would be expected as a result of implementing this INRMP.

The INRMP is the final plan that will direct the natural resources management program at HWAD from 2013 through 2018. An ecosystem approach was used to develop the management measures for each resource area. The overlap of similar management measures for different resource areas is indicative of the relationship the components of an ecosystem have with one another. The need for integrated natural resources management is evident from the complexity of these relationships. For example, the Mount Grant watershed supports the military mission by providing a source of clean potable water and serves as a valuable training area. The area also provides recreational opportunities such as hunting. In addition to being essential to support the military mission, the condition of Mount Grant and Walker Lake directly influences the quality of wildlife habitat and diversity of wildlife inhabiting HWAD. The condition of vegetated watersheds directly influences water quality, the condition of fisheries, and sensitive habitats such as wetlands. These habitats are necessary to maintain and increase biodiversity at HWAD.

Managing Mount Grant, Walker Lake, and other habitats using an ecosystem approach will maintain, protect, and enhance natural resources. Results from habitat assessments and surveys serve as indicators of the overall ecological health of installation property. Areas of degraded habitat and watersheds result in the loss of ecological integrity and biodiversity, as well as degraded water quality. Adaptive ecosystem management, soil stabilization, and revegetation projects improve the health of small-scaled habitats and watershed conditions over the larger scale. Soil stabilization and revegetation along waterways and in upland areas mitigate erosion, decreasing sediment loads to streams, lakes, ponds, and wetlands. The effects of small-scaled habitat improvements extend throughout the watershed benefiting wildlife, aquatic life, and improving vigor of the ecological system.

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1 OVERVIEW

“The Army is committed to environmental stewardship in all actions as an integral part of its mission and to ensure sustainability” (HQDA 2007).

The purpose of this Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) is to guide the Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD) from 2013 through 2018 and provide a solid foundation for HWAD on which to build the program beyond 2018. Implementing this INRMP will allow HWAD to achieve its goal to ensure the sustainability test and demilitarize munitions, to maintain equipment, and to provide tenant support while maintaining ecosystem viability. In addition, implementing the INRMP ensures that natural resource conservation measures and Army activities on HWAD land are integrated and consistent with federal stewardship requirements.

1.1 INRMP Vision

Under the Natural Resource Management on Military Lands Act of 1960 (Title 16 of the *United States Code* [U.S.C.] section 670a *et seq.*), commonly known as the Sikes Act,

The Secretary of Defense shall carry out a program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations. To facilitate the program, the Secretary of each military department shall prepare and implement an integrated natural resources management plan for each military installation in the United States under the jurisdiction of the Secretary. Consistent with the use of military installations to ensure the preparedness of the Armed Forces, the Secretaries of the military departments shall carry out the program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations; the sustainable multipurpose use of the resources, which shall include hunting, fishing, trapping, and nonconsumptive uses; and subject to safety requirements and military security, public access to military installations to facilitate the use.

Per 16 U.S.C. 670a(b) *et seq.*, to the extent appropriate and applicable, the INRMP provides for the following:

- Fish and wildlife management and land management
- Fish and wildlife habitat enhancement or modifications
- Surface water and wetland protection, enhancement, and restoration where necessary for the support of fish, wildlife, or plants
- Integration of, and consistency among, the various activities conducted under the plan
- Establishment of specific natural resource management goals and objectives for the proposed action
- Sustainable use by the public of natural resources to the extent that the use is consistent with the needs of fish and wildlife resources
- Public access to the military installation that is necessary or appropriate for the use described above, subject to the requirements necessary to ensure safety and military security
- Enforcement of applicable natural resource laws (including regulations)

- No net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission of the installation
- Such other activities as the Secretary of the Army determines appropriate

In preparing this INRMP, HWAD has maintained its commitment to ensure that environmental considerations are integral to the mission and has complied with U.S. Army Regulation (AR) 200-1, *Environmental Quality: Environmental Protection and Enhancement* (HQDA 2007); the Department of the Army's INRMP Policy Memorandum (March 21, 1997), titled *Army Goals and Implementing Guidance for Natural Resources Planning Level Surveys and INRMP* (HQDA 2007); and Title 32 of the *Code of Federal Regulations* (CFR) Part 651, *Environmental Analysis of Army Actions*. In addition, this INRMP provides the guidance necessary for HWAD to maintain compliance with the Endangered Species Act (ESA), the Clean Water Act (CWA), and Executive Order (EO) 11990 (Protection of Wetlands). This document reflects HWAD's commitment to conserve, protect, and enhance natural resources necessary to provide support maintenance and storage services for the U.S. Army.

1.2 Strategic Goals and Objectives

The strategic goal of this INRMP for HWAD is to conform to the goals of the Conservation Program of the Department of Defense (DoD), which is to support the military mission by

- Providing for sustained use of its land and air resources
- Protecting valuable natural and cultural resources for future generations
- Meeting all legal requirements
- Promoting compatible multiple uses of those resources
- Achieving efficiencies and other savings by partnering with interested stakeholders

The goal established by HWAD is for the natural resources management program to maintain ecosystem viability while supporting the military mission. HWAD has identified objectives necessary to achieve that goal:

- Support the military mission of HWAD
- Maintain the Mount Grant watershed in an ecologically sound condition
- Buffer wildlife areas and industrial areas from the impacts of the military mission
- Provide access and funding for monitoring the condition of the natural resources

The ability to achieve those goals depends directly on the health and condition of the natural resources at the installation. Protecting the ecological and biological integrity of Walker Lake, Mount Grant, industrial areas, and active military areas ensures that those lands will continue to provide biodiverse habitats. Such protection will also preserve outdoor recreational activities at HWAD, such as hunting, sightseeing, and golfing.

To protect cultural resources, military operations will maintain adequate communication with the Cultural Resources Manager. All activities on the depot that could affect cultural resources will be coordinated with the cultural resources staff.

Natural resources management at HWAD must remain flexible if it is to achieve long-term success. HWAD will achieve and maintain this flexibility by incorporating adaptive management

techniques. Adaptive management is a process by which new monitoring data and scientific literature are used to evaluate the success of the management measures in place. That information is then used to determine changes in the management approach needed to ensure the program's continued success. The natural resources management program might also be required to adapt to unforeseen changes in military mission and legal requirements.

1.3 Responsibilities and Interested Parties

The success of the management of natural resources on HWAD and implementing this INRMP requires a cooperative effort among the parties directly responsible. Brief descriptions of the parties directly responsible for implementing this INRMP and other interested parties are provided below. HWAD is a government-owned contractor-operated (GOCO) facility; therefore, additional coordination might be required with contractor personnel if their roles at the installation change.

1.3.1 Hawthorne Army Depot

As a GOCO facility operating under the direction of SOC of Nevada, LLC (SOC), a limited number of military and civilian/government personnel are employed at HWAD. Thus, natural resources program management includes responsible parties from both the Army contracting officer (ACO) staff and from the operating contractor, SOC.

The roles of the organizations at HWAD directly responsible for, or helping to implement, this INRMP are described below. Figure 1-1 illustrates the organization structure of HWAD.

Army Contracting Officer (ACO). The ACO staff has primary responsibility and oversees the real property officer and the security division manager for the following tasks:

- Ensure that the INRMP is applied in a balanced manner and that it receives continuous planning
- Plan, promote, and foster natural beauty, and implement programs for environmental protection and enhancement—both on the installation and in cooperation with local communities
- Review and update Standard Operating Procedure number 320-0100 to maintain current compliance with state fish and game regulations
- Conduct meetings with state and federal agencies to enhance wildlife management
- Coordinate wildlife program recommendations with the HWAD commander and cooperating agencies
- Maintain records in accordance with state and federal agencies' requests for fish counts and wildlife harvests
- Develop, improve, and maintain fish and wildlife habitat by recommending harvest quotas and limiting seasons, in cooperation with state and federal laws

HWAD Security Department. The installation's security department, collects fees, enforces natural resources laws, and monitors fences.

HWAD Contract Administration and Operations Division (SJMHW-CAO). This division reviews water quality operations and reviews management of cultural and historical resources.

HWAD Maintenance, Planning, and Housing. This department maintains all grounds, except private-housing, landscaped areas.

Source: Michael Baker 2009

Figure 1-1. HWAD organizational structure.

Natural Resources Conservation and Beautification Committee. The Natural Resources Conservation and Beautification Committee implements the requirements of AR 200-1 by ensuring that the INRMP is applied in a balanced manner and that it receives continuous planning; and to plan, promote, and foster natural beauty, and implement programs for environmental protection and enhancement—both on the installation and in cooperation with local communities (HQDA 2007). This team is also integrated with the master planning board to ensure more thorough input. Members of the Natural Resources Conservation and Beautification Committee are

- Commander, chairman
- Civilian executive assistant
- Chief, Contract Administration and Operations Division
- Facilities management specialist
- Environmentalist
- Security officer
- Safety representative
- Recorder

1.3.2 Other Defense Organizations

Joint Munitions Command. Joint Munitions Command is the subcommand of the Army Materiel Command, and Joint Munitions Command oversees all government contractors at HWAD.

U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE), Mobile District. The Mobile District provided contractor support for preparing this INRMP.

1.3.3 Other Federal Agencies

A number of federal agencies, in addition to DoD and HWAD, have an interest or role in managing natural resources at HWAD. The basis of those agencies' involvement includes signatory responsibilities, cooperative agreements, regulatory authority, and technical assistance as required by federal laws and regulations. The agencies and their roles are described below.

U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS). USFWS provides signatory approval of the fish and wildlife components of the INRMP. It is the primary federal agency for issues regarding fish and wildlife management and the regulatory authority for the ESA and the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA) (16 U.S.C. 703-711). HWAD and USFWS maintain a cooperative agreement regarding the fish and wildlife program.

U.S. Bureau of Land Management (BLM). The BLM is responsible for managing more than 260 million acres of public land and 700 million acres of federal subsurface mineral estate nationwide. The BLM also responds to public demand for recreation, wildlife, open space, and energy needs. At HWAD, the BLM is available for managing feral horses and conservation surveys and provides signatory approval of the INRMP.

U.S. Forest Service (USFS). HWAD maintains an open-burn/open-detonation (OB/OD) on satellite land adjacent to Toiyabe National Forest and provides signatory approval of the INRMP regarding USFS lands. HWAD coordinates its satellite boundary requirements with USFS.

HWAD has developed cooperative agreements with BLM and USFS for the installation's fire prevention plan and fire-fighting.

U.S. Department of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS). NMFS is the agency in addition to the USFWS with regulatory authority under the ESA and essential fish habitat under the Magnuson-Stevens Act of 1996.

U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). The USGS also cooperates with HWAD for sage-grouse tracking and surveys for sage-grouse on Mount Grant. Dr. Eric Blomberg is the wildlife biologist working with the installation. Dr. Erik Beever has been conducting research on Mount Grant and adjacent areas since the mid-1990s and continues to be heavily involved in research efforts at HWAD for the American pika, as part of pika research across the hydrographic Great Basin.

1.3.4 State Agencies

Nevada Department of Wildlife (NDOW). NDOW provides signatory approval of the fish and wildlife aspects of the INRMP, and it is the primary state agency coordinating issues regarding fish and wildlife management at HWAD. NDOW manages regulated fisheries and stocking program for the threatened Lahontan cutthroat trout (LCT) at HWAD.

Nevada State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO). SHPO provides signatory approval of the cultural and historic properties subject to effect by HWAD actions.

1.3.5 Native American Tribes

Walker River Paiute Tribe (WRPT). The WRPT has notified HWAD that it has interests in the region and resources that contain the Walker River, Walker Lake, and the Wassuk Range Mountains, specifically on Mount Grant. The Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan (ICRMP) was used to develop a Native American Consultation Management Plan that identifies the process for HWAD consultations with the WRPT for long-range planning and to address specific concerns (Earth Tech 2002). Consultation efforts are coordinated by the HWAD Cultural Resource Manager, who could be appointed as a liaison for Native American issues. The installation Commander has sole authority to sign consultation and agreement documents. The tribe is a coordinating agency for this INRMP and for all cultural and historical consultations and also provides signatory approval for those aspects of the INRMP.

1.3.6 Universities

University of Nevada. The Department of Biology conducts research on Walker Lake including aquatic biota, birds, water levels, biodiversity, and water quality. The University of Nevada at Reno (UNR) and the Nevada Department of Agriculture are preparing a management plan for the eradication and control of tamarisk along Walker Lake.

University of California at Berkeley. The university conducts limnology research on Walker Lake.

University of California at Davis. The university has conducted bird and butterfly surveys on HWAD.

San Francisco State. The Department of Biology conducts research on desert scorpions at HWAD.

1.3.7 Contractors

Contractors provide government support throughout the installation for natural resources and environmental management projects. That technical support includes preparing the INRMP, National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) analyses and documentation, conducting cultural and biological resource surveys, and general natural resource management support.

1.3.8 Other Interested Parties

A private citizen, the Great Basin Bird Observatory (GBBO), and the Nevada Working Group of Partners in Flight (NWGPF) survey wintering birds at Walker Lake. The Bi-State Technical Advisory Committee, Nevada and California is working with a myriad of state and federal agencies, universities, interested parties, and landowners to conserve the greater sage-grouse.

1.4 Military Mission

1.4.1 Mission Statement and Vision

HWAD's Mission. HWAD is an archive site for storing slow-moving ammunition and stocks awaiting demilitarization. As the designated site for long-term storage of reused industrial plant equipment, HWAD receives, stores, and accounts for all industrial plant equipment. HWAD's mission is as follows (HWAD 2012a):

- Provide for the receipt, storage, rewarehousing, preservation, packaging, surveillance, renovating, demilitarization/disposal, and issue of conventional ammunition, including response to DoD shipping contingency/wartime requirements as identified by higher headquarters to meet all operational munitions movement
- Provide nationwide depot redistribution for demilitarization and maintenance/renovation projects identified by the single manager for conventional ammunition
- Ensure capability to ship/receive containerized munitions
- Operate the calibration laboratory
- Maintain an International Standards Organization container maintenance/repair facility
- Maintain an ammunition maintenance capability
- Provide limited training facilities for DoD conventional forces and Special Forces military personnel

HWAD Vision. HWAD's Vision 2025 outlines the military vision as, "The ongoing transformation of [HWAD], Nevada, as a West Coast Combat Support Services Center that serves the needs of all of the DoD combat and support services" (Michael Baker 2009).

1.4.2 Military Mission and Environmental Policy

HWAD is a 147,236-acre (59,489-hectare) installation in Mineral County, Nevada. The installation's main military mission is to test and demilitarize munitions, to maintain equipment, and to provide tenant support. Tenants include the U.S. Marine Corps Programs Office and the U.S. Naval Underseas Warfare Engineering Station-Keyport Detachment. Tenant activities

include the operation of the Carter munitions test range and renovation, assembly, and maintenance of a naval mine assembly facility. HWAD has an informal mission component for low-impact Special Forces training in addition to its core ammunition support activity. HWAD's natural resource management staff maintains compliance with a variety of natural resources laws, such as the ESA, CWA, National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), and NEPA.

1.4.3 Future Mission Impacts to Natural Resources

The INRMP is a living document developed on the basis of short-, medium-, and long-range planning goals. Short-range goals include activities planned in the next 5 years, and medium-range goals include activities in a 6- to 10-year period. Long-range goals are usually scheduled beyond 10 years. As a living document, goals can be revised to reflect evolving environmental conditions.

1.5 Installation Land Use

1.5.1 Location and Brief Description

HWAD is in southwestern Nevada, in Mineral County, approximately 132 miles southeast of Reno, Nevada, and 65 miles southeast of Carson City, Nevada (see Figure 1-2). The installation is bisected by U.S. Highway (US) 95, and the town of Hawthorne is surrounded by the installation. On the north, HWAD is bordered by the Township of Walker Lake and associated communities, private ranches and Walker Lake; on the east, south and west, HWAD is bordered by BLM public grazing lands. US 839 runs northeast, US 95 runs northwest and bends to the east, and US 359 runs south from the installation. HWAD is within 300 miles of Las Vegas, Nevada, and Los Angeles and Sacramento, California.

The installation land is used for ordnance storage and demolition, administrative and warehouse operations, training, land management, and recreation. The elevation ranges from 3,900 to 5,000 feet above mean sea level (msl). The southern portion of Walker Lake belongs to the installation, and the boundary is marked with buoys. Approximately 45,000 acres of the installation are on Mount Grant with a maximum elevation of 11,329 feet msl, an additional 100,000 acres are used for ordnance storage and demolition, and 328 acres are used for industrial administration buildings.

1.5.2 Historic Land Use

The town of Hawthorne was established by gold prospectors and miners and was officially recognized as a town in 1879 (Earth Tech 2002). The Carson and Colorado Railroad Company constructed a railroad to the town in 1880. Before the installation was constructed in 1928, Hawthorne's population was about 244 residents (Earth Tech 2002). HWAD was historically included as an area in the Northern Paiute territory, and in 1874 the Walker River and Pyramid Lake reservations were formally established.

HWAD was commissioned to be a naval ammunition storage and manufacturing plant after deadly explosions at the Lake Denmark Naval Ammunitions Depot in New Jersey in 1926. HWAD's remote location surrounded by mountain ranges but with nearby railroad tracks and government owned land made it an ideal candidate for a state-of-the-art ammunition storage facility. HWAD served as the most important ammunition installation for the Pacific during World War II. Since its inception, HWAD has passed into Army ownership

HWAD Location
Hawthorne Army Depot
Hawthorne, Nevada
Figure 1-2

LEGEND
Hawthorne Army Depot
cities
Interstate
Highway

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, USGS, ESRI

1.5.3 Current Land Use

HWAD is divided into four general land use areas: (1) active military areas; (2) the cantonment area—industrial, administration, and housing areas; (3) the Mount Grant watershed; and (4) the area at the south end of Walker Lake (see Figure 1-3).

The active military areas consist of unimproved areas that service the magazine and warehouse areas, and areas used for test ranges and permitted OB/OD of unstable ordnance. These areas are surrounded by a large buffer zone of unimproved land and, on the northeast side, by Walker Lake. The primary ordnance areas at HWAD cover about 100,000 acres that cross US 95. This area is surrounded on its northeast, east, south, and west by fencing and on its north and northwest by a boundary line that includes a portion of Walker Lake.

The New Bomb Demilitarization Facility is a 3,000-acre secondary ordnance area, which is fenced along its borders. The facility is about 23 miles south of HWAD's southern boundary and is not contiguous to the rest of HWAD. USFS lands border the New Bomb Demilitarization Facility.

The cantonment area is centrally located in the installation and covers about 328 acres. This area includes industrial, administration, and housing areas and comprises the Main Base, Old Bomb Area (south of the South Magazine Area), Western Area Demilitarization Facility (WADF), and the North, Central, and South Magazine Areas. HWAD has 2,904 ammunition storage structures including 2,428 igloos and 476 explosive warehouses, barricaded open sites, and inert warehouses (Michael Baker 2009). Resources managed in the cantonment area include improved lands that have been developed into buildings, roadways, and a golf course. The surrounding lands have either been converted to lawns and other forms of landscaped areas or left as desert habitat.

The northwest portion of the installation consists of Mount Grant and includes about 45,000 acres. HWAD and Army Materiel Command have determined that Mount Grant is a multiple-use zone, providing habitat for desert wildlife, supplying water to HWAD, serving as a recreation area, and containing mining and cultural artifacts. The Flat Ranges are at the foot of Mount Grant. The Old Bomb Area and Carter Ranges are at the south end of the South Magazine Area.

Walker Lake is a highly alkaline, mineralized lake. Although the lake and the adjoining beachfront are no longer used for test range activities, a security line of water buoys extends across the south end of the lake to denote entering an unexploded ordnance (UXO) area on Army property. The southern one-third of Walker Lake is in the ordnance area.

1.5.4 Future Land Use

The existing land uses on the installation will continue, with the exception that short- and long-range infrastructure development projects could be implemented according to HWAD's Real Property Master Plan, as outlined in the Future Development Plan (Michael Baker 2009). The plan identifies a variety of facility and infrastructure development projects, both programmed and unprogrammed, that could be implemented pursuant to available funding.

HWAD Installation Layout
 Hawthorne Army Depot
 Hawthorne, Nevada
 Figure 1-3

LEGEND

- Hawthorne Army Depot
- Access Control Point
- Contamination Area
- Ammunition Storage
- Live Fire Restricted Area
- Railroad
- Highway
- Street
- Stream

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, ESRI

1.6 Land Use Planning

1.6.1 Land Use Planning Standards and Decision-Making Processes

Carrying out HWAD's mission to test and demilitarize munitions, maintain equipment, and provide tenant support requires a large area of land for a buffer area surrounding the various detonation sites and large industrial and storage areas. HWAD is in a remote area to reduce the risk to population centers of explosive accidents and the associated nuisance noise and air disturbance.

Installation training, maneuver, maintenance, and storage areas are subject to multiple uses and are managed by HWAD to give consideration of all demands for using the land and water resources to ensure consistency with the military mission, conservation, and environmental protection.

1.6.2 Relationship of This INRMP to Other Plans

This INRMP integrates military support operations with the requirements to maintain the ecological health of the installation's natural resources. That goal is achieved by implementing the INRMP and various other plans and programs that support the military mission. Related plans and programs are discussed below.

Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP). The ICRMP is a 5-year plan (2006 through 2011) and is designed to serve as the Commander's decision document for actions that could affect cultural resources.

Integrated Pest Management Plan (IPMP). The IPMP is established and maintained as a part of the Real Property Maintenance Program for HWAD and in conjunction with the INRMP.

Invasive Species Survey Report. Invasive plant species surveys were conducted at HWAD in 2003. The objective of the survey was to gather information on the location and prevalence of invasive plants to improve natural resource management at HWAD and to comply with federal and U.S. Army directives.

Oil Removal Contingency Plan (ORCP). HWAD prepared an ORCP in accordance with the regulations described in 40 CFR Parts 109 and 112. HWAD uses large quantities of petroleum oil lubricant (POL) products as fuels and lubricants during operations. The plan describes the emergency organization and anticipated response to spills, fires, explosions, or other emergencies involving POLs.

Rare Plant Survey and Management Recommendations. HWAD conducted a geographical and biological survey on rare plant species to ensure compliance with endangered species laws and to provide conservation management where needed. The objective of this study was to search for potential rare vascular plant species, document their occurrences, habitat requirements, population biology, and make recommendations for conservation management.

Real Property Master Plan (RPMP). The RPMP serves as a manual for proper management and long-term use of facilities and other real property assets at HWAD. The RPMP also facilitates effective allocation and investment of DoD funding and other federal resources to support the planning, programming, budgeting, and execution process. The RPMP assists real property

stewards in proactively mitigating facility challenges by ensuring efficient acquisition, use, and disposal of real property assets for mission support.

Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasure Plan (SPCCP). The SPCCP is required in accordance with 40 CFR 112.7 for owners and operators of facilities that gather, store, process, transfer, distribute, use, or consume oil and oil products and might reasonably be expected to discharge oil (in quantities that could be harmful) in or on navigable water of the United States or adjoining shorelines or waters of the contiguous zone or affecting certain natural resources. HWAD has more than the required quantity of more than 1,320 gallons of POL that could affect navigable waters or natural resources.

Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP). HWAD's SWPPP identifies potential sources of pollution that could affect the quality of stormwater discharges associated with the installation's industrial activities. The plan also describes the practices that are to be used to reduce the pollutants in stormwater discharges associated with HWAD's industrial activity and to ensure compliance with the terms and conditions of the permit. This plan is being updated and the erosion control measures will be included in Appendix F when complete.

1.7 Strategic Design of the INRMP

1.7.1 INRMP Preparation Methods

Preparing this INRMP involved reviewing and analyzing past natural resources management practices, ongoing programs, and the conditions of the existing resources as detailed in Section 2.0. The review process included interviewing HWAD personnel and key individuals from state (e.g., Nevada State Office of Energy, Nevada Department of Environmental Protection, NDOW) and federal agencies (e.g., USGS, USFS, BLM), collecting existing environmental documentation, and conducting field reconnaissance of the installation.

The findings from interviews, field reconnaissance, and document review process have been synthesized and incorporated into this INRMP using the ecosystem management approach. Where data gaps exist, inventorying and monitoring programs have been proposed. Those programs are designed to collect the data necessary to fill the information gaps and to achieve the objectives of the land management program.

1.7.2 Approaches and Strategies for Resource Management

The approach used to develop the discussion of the management strategies for each resource followed four general steps:

- **Goals and Objectives.** The goals and objectives for managing the resource, and the relationship of the resource to other components of the ecosystem (including the human component) and the military mission were described.
- **Management Strategies.** Past management strategies, current conditions, and an array of management strategies that are based on current ecosystem management principles were evaluated and considered to develop management strategies that would achieve the goals and objectives for the resource and those of the overall natural resources management program. An inventory was included of needs and monitoring programs necessary to generate data to ensure the continued success of the program and to provide the information needed to facilitate the integration of adaptive management techniques.

Adaptive management is a continuing process of actions based on planning, monitoring, evaluation, and adjustment. When adequately designed and effectively implemented, the process allows managers to determine how well an action meets their objectives (whether that is protection of sensitive habitats or maintenance of scenic beauty) and what management steps are needed to increase the chances of achieving the objective.

- **Other Management Alternatives.** Other management alternatives were considered during the screening process but eliminated because they were incompatible with the requirements of the military mission, ecologically unsound, or economically infeasible.
- **Ecosystem Management.** This INRMP follows the direction set forth in the memorandum issued by the Deputy Under Secretary of Defense for Environmental Security (August 8, 1994) regarding implementing ecosystem management in the DoD. The memorandum states that ecosystem management is to be the basis for management of DoD lands and waters. In that context, ecosystem management includes the following:
 - **Ecological Approach:** Individual species management will shift to managing ecosystems.
 - **Partnerships:** Ecosystems cross political boundaries, making the need for cooperation, coordination, and partnerships essential for managing ecosystems.
 - **Participation:** Public needs and desires will be emphasized in management decisions.
 - **Information:** The best available scientific information will be used to select technologies used in managing natural resources.
 - **Adaptive Management:** Adaptive management techniques will be incrementally applied as they are identified.

DoD's overall goal regarding ecosystem management is "...to preserve, improve, and enhance ecosystem integrity. Over the long-term, this approach will maintain and improve the sustainability and biological diversity of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems while supporting sustainable economies and communities." The specific principles and guidelines that DoD has identified to achieve that goal are listed below. They are reflected in the management measures in Section 3.0, Future Natural Resources Management.

- Maintain and improve the sustainability and native biodiversity of ecosystems
- Administer with considerations of ecological units and time frames
- Support sustainable human activities
- Develop a vision of ecosystem health
- Develop priorities and reconcile conflicts
- Develop coordinated approaches to work toward ecosystem health
- Rely on the best science and data available
- Use benchmarks to monitor and evaluate outcomes
- Use adaptive management
- Implement through installation plans and programs

Ecosystem management recognizes that humans are ecosystem components and that sustainable human activity does not mutually exclude the preservation and enhancement of ecological integrity. Therefore, ecosystem management provides HWAD the means to both protect biodiversity and continue to provide high-quality military readiness.

The management measures and strategies that will be implemented at HWAD have been developed with consideration of the interrelationships among the individual components of the ecosystem, the requirements of the military mission, and other land use activities. The focus is on maintaining the structure, diversity, and integrity of the biological communities, while recognizing that the military mission is a vital component of the ecosystem. An adaptive management strategy has been incorporated into this INRMP to monitor the temporal and spatial dynamics of the ecosystems and to adjust the management measures and strategies on the basis of improved knowledge and data. Monitoring programs will generate the data needed to determine whether the management measures and strategies are effective in achieving their intended goals and objectives. Such a management approach will preserve and enhance natural resources while providing the optimum environmental conditions required to sustain the military mission and training areas.

1.7.3 Plan Organization

The INRMP has five sections:

1. **Overview** provides background information about the mission and installation and identifies key issues and any issues that might be unresolved.
2. **Current Conditions and Use** describes the baseline condition to be used as background and as a context for future management goals, objectives, and actions that are detailed in Section 3.0.
3. **Future Natural Resources Management** proposes an array of management approaches needed to fully integrate natural resources management with military use of the land. This section describes strategies for complying with environmental laws and conserving, managing, and restoring habitats, species, soil, and water. It also addresses inventory, monitoring, and research programs that provide for the foundation for sound, performance-based environmental compliance and form the basis for responsive, adaptive management in support of military land and water use requirements.
4. **Implementation** shows how the installation uses scheduling and funding to ensure that strategies are implemented to achieve goals and objectives and the desired future condition, and the ways the INRMP will be supported by implementing funding options.
5. **Appendices** include supporting documents used for the INRMP, including management plans, species lists, cooperative agreements, Memorandums of Understanding (MOU), and Memorandums of Agreement (MOA).

1.7.4 Key Issues for Natural Resources Management

HWAD must address two key issues to support the military mission and to maintain and conserve the installation's natural resources:

- INRMP project implementation
 - Ensure that INRMP projects, including follow-up inventorying and monitoring work, are properly identified, developed, and submitted for funding
 - Determine if project funding has been received, obligated, and expended
 - Follow projects through completion and evaluate whether they meet expected objectives
- Ecosystem integrity
 - Evaluate the extent and quality of the installation's native ecological systems
 - Identify the installation's habitats that are susceptible to change or damage from various stressors
 - Identify the stressors that affect each habitat

1.7.5 Implementing Funding Options

The following paragraphs describe HWAD's funding and schedule information.

Capital Investment Strategy (CIS). The CIS is the overall plan for using and investing in real property to support HWAD's mission and objectives and to accommodate military and civilian employees in quality living and working facilities (required under AR 210-20, *Master Planning for Army Installations*) (HQDA 2005). The CIS provides a methodology to identify infrastructure and facility projects by examining future mission changes and existing facility surpluses and deficits to optimize underused infrastructure, prioritizing the construction program, and offering intermediate solutions to shortfalls.

Fish and Wildlife Funds. HWAD confers with cooperating governmental agencies for wildlife materials and professional expertise. HWAD is responsible for collecting fees for fishing access, submits fees to the government, and is able to receive funding to support conservation projects.

Installation Action Plan (IAP). The purpose of the IAP is to outline the total multiyear cleanup program for an installation. The plan identifies environmental cleanup requirements at each site or area of concern and proposes a comprehensive, installation-wide approach, along with the costs and schedules associated with conducting investigations and taking the necessary remedial actions. All site-specific funding and schedule information is prepared according to projected overall Army funding levels and is, therefore, subject to change. HWAD's IAP (2012a) addresses the following areas: Land Use Control, Installation Restoration Program (IRP), Military Munitions Response Program (MMRP), and Compliance Restoration.

Operations and Maintenance (OM). Unlike other Army installations, HWAD is a GOCO installation and does not have a specific set-aside OM project list of funding. Funding for OM at HWAD is provided through the contract between the Army and SOC. No specific funds are allocated/budgeted for OM projects. OM projects are conducted as needed depending on available funding.

1.7.6 Updating the INRMP

AR 200-1 requires installations to review their INRMPs annually (see Appendix I) and to revise them as necessary. Major revisions to the INRMP are to be undertaken every 5 years (HQDA 2007). Previous NEPA documentation should be assessed to ensure that the effects of the natural resources management practices in future INRMP updates have been adequately addressed.

1.8 Pending and Unresolved Issues

1.8.1 Pending Issues

None.

1.8.2 Unresolved Issues

None.

1.9 Regulatory and Jurisdictional Framework

1.9.1 Key Laws and Regulations

The preparation of this INRMP encompasses compliance with certain laws and EOs. For an INRMP to be valid, it must comply with applicable natural resource laws and with DoD directives, instructions, and Army policies.

As mentioned in Section 1.1, preparing this INRMP is in accordance with the provision of the Natural Resource Management on Military Lands Act of 1960 (16 U.S.C. 670 *et seq.*), commonly known as the Sikes Act. In addition, Chapter 3-7 of AR 200-1 (December 13, 2007) specifies Army policies and legal and other requirements, including statutes, laws, regulations, and other guidance applicable to the Army Natural Resources Management Program (HQDA 2007). Table 1-1, although not exhaustive, includes most of the legal requirements applicable to HWAD.

**Table 1-1.
Federal statutes, laws, and regulations applicable to natural resources
management on Army lands**

Authority	Summary
Archaeological and Historical Preservation Act, 16 U.S.C. 472A <i>et seq.</i>	Requires federal agencies to identify and recover data from archaeological sites threatened by their actions.
Archaeological Resources Protection Act, 16 U.S.C. 470aa-470ll	Requires permits and provides for civil and criminal penalties for persons disturbing archaeological resources on federal and tribal lands without a permit.
Clean Air Act, 42 U.S.C. 7401 <i>et seq.</i>	Regulates air emissions from stationary and mobile sources. Authorizes the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to establish National Ambient Air Quality Standards to protect public health and welfare and to regulate emissions of hazardous air pollutants.
CWA, 33 U.S.C. 1251 <i>et seq.</i>	Establishes the basic structure for regulating discharges of pollutants into waters of the United States and regulating quality standards for surface waters.

Table 1-1. (continued)

Authority	Summary
CWA, 33 U.S.C. 1344 <i>et seq.</i>	Authorizes EPA to establish a permit program to regulate the discharge of dredged or fill material into waters of the United States. Activities exempted from regulation include all those associated with the continuation of normal farming, forestry, and ranching practices.
Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act (CERCLA), 42 U.S.C. 9601 <i>et seq.</i>	Provides a federal Superfund to clean up uncontrolled or abandoned hazardous waste sites and accidents, spills, and other emergency releases of pollutants and contaminants into the environment. CERCLA gives EPA power to seek responsible parties for cleanup.
EO 11988: Floodplain Management	Directs all federal agencies to avoid, if possible, development and other activities in the 100-year base floodplain.
EO 11990: Protection of Wetlands	Directs all federal agencies to avoid, if possible, adverse effects on wetlands and to preserve and enhance the natural and beneficial values of wetlands.
EO 12088: Federal Compliance with Pollution Control Standards	Delegates responsibility to the head of each executive agency to ensure that all necessary actions are taken for the prevention, control and abatement of environmental pollution. The EO gives EPA the authority to conduct reviews and inspection to monitor federal facility compliance with pollution control standards.
EO 12898: Federal Actions to Address Environmental Justice in Minority Populations and Low-Income Populations	Requires each federal agency to make achieving environmental justice part of its mission by identifying and addressing, as appropriate, disproportionately high and adverse human health or environmental effects of its programs, policies, and activities on minority populations and low-income populations.
EO 13045: Protection of Children from Environmental Health Risks and Safety Risks	Requires each federal agency to prioritize, identify, and assess environmental health risks and safety risks that might disproportionately affect children and ensure its policies, programs, activities, and standard address disproportionate risks to children that result from environmental health or safety risks.
EO 13175: Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments	Requires agencies to consult with tribal officials regarding the need for federal standards and any alternatives that would limit the scope of federal standards or otherwise preserve the prerogatives and authority of Indian tribes.
ESA, 16 U.S.C. 1531 <i>et seq.</i>	Requires federal agencies, in consultation with USFWS or NMFS or both to ensure that actions they authorize, fund, or carry out are not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of any listed species or result in the destruction or adverse modification of designated critical habitat of such species. Prohibits any action that causes a <i>take</i> of any listed species.
Farmlands Protection Policy Act, 7 U.S.C. 4201	Authorizes US Department of Agriculture in cooperation with other departments, agencies, independent commissions, and other units of the federal government to develop criteria for identifying the effects of federal programs on the conversion of farmland to nonagricultural uses.
Federal Facility Compliance Act, 42 U.S.C. 6901	Requires federal facilities to comply with federal, state, and local environmental laws and regulations.

Table 1-1. (continued)

Authority	Summary
Federal Land Policy and Management Act of 1976, 43 U.S.C. 1701-1784	Governs the BLM in managing public lands to protect the quality of scientific, scenic, historical, ecological, environmental, air and atmospheric, water resource, and archaeological values that, where appropriate, will preserve and protect certain public lands in their natural condition; provide food and habitat; and outdoor recreation.
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act	Requires consultation with USFWS on actions affecting water resources.
Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act, 16 U.S.C. 2901	Authorizes financial and technical assistance to the states for development, revision, and implementation plans and programs for nongame fish and wildlife.
MBTA, 16 U.S.C 701-719c	Decrees that all migratory birds and their parts (including eggs, nests, and feathers) are fully protected.
NEPA, Public Law 91-90	Requires federal agencies to consider effects on the human environment from proposed action and to document environmental effects during project planning.
NHPA, 16 U.S.C. 470 <i>et seq.</i>	Requires agencies to identify historic properties subject to effect by their actions and to consult with the SHPO and others about alternatives and mitigation.
Noise Control Act of 1972, Public Law 92-574	Establishes a national policy to promote a noise-free environment through federal control of major sources of noise in commerce, while state and local governments have primary control over other aspects of noise generating sources.
Resource Conservation & Recovery Act (RCRA) of 1976, 42 U.S.C. 6901 <i>et seq.</i>	Authorizes EPA to control hazardous waste from cradle to grave through generation, transportation, treatment, storage, and disposal of hazardous waste.

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2 CURRENT CONDITIONS AND LAND USE

2.1 Military Mission

The mission of the U.S. Army is defined at 10 U.S.C. 3062(a): it is the intent of Congress to provide an Army that is capable, in conjunction with other armed forces of preserving the peace and security, and providing for the defense, of the United States, the territories, commonwealths, and possessions, and any areas occupied by the United States; supporting the national policies; implementing the national objectives; and overcoming any nations responsible for aggressive acts that imperil the peace and security of the United States.

HWAD's military mission is to test and demilitarize munitions, maintain equipment, and provided tenant support. Activities and resources the installation supports are

- Receive, store, and issue/ship conventional ammunition
- Demilitarize and dispose of unserviceable, obsolete, and surplus ammunition
- Renovate conventional ammunition
- Inspect conventional ammunition

HWAD is a Tier II facility storing war reserve ammunition to be used after the first 30 days and maintain designated ammunition in a state of readiness for mobilization, including assembly, or otherwise providing base unit materials (Michael Baker 2009). In addition to Army military and civilian personnel, HWAD has two active tenants: the U.S. Navy and the U.S. Marine Corps.

2.1.1 Ammunition Support

HWAD receives, stores, re-warehouses, preserves and packages, monitors, renovates, demilitarizes and disposes of conventional ammunition; issues conventional munitions; ensures capability to ship/receive containerized munitions; operates calibration lab, maintains an International Standards Organization container maintenance/repair facility and maintains an ammunition maintenance capability. HWAD has 2,904 ammunition storage structures including 2,428 igloos and 476 explosive warehouses, barricaded open sites, and inert warehouses (Michael Baker 2009).

2.1.2 Tenant Support

The U.S. Navy maintains a Naval Undersea Warfare Center (NUWC) Detachment at HWAD designated NAVUNSEAWARCEN DET, with the following missions:

- Renovate, assemble, maintain, segregate, and modify naval mines, mine components, test and support equipment
- Operate and maintain naval mine assembly facilities
- Maintain naval mines in the readiness condition assigned by the Naval Systems Command
- Maintain proper surveillance of mine material as required
- Support various service programs through the Combat Systems Logistical Center

The U.S. Marine Corps maintains an office at HWAD: the Naval Surface Warfare Center, Crane Division, Detachment Fallbrook, and master chief petty officer – Hawthorne, with the following missions:

- Operate the Marine Corps Ballistic and Component Test Facility
- Manage development, maintenance, and operation of the Lance Corporal Carter Test Range for expanded weapons systems, equipment and vehicle testing
- Perform and oversee testing associated with renovation and procurement of Marine Corps material

2.1.3 Training

HWAD no longer maintains an agreement with High Desert Special Operations Center, their contract with the Army ended in 2012. Since the explosion that took the lives of the Marines training in 2013, HWAD only has a few snipers working in the Old Bomb area with artillery limited to a 0.50 Barrett sniper rifle (Peterson, personal communication, 2013c)."

2.1.4 Mercury Storage

In 2010 the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) designated HWAD as the facility for the long-term management and storage of elemental mercury generated in the United States (DOE 2010). The Defense Logistics Agency Strategic Materials is responsible for the safe, secure, and environmentally sound stewardship of the mercury stockpile. The stockpile consists of approximately 4,436 metric tons of mercury. The stockpile was transferred to HWAD between September 2010 and March 2011 and is stored in 14 buildings. An MOA exists between the Defense National Stockpile Center and the U.S. Army Joint Munitions Command (Appendix D).

A hazard analysis conducted on the whole operation. The net explosive weight was reduced in the magazines in proximity of the mercury (Figure 2-1) of the buildings in the 110 group they are on a bias, this was done to limit the number of buildings that would have to be re-warehoused to accommodate the explosive arc, this is the area that would be affected if the buildings with ammunition exploded. They would not affect the mercury building with the reduced explosives as the mercury buildings are well outside the arc. They all have identification, and fire protection. This is a State approved site for mercury storage by NDEP (DOE 2010, DLA 2004).

HWAD Mercury Storage Area

Hawthorne Army Depot, Hawthorne, Nevada
Figure 2-1

LEGEND

- Hawthorne Army Depot
- Industrial Area
- Mercury Storage
- Building
- Hawthorne Army Depot
- Highway
- Street
- Railroad

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, ESRI

2.2 Operations and Activities

2.2.1 Relationship between the Military Mission and Natural Resources

The Army recognizes that a healthy and viable natural resources base is required to support the military mission. HWAD has 2,904 ammunition storage structures including 2,428 igloos and 476 explosive warehouses, barricaded open sites, and inert warehouses (Michael Baker 2009). Tenant activities at the installation consist of the operation of the Carter munitions test range and renovation, assembly, and maintenance of a naval mine assembly facility. A mercury stockpile of 4,436 metric tons is stored in 21,450 drums in 14 buildings on the northeast end of the installation. This INRMP ensures that environmental considerations are an integral part of planning at HWAD and those natural resources are protected in accordance with Army regulations and policies.

Ongoing military operations performed in support of the HWAD mission could alter the environmental setting and condition of natural resources. Ammunition storage at the installation poses a risk of explosive accidents and the associated nuisance noise and air disturbance. Elemental mercury storage on the site poses a threat to the human and natural environment if an accidental release occurs.

Existing natural resources on HWAD land can influence the manner in which the HWAD mission is executed. Although natural resources provide a safe environment for meeting mission requirements, their existence also can limit certain military support activities. For example, topographic features of the land or the presence of wetlands or threatened and endangered species might prevent military activities from occurring because of the potential for adverse effects on those sensitive resources. In addition, any permanent degradation of natural resources as a result of ongoing military use would, in turn, ultimately lead to further mission impairment if the proper conditions are no longer available. Therefore, proper management of natural resources and their use by the military is a sound environmental practice, and it directly supports the HWAD mission. This INRMP considers the effects of such natural resources on the mission. Examples of activities and their effects on the environment and examples of how degradation of natural resources affects the military mission are provided in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1.
Mission activities and potential effects

Activity/use	Potential effects on natural resources	Potential effects on HWAD mission
Ammunition Support	Loss of habitat Soil compaction and erosion	Contamination could limit additional storage Increased maintenance costs
Tenant and Training Activities	Loss of habitat Habitat degradation Soil compaction and erosion	Safety hazards during military operations Loss of training realism
Mercury Storage	Loss of habitat Soil compaction and erosion	Contamination could limit additional storage Increased maintenance costs

Implementing environmentally sound practices, and considering alternatives to those practices as they are developed, limits the potential for serious alterations to natural resources. In addition, such practices likely result in a more effective, long-term approach to natural resource protection and conservation. Presented below are examples of practices to avoid permanent and serious environmental degradation at HWAD.

2.2.1.1 Ammunition Support

Munition storage magazines and storehouses are throughout the installation. These buildings were constructed according to the guidelines for building construction and erosion susceptibility of various soil types found at HWAD. Constructing buildings in accordance with soil conditions reduces erosion and loss of soil throughout the installation.

2.2.1.2 Tenant and Training Activities

Tenant support building and associated operations are mostly in the western side of the installation near the town of Hawthorne. Concentrating these operations in one location minimizes the footprint of the installation, causing fewer disturbances to natural resources.

2.2.1.3 Mercury Storage

Mercury storage at HWAD is in 14 buildings in the northeast area of the installation. Concentrating the mercury storage in one area reduces the impacts to resources throughout the installation if an accidental spill occurs. A 2006 MOA between Defense National Stockpile Center and U.S. Army Joint Munitions Command outlines the handling and military support for storing elemental mercury at HWAD. The MOA is in Appendix D.

2.2.2 Future Military Impacts on Natural Resources

The INRMP is considered a living document that is based on several short-, medium-, and long-range planning goals. Short-range goals include activities that are planned to occur in the next 5 years, and medium-range goals are activities in a 6- to 10-year period. Long-range goals are usually scheduled beyond 10 years. Because the INRMP is a living document, goals could be revised to reflect evolving environmental conditions. In addition, medium- and long-range planning goals eventually become short-range activities that also require implementation.

The primary long-range planning goal at HWAD is to continue supporting the military mission while expanding and supporting environmental strategies and goals consistent with Army regulations and policies. With long-range planning goals in mind, HWAD has developed several short-range goals for the installation to support the current mission and meet future needs. To that end, this INRMP includes management measures that meet three short-range planning goals:

1. To implement a comprehensive environmental strategy that represents compliance, restoration, prevention, and conservation
2. To improve the existing management approach to protecting natural resources on the installation
3. To meet legal and policy requirements consistent with national natural resources management philosophies

2.3 Facilities and Developed Areas

HWAD is primarily semi-improved land consisting of scrub-shrub desert vegetation and mountainous vegetation surrounding the storage facilities. Developed areas are concentrated on the western side of the installation and include administrative buildings, buildings for tenant operations, and storage buildings.

2.3.1 Army Defense Environmental Restoration Program

The Army Defense Environmental Restoration Program at HWAD comprises the IRP, MMRP, and Compliance Restoration. Those programs are responsible for addressing soil, surface water, and groundwater pollution through remediation and monitoring, addressed through an IAP. The IAP contains the cleanup history, current site status, contaminants of concern at each site, response actions taken, past milestones, and future actions. The plan outlines the total multiyear cleanup for the installation and identifies environmental cleanup requirements at each area of concern and proposes a comprehensive, installation-wide approach with associated costs and schedules to conduct investigations and necessary remedial actions (HWAD 2012a).

2.3.2 Installation Restoration Program

The IRP focuses on identifying, investigating, and cleaning up Army lands contaminated before October 17, 1986, to eliminate unacceptable risks to human health and the environment. Installations can perform only those studies necessary to determine the need for remedial action, identify the remedial alternative, and implement the selected remedial action (U.S. Army 2004a).

IRP responses are carried out in accordance with the CERCLA as amended by the Superfund Amendments and Reauthorization Act, using the process described in the National Oil and Hazardous Substances Pollution Contingency Plan, 400 CFR Part 300, and if applicable, consistent with the substantive requirements of RCRA. The IRP also complies with state, regional, and local requirements that have been identified as applicable. Under the IRP, HWAD investigates and, if necessary, remediates former disposal and test areas (U.S. Army 2004a). As summarized in Table 2-2, HWAD has 129 sites under the IRP, 123 have been classified as *No Further Action* (NFA) needed, and an additional 6 sites remain active.

Table 2-2.
HWAD IRP sites

Site IRP status	Number of sites
NFA	123
Active (listed below with Site ID)	6
101-44 Impoundment (HWAAD-B04)	
BLDG 336: Fuel Storage Area (HWAAD-B24A)	
103-6 POL Pit (HWAAD-B26)	
103-16 Catchment Pit (HWAAD-B27A)	
49-10 Pit/Landfill #1 & #2 (HWAAD-I09)	
PBC (PBC @ Hawthorne)	

Source: HWAD 2012b

2.3.3 Military Munitions Response Program

Congress established the MMRP under the Defense Environmental Restoration Program on current and former defense sites to address UXO, discarded military munitions, and munitions constituents at concentrations high enough to pose an explosive hazard and potential environmental contamination. Munitions response includes investigation, removal, and remedial actions that address explosives safety, human health or environmental risks presented by UXO, discarded military munitions, and munitions constituents.

The *Program Management Manual* for MMRP was published in September 2009 and provides information, resources, and tools to implement the MMRP at U.S. Army active installations. The guide creates a prioritization system for the sites, establishes a funding program element for the program, and highlights those requirements that deviate from the established IRP. Munitions response actions will be conducted under the process outlined in the National Contingency Plan (40 CFR Part 300) as authorized by CERCLA (42 U.S.C. 9605).

HWAD completed a phase three Army range inventory (also known as the closed, transferred, or transferring inventory) in May 2003. The inventory identified 18 sites as eligible for the MMRP. The phase three inventory serves as the preliminary assessment under CERCLA. The site inventory was finalized in September 2009. A remedial investigation is underway for 13 MMRP sites. Five sites at HWAD are classified as NFA, and 13 sites are classified as active. A summary of the MMRP is in Table 2-3.

The primary goal of the MMRP site inventory is to collect enough information to determine the following:

- Whether a remedial investigation/feasibility study is required
- Whether an immediate response is necessary
- Whether the site qualifies for an NFA status

**Table 2-3.
HWAD MMRP sites**

Site MMRP status	Number of sites
NFA	5
Active (listed below with Site ID)	13
Walker Lake Water Test Range (HWAAP-001-R-01)	
Walker Lake Land Test Range (HWAAP-002-R-01)	
Old Bomb Rocket Firing Range-South (HWAAP-006-R-01)	
Walker Lake Land Test Range (HWAAP-008-R-01)	
ASROC Ranges (HWAAP-009-R-01)	
ASROC Ranges (HWAAP-010-R-01)	
Pre-1940 Detonating Pits (HWAAP-012-R-01)	
Pre-1940 Detonating Pits (HWAAP-013-R-01)	
Kickout Outside New Bomb Area (HWAAP-017-R-01)	
Mono Lake (HWAAP-018-R-01)	

Table 2-3. (continued)

Site MMRP status	Number of sites
Whiskey Flat (HWAAP-020-R-01)	
Walker Lake Water Test Range (HWAAP-021-R-01)	
Old Bomb Rocket Firing Range-East (HWAAP-022-R-01)	

Source: HWAD 2012b

2.3.4 Compliance-Related Cleanup

In April 2003, environmental restoration and Compliance Cleanup (CC) activities became unified under the Army Environmental Cleanup Strategy to create a unified cleanup program optimizing efficiency, accountability, and consistency by applying common objectives and requirements to all cleanup associated with past and current activities in support of installations and transforming the Army (U.S. Army 2004b).

The CC program includes actions to address contamination at overseas Army facilities; contamination resulting from operation that have occurred since October 1986 at Army Active, Excess, and Special installations, and Army National Guard federally owned facilities; and contamination at nonfederally owned, federally supported Army National Guard facilities. The CC mission is to perform appropriate, cost-effective cleanup to protect human health, safety, and the environment and to sustain operational readiness and training (U.S. Army 2004b).

As summarized in Table 2-4, HWAD has eight sites under the CC program. Two have been classified as NFA status, and six sites remain active.

**Table 2-4.
HWAD CC sites**

Site CC status	Number of sites
NFA	2
Active (listed below with Site ID)	6
Old Bomb Fenced Disposal Area (CCHWAAP-023)	
103-8/10 Oxidation Ditch (CCHWAAP-B27B)	
103-20 Surface Impoundment (CCHWAAP-B27C)	
103-41 Unlined Ponds (CCHWAAD-B29)	
Burn Pit @ pdo H02 (CCHWAAD-H02)	
101-42 Catchment Pit (CCHWAAD-I15)	

Source: HWAD 2012b

2.4 Vegetation

Native vegetation has been surveyed by several sources—the U.S. Army Environmental Health Agency, BLM (through The Nature Conservancy [TNC]), UNR, USFWS, and Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS). Tetra Tech has performed invasive species surveys to inventory

the extent of invasive species at HWAD. Appendix A also provides lists of plant species identified in Mineral County.

2.4.1 Vegetative Cover

HWAD is in Walker Lake Valley, a high-desert valley that trends north-northwesterly and is bordered by the Wassuk Range to the west and southwest and by the Gillis Range and Garfield Hills to the east and southeast. Adjacent to and northwest of the installation, Walker Lake occupies the topographic low point in the Walker Lake Valley. The valley floor of HWAD is dominated by shrubland and sparsely vegetated with grasslands. Pockets of woodland conifer and hardwood habitat are on Mount Grant along with shrubland. A variety of firs dominate the habitat on Mount Grant including pinyon-juniper forest communities and other hardwood communities composed of aspen, willow, and cottonwoods (Figure 2-2).

Vegetation and land cover at HWAD was mapped by use of geospatial data from the USGS Earth Resources and Observation Science Center. Existing vegetative cover information is presented in Figure 2-2 and Table 2-5. The installation is dominated by shrubland (73 percent) and conifer (17 percent) habitats. The remaining 10 percent consists of sparsely and nonvegetated areas, maintained grasslands, and other as detailed in Table 2-5.

Forest communities on the installation include primarily conifers. The dominant species are a wide variety of firs and the pinyon-juniper forest communities. Other hardwood forest communities are dominated primarily with aspen, willow, and cottonwoods.

**Table 2-5.
HWAD vegetative cover**

Vegetation classification	Percent coverage
Shrubland ^a	73%
Conifer ^b	17%
Nonvegetated ^c	3%
Agriculture ^d	2%
Grassland ^e	1%
Exotic Herbaceous ^f	< 1%
Developed	< 1%
Hardwood ^g	< 0.5%
Riparian ^h	< 0.5%
Conifer Hardwood ⁱ	< 0.05%

Notes:^a Big Sagebrush Shrubland and Steppe, Blackbrush Shrubland, Chaparral, Desert Scrub, Greasewood Shrubland, Low Sagebrush Shrubland and Steppe, Mountain Mahogany Woodland and Shrubland, Salt Desert Scrub

^b Douglan fir-Grand fir-White fir Forest and Woodland, Douglas fir-Ponderosa Pine-Lodgepole Pine Forest and Woodland, Juniper Woodland and Savanna, Limber Pine Woodland, Lodgepole Pine Forest and Woodland, Mountain Hemlock Forest and Woodland, Pinyon-Juniper Woodland, Ponderosa Pine Forest, Red Fir Forest and Woodland, Subalpine Woodland and Parkland

^c Barren, Open Water, Snow-ice

^d Irrigated Grassland, Pasture

^e Alpine Grassland, Transitional Herbaceous Vegetation, Recently Burned-Herbaceous

^f Introduced Upland Vegetation

^g Rocky Mountain Aspen Forest and Woodland, Mediterranean California Mixed Oak Woodland

^h Western Riparian Woodland and Shrubland

ⁱ Aspen-Mixed Conifer Forest and Woodland, Conifer-Oak Forest and Woodland

HWAD Vegetation
 Hawthorne Army Depot
 Hawthorne, Nevada
Figure 2-2

LEGEND

Hawthorne Army Depot	Conifer-Hardwood	Riparian
Agricultural	Grassland	Shrubland
Conifer	Developed	Sparsely Vegetated
	Exotic Herbaceous	Non-vegetated
	Hardwood	

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, USGS EROS, ESRI

2.4.2 Special-Status Plant Species and Habitats

No federally listed threatened or endangered plant species have been identified at HWAD. One state-listed species, the sand cholla (*Opuntia pulchella*) was identified by TNC in 2001 (Nachlinger 2003) but it is no longer listed as a protected species by the Nevada Natural Heritage Program (NNHP) (NNHP 2013). Additionally, several Nevada Natural Heritage species are native to the area: (1) Bodie Hills rock cress (*Arabis bodiensis*); (2) Bodie Hills draba (*Cusickiella quadricostata*); (3) Nevada oryctes (*Oryctes nevadensis*); (4) Nevada dune beardtongue (*Penstemon arenarius*); (5) Mono phacelia (*Phacelia monoensis*); (6) Masonic mountain jewelweed (*Streptanthus oliganthus*); and (7) the state-protected critically endangered Sodaville milkvetch (*Astragalus lentiginosus* var. *sesquimetralsis*) (USFWS 1997; NDOW 1997; NNHP 2013). Bodie Hills rock cress, gray wavewing (*Cymopterus cinerarius*), Beatley buckwheat (*Eriogonum beatleyae*), Alexander ocher-flowered buckwheat (*Eriogonum ochrocephalum* var. *alexanderae*), sand cholla, and Wassuk beardtongue (*Penstemon rubicundus*) were identified on HWAD lands in surveys conducted by TNC in 2000. The Sodaville milkvetch was not observed at HWAD, although eight other species of the genera *Astragalus*, including freckled milkvetch (*A. lentiginosus* var. *kennedyi*) were observed.

No known critical habitats, as defined by the USFWS, are on HWAD land holdings, although NNHP has indicated that Mount Grant might be considered a sensitive environment (NNHP 2003). Mount Grant is managed to conserve its balanced ecological state. Several sensitive habitats are within 100 miles of HWAD: (1) Toiyabe National Forest (within 20 miles southwest), (2) Stillwater Wildlife Refuge (about 60 miles north), (3) Mason Valley Wildlife Refuge (40 miles northwest), and (4) Yosemite National Park (about 60 miles southwest).

2.4.3 Invasive Species

Invasive species surveys conducted from September 2002 to December 2003 identified six target species including African rue (*Peganum harmala*), Russian knapweed (*Centaurea repens*), tamarisk (*Tamarix* sp.), scotch thistle (*Onopordum acanthium*), tall whitetop/perennial pepperweed (*Lepidium latifolium*), and whitetop/hoary cress (*Cardia draba*) (Tetra Tech 2004). Other species were also observed during those surveys and are presented in Appendix B. Efforts are being made to control the tamarisk growth along the perimeter of Walker Lake and the lower elevations of Mount Grant, including the release of Japanese beetles (*Popillia japonica*). Whitetop/hoary cress, potentially introduced by equipment used to control tamarisk, is being controlled through pesticide use (Appendix B).

2.5 Geology and Soils

2.5.1 Geology

HWAD in southwest Nevada is in the Great Basin section of the Basin and Range physiographic province. The majority of the HWAD facilities are specifically in the eastern half of the depot property in the Whiskey-Flat-Hawthorne subarea of Walker Lake Valley. Walker Lake Valley is a high-desert valley that trends north-northwesterly and is bordered by the Wassuk Range to the west and southwest and by the Gillis Range and Garfield Hills to the east and southeast. Just to the northwest of the main depot complex, Walker Lake occupies the topographic low point in the Walker Lake Valley. Walker Lake is a remnant of a glacial lake that once covered much of the northwestern Great Basin. Relief and topography across the 147,000-acre depot differ greatly. Elevations range from 11,329 feet msl at Mount Grant in the Wassuk Range in the far western portion of the depot property to about 3,960 feet msl just to the northwest of the depot facility complex along the shoreline of Walker Lake. Along the valley floor, where the main depot complex is, the topography is gently sloping (DLA 2004).

The east face of the Wassuk Range is an active fault scarp that has down-dropped the west side of the Walker Lake Valley relative to the east side. This fault roughly bisects HWAD. The fault is part of the regional Walker Lake fault zone. Faulting has occurred in the foothills bordering the depot (DLA 2004).

Geologic strata of the Walker Lake Basin and the Walker Lake Valley as a whole consist of unconsolidated alluvium (basin fill) that includes alluvial fan, floodplain, windblown channel and lake deposits, and terrace gravels and evaporates. While the maximum depth of the basin fill to bedrock is unknown, it is at least 1,008 feet according to well completion records for Hawthorne Utilities Well No. 5. Rocks of the Wassuk Range are principally granitic rocks dominated by quartz monzonite. Rocks of the Excelsior formation, which unconformably overlie the rocks of the Wassuk Range, are composed of metamorphosed volcanic rocks (e.g., flows, tuffs, breccias, basalt, and rhyolite) and sedimentary interbeds. The Excelsior formation is also exposed in the Garfield Hills to the southeast of the depot facility complex. Limestone of the Luning formation also occur southeast of the depot. Additionally, unaltered volcanic rocks are exposed in the vicinity of the depot (e.g., in the Garfield Hills) (DLA 2004).

2.5.2 Soils

NRCS characterized 76 soil types at HWAD (USDA SCS 1991). The five soil types occurring most frequently are the Inmo Association, the Granmount-Kiote-Hiridge Association, the Nupart-Kazan-Rock Outcrop Association, the Wassit-Ahchew Association, and the Patna Loamy Sand. This section briefly describes each of these five soil types. Most of the 76 soil types extend over less than 2 percent of HWAD acreage. Further detail regarding HWAD soils including land capability, wildlife habitat potential, and salinity is in the soil survey and the range site and range condition inventory (USDA SCS 1991).

The Inmo Association occurs on alluvial fan remnants and channels with 2 to 4 percent slopes (USDA SCS 1991). The Inmo Association is a very gravelly, loamy sand. This association, which occurs from 4,100 to 4,920 feet msl originated from a granite alluvium parent material. The Inmo Association is classified as a Typic Torriorthents, sandy-skeletal, mixed mesic.

The Granmount-Kiote-Hiridge Association occurs on north- and east-facing, slightly concave back slopes of mountains, and convex shoulders and back slopes of mountains with 15 to 50 percent slopes (USDA SCS 1991). Granmount is a very gravelly, fine, sandy loam. Kiote is a gravelly loam. Hiridge is a very gravelly, sandy loam. This association, which occurs from 7,800 to 10,800 feet msl, originated from a residuum and colluvium erosion of andesitic rock and altered andesitic rock. This association is classified as (1) Argic Cryoborolls, clayey-skeletal, mixed (Cranmount); (2) Argic Pachic Cryoborolls, loamy-skeletal, mixed (Kiote); and (3) Argic Cryoborolls, loamy-skeletal, mixed, shallow (Hiridge).

The Nupart-Lazan-Rock Outcrop Association occurs on north-facing and higher-elevation, south-facing back slopes of mountains with 50 to 75 percent slopes (USDA SCS 1991). Nupart is a very gravelly, loamy sand. Lazan is a very gravelly, coarse sand. The rock outcrops consist of about 20 percent of the association. This association, which occurs from about 5,580 to 8,800 feet msl, originates from residuum and colluvium erosion of granitic rock. This association is classified as (1) Entic Haploxerolls, sandy-skeletal, mixed, frigid, shallow (Nupart); and (2) Typic Xerorthents, sandy-skeletal, mixed, mesic, shallow (Lazan).

The Wassit-Ahchew Association occurs on side slopes of mountains with 30 to 50 percent slopes and steeper north-facing back slopes with 50 to 75 percent slopes (USDA SCS 1991). Wassit is a very stony, sandy loam. Ahchew is a very stony, fine, sandy loam. This association, which occurs from about 5,400 to 9,000 feet msl, originates from residuum and colluvium erosion of volcanic rock with volcanic ash. The soils in this association are classified as (1) Lithic Mollie Haploxerolls, loam-skeletal, mixed, frigid (Wassit); and (2) Xerollic Haplargids, loamy-skeletal, mixed, mesic, shallow (Ahchew).

The Patna Loamy Sand soil occurs on lake plain terraces with zero to 2 percent slopes (USDA SCS 1991). This soil, which occurs from 4,160 to 4,550 feet msl, originates from deposition of mixed lacustrine materials. This soil is classified as Typic Haplargids, coarse-loamy, mixed, and mesic.

2.6 Water Resources

Nevada is divided into 72 watersheds. HWAD is primarily in the Walker Lake watershed, with a small portion of the western edge of the property (in the Wassuk Mountain Range) in the East Walker watershed (EPA 2013). The following sections describe HWAD groundwater, surface water resources, water quality issues including standards and criteria, wastewater management, and stormwater management.

2.6.1 Groundwater

HWAD is almost entirely in the Walker Lake Valley groundwater basin, including the Industrial Area/Main Base; the North, Central, and South Magazines; Old and New Bomb Areas; Walker Lake; and most of Mount Grant. A small portion of HWAD, high in the Wassuk Mountain Range at the western edge of HWAD property on Mount Grant, is in the East Walker Area groundwater basin (Michael Baker 2009).

The Walker Lake Valley is a closed hydrogeologic basin, and groundwater losses are generally the result of evaporation and groundwater pumping. Groundwater gradients are directed toward the valley axis and Walker Lake, but this gradient might be modified locally by pumping. A small amount of groundwater is discharged to springs, and some could be lost through flow into the

older consolidated rocks. The groundwater depth varies from about 5 feet below ground surface on HWAD near the southern end of Walker Lake to about 200 feet in HWAD's Old Bomb Area (Michael Baker 2009).

The specific yield of the uppermost 100 feet of saturated material in the Walker Lake Valley is reported to average 10 percent and could be as high as 15 percent. The USGS has estimated the storage capacity of the aquifers in this area at approximately 900,000 acre-feet. Several wells near the town of Hawthorne and in the Whiskey Flats area have a saturated thickness exceeding 300 feet. The safe yield from the aquifer in the area is estimated to be 4,600 acre-feet per year. In 1966 the discharge rate for municipal and installation production wells was approximately 2,800 acre-feet per year (Michael Baker 2009).

The chemical quality of the groundwater at the edge of a closed basin, such as the Walker Lake Valley, is usually better than the groundwater in the central part of the basin. Water quality analyses of samples taken from potable water wells in Whiskey Flats and Well No. 5 in the town of Hawthorne, on the alluvial fan on the western part of the valley, have total dissolved solid (TDS) concentrations of approximately 500 and 400 milligrams per liter (mg/L), respectively (Michael Baker 2009). EPA's secondary drinking water standard for TDS is 500 micrograms per liter. Wells closer to Walker Lake are reported to have even higher TDS concentrations.

In the basin, groundwater quality data show consistently high sulfate and TDS concentrations at various locations. These levels are reported to frequently exceed the EPA secondary standards for drinking water. Several wells in the area also have concentrations of nitrates and fluorides that exceed drinking water standards. These same records indicate that the quality of the water did not deteriorate or change significantly between 1946 and 1966. Origins of poor water quality in the basin are unknown, but several natural sources are possible. The most important of these sources is evaporite deposits in the valley fill material related to the retreat of Lake Lahontan. Mineralized geothermal water at depth in the basin could contribute to groundwater salinity. High TDS could be caused by recharge from mineralized zones in the mountain blocks (Michael Baker 2009).

In addition, two groundwater plumes (containing nitrate and hydrocarbons) are south of Walker Lake and north of the HWAD North Magazine. These plumes do not pose a risk to the lake because of ongoing bioremediation projects and remediation of the sewer system (Michael Baker 2009).

The potable water supply source for HWAD varies seasonally. Approximately 90 percent of the water supply comes from surface water sources that feed into Black Beauty Reservoir, upgradient of potential contamination sources, between November and May. In the other months, the remaining 10 percent of water supply for HWAD is supplied by groundwater wells on the installation (Michael Baker 2009).

Seven groundwater wells are on HWAD. Wells No. 5 and 11 are being pumped by HWAD to augment the Black Beauty Reservoir. Water from the wells is treated with chlorine gas and stored in one of seven aboveground steel storage tanks throughout the installation. Both surface and groundwater are treated before distribution. Surface water is treated for bacteria, and Well No. 11 (groundwater) is treated for arsenic and fluoride (Michael Baker 2009).

Groundwater in the immediate area is a poor source of potable water, because it is high in mineral content, and the south Walker Lake basin has an underground geothermal source. However, HWAD pumps and uses it as a potable water source only during periods of peak water use in the

summer. Because of the high heavy metal content of the groundwater, HWAD heavily relies on the Mount Grant watershed for most of its potable water. When used, groundwater that has been heated by the geothermal source is cooled before being distributed to facilities. Groundwater and surface water that has excessive mineral content, specifically fluoride and arsenic, is either not used or is treated to comply with federal and state drinking water standards before it is distributed (Peterson, personal communication, 2012). HWAD recently completed a new groundwater treatment plant. This new water system is able to serve the maximum population, which is the population plus fire-fighting reserves (Michael Baker 2009). HWAD also has the town of Hawthorne in emergencies, or the town can feed out lines to HWAD.

The Army is working with the private sector and the Navy to develop a major geothermal project at HWAD, with the capability of producing 30 megawatts of clean energy. The geothermal power electric generation plant will be used to supply the installation with power. The fuel source for the plant will be naturally occurring underground steam and hot water. The plant will provide all required electric power to HWAD with the Army receiving revenues from excess energy sold to the grid. The plant was estimated to be completed in 2012, but as of April 2013, construction has not begun. Benefits to the Army include energy security, increased geothermal base, and a funding stream estimated at \$631 million per year or \$13.5 million over the next 25 years.

HWAD has a *Work Plan for Basewide Groundwater Monitoring Program* that describes the procedures and equipment used for sampling the groundwater monitoring wells in the long-term monitoring program at HWAD. The work plan lists the wells selected to be sampled in the long-term monitoring program and the frequency of sampling. The work plan is intended to present a standardized sampling method to be consistently applied for the duration of the sampling effort at HWAD (Plexus 2007).

2.6.2 Surface Water

HWAD is bounded by mountains and hills to the east and west, a low saddle to the south, and Walker Lake to the north. No perennial surface streams are along the valley floor, but seasonal runoff recharges the valley aquifers. The general direction of flows from the Wassuk Mountain Range across the installation is to the east and northeast. The installation captures water in a series of basins on major creeks on Mount Grant, which includes Cottonwood, Squaw, Rose, and House Creeks. The Garfield Hills, to the northeast of the installation, also generate water flows across the installation to the northwest toward Walker Lake.

The valley floor of HWAD's basin consists of a broad alluvial apron that is flanked by alluvial fans with slopes of up to 6 percent. The alluvial fans are created by sheet and channel erosion in the mountains, primarily resulting from intense local thunderstorms. Walker Lake Valley serves as the terminal point in the surface flow system. On the installation itself, dikes and ditches control surface water flows during intense local thunderstorms (Michael Baker 2009).

Surface water bodies flow over about 7.9 percent of depot grounds, excluding the Walker Lake area (Tetra Tech 1997). Mount Grant and Walker Lake surface water features are shown in (Figure 2-3) and are described below.

HWAD Surface Water Features
 Hawthorne Army Depot
 Hawthorne, Nevada
 Figure 2-3

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, ESRI

2.6.2.1 Mount Grant Watershed

The Mount Grant watershed consists of runoff water from rain, snow, and mountain springs. Enough water is generated to support a diverse desert ecosystem, supply HWAD with a primary, high-quality potable water source and supply a small amount of recharge to Walker Lake (Tetra Tech 1997).

In 2004, a climate monitoring station was installed at the request of the USFS. Mount Grant was chosen because of the ease of access to the summit with a gravel road, the area's high security, and HWAD's interest in high-elevation climate. Eighteen tidbit temperature data loggers were installed along the major slopes to the summit. The data loggers record the latitude, longitude, and elevation and record the temperature, time, and date at hourly intervals. The data loggers are picked up annually. One precipitation gage is installed at an elevation of 9,765 feet msl (Millar 2004).

Surface water in the Mount Grant watershed is a key natural resource for HWAD because it is the main water supply for military operations and readiness. A high quality of surface water is required to keep treatment and cost to a minimum. Other than chlorinating, surface water supply receives no additional treatment before being used by the base. To maintain this high standard, the military has restricted grazing and public access to the watershed since the late 1920s. Consequently, a large area on Mount Grant has been viewed as a baseline area for comparison with similar terrestrial ecological systems subject to grazing management elsewhere (TNC 2003).

The Mount Grant surface water resource at HWAD consists of seven creeks and numerous springs on the mountain, including Cat Creek, Cottonwood Creek, Dutch Creek, House Creek, Lapon Creek, Rose Creek, and Squaw Creek. Two creeks in the watershed are not part of the surface water system—Lapon Creek, which flows west away from HWAD, and east flowing Dutch Creek with privately owned water rights (TNC 2003). In recent years, House Creek has not provided enough water to contribute to the drinking water supply (Tetra Tech 1997). Surface waters from Cottonwood, Squaw, Rose, and Cat Creeks are collected in a chain of open catch basins, weirs, and diversions and conveyed by pipe to three storage reservoirs: Cat Creek, Rose Creek, and Black Beauty. The watershed runoff feeds into Cat Creek and Rose Creek Reservoirs, and in turn into Black Beauty Reservoir. An underground tank, known as Station Reservoir, is fed by Black Beauty Reservoir or Well No. 11, a hot water well (Michael Baker 2009).

The water distribution system connects the reservoirs and elevated storage tanks, providing water for the fire protection system, irrigation system, industrial uses, and potable water supplies. Currently, 500,000 gallons of surface water is available per day (24-hour period). Each of the water towers at HWAD has a 50,000-gallon tank. To maintain the public golf course, between 650,000 to 700,000 gallons of water are used per day. In training periods, about 50,000 gallons of water are used per month. Black Beauty and Station Reservoirs are treated with chlorine to comply with drinking water regulations before it is distributed to storage tanks on the installation. The quality of the water is monitored three times a week and more frequently if the quality is suspect (CH2MHill 2007). HWAD recently installed a 500,000-gallon-per-day filtration facility near Black Beauty Reservoir. The treated water is distributed in belowground mild steel, cast iron, ductile iron, PVC, or asbestos concrete transmission lines using gravity flow to one of the seven aboveground steel storage tanks on the installation. Station Reservoir typically feeds the Main Base Area and will feed the Magazine Area when HWAD is not using any surface water. HWAD recently activated two 500,000-gallon treated water storage tanks (Michael Baker 2009).

The HWAD potable water supply source varies seasonally. From November to about May, about 99 percent of the water is from surface water sources that are upgradient from any potential contamination areas at HWAD. Those sources feed in to Black Beauty Reservoir. For the remaining months, the Black Beauty Reservoir surface water sources are augmented by groundwater. It is estimated that the groundwater supply has never provided more than 40 percent of the total makeup water in drier months. The water supply system depends more heavily on surface water from the reservoirs and less on groundwater from the wells (URS 2009).

Potable water is a scarce resource in the area. Mount Grant watershed is the only surface water source in the immediate area that is not contaminated with giardiasis (*Giardia lamblia*) and that generally has levels of TDS that are low enough for it to be a potable water source. As noted, groundwater in the area is a limited potable water sources because of high mineral content and an underground geothermal source, and Walker Lake (as described in the following section) is not a feasible source of potable water because of water quality and quantity issues (Tetra Tech 1997). Therefore, HWAD has taken steps to protect and limit access to the diversion basins and the land in the Mount Grant watershed used for the water supply. Access is restricted to Rose Creek and Cat Creek Reservoirs by locked gates on the roads leading to them. Black Beauty Reservoir is protected by a tall chain-link fence topped with barbed wire (URS 2009). The management and maintenance of the water system includes a monitoring schedule to ensure that water quality parameters meet water quality criteria, the water system operates without failure, the water system operates reliably, and repair of aging or broken mechanisms is completed before the watershed and potable water supply are adversely affected.

HWAD has an *Operation and Maintenance Manual for the Potable Water Systems* that provides detailed instructions on the water system maintenance in the Mount Grant watershed. Table 2-6 includes the checklist of water quality parameters tested and specific items inspected.

Table 2-6.
Watershed monitoring schedule

Parameter	Duration
Turbidity throughout the watershed	Three times per week ^a
Inlet screens (for debris)	Three times per week ^a
Damage to piping or creek beds	Three times per week ^a
Dead animals	Three times per week ^a
Damage to fence line	Three times per week ^a
Algae growth	Three times per week ^a
Unauthorized entrance, such as by transients	Three times per week ^a
Anything potentially hazardous to potable water system	Three times per week ^a
Weir	Three times per week ^a
Turbidity before chlorination	Continuous ^b
Disinfected water temperature	Continuous

Table 2-6. (continued)

Parameter	Duration
Disinfected water pH	Continuous
Disinfectant contact time	Daily
Residual disinfectant concentration upon entering reservoir and exiting reservoir	Continuous

Source: DZHC, no date (as cited in CH2MHill 2007)

Notes:

^a Increase frequency of monitoring with weather events that could increase turbidity, such as wind or rainstorms.

^b When turbidity levels are greater than one nephelometric turbidity unit, the reservoir is bypassed, and the water is discharged to Walker Lake rather than distributed to the drinking water system.

2.6.2.2 Walker Lake

The southern one-third of Walker Lake is within HWAD boundaries. Walker Lake has an area of about 38,000 acres and a capacity of approximately 3 million acre-feet (Michael Baker 2009). The lake receives inflow from the Wassuk and Gillis Mountain ranges and is fed by the Walker River from the north and west. The lake is a remnant terminal lake that dropped about 80 percent in volume in the 20th century (Tetra Tech 1997). The water level of the lake is declining because of upstream water use, diversions of runoff for irrigation north of the lake, and because surface runoff after a rainfall or snowmelt rarely reaches the lake because of the arid climate and diversions. Water from the Walker River is diverted to the agricultural activity occurring northwest of Walker Lake and in California. The water level of the lake has been declining, on average 1.7 feet per year (4,020 feet in 1940 to 3,956 feet in January 1979). Between 1950 and 1979, the lake level declined by 44 feet, and the south shoreline of Walker Lake receded at a rate of approximately 230 feet per year. Greater than normal snowfall in the Sierra Nevada Mountains in the 1998 and 1999 snow seasons slightly raised the lake's water level above the level of the early 1990s (Michael Baker 2009). Walker Lake water levels fluctuated in its prehistory, and research indicates that Walker Lake was dry for about 4,000 years in the Holocene period (Tetra Tech 1997).

The lake's water quality is poor. The climate and low volume of recharge increased the salinity to levels that threaten the aquatic health and eliminate its potential for use as a potable water source. Since 1994, HWAD attempts to divert an annual average of 1 million gallons of water from the Mount Grant watershed to the lake to offset the loss of the lake recharge source, which was mainly Walker River. Although the discharge of excess surface water from Mount Grant helps to offset the lack of water collected in Walker Lake, note that annual evaporation in the area is 130,000 acre-feet per year, and Mount Grant generates less than 15,000 acre-feet per year. Consequently, the surface water at Mount Grant is not a feasible remedy for the receding lake levels. The drop in water level has exposed a beachfront area along the lake's southern shore. Walker Lake supports a very limited number of species because of the toxicity to most aquatic biota from the high concentrations of TDS ranging from 20,000 to 50,000 mg/L, which has extirpated the LCT. As a result, fishing in Walker Lake is prohibited.

HWAD does not actively use Walker Lake or the adjoining beachfront. However, from the 1940s to the 1970s, the southern end of the lake was a backdrop for a munitions test range and poses a UXO hazard. A biological assessment conducted in 1995 concluded that contaminants from past munitions testing did not remain in the water, sediment, or fish tissue samples from Walker Lake.

The exposed beach area is routinely surveyed, and identified UXO are either removed or detonated (Tetra Tech 1997).

2.6.2.3 Floodplains

Most of the installation (including Mount Grant, the New Bomb Area, the majority of the North, Central, and South Magazines, and the western half of the Industrial Area/Main Base) is in an Area designated Zone D on the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Flood Insurance Rate Map (Figure 2-4). Zone D contains areas with possible, but undetermined, flood hazards, where no flood hazard analysis has been conducted. However, FEMA maps indicate a Flood Zone A for Walker Lake; Zone AO along the southern boundary of the lake; and Zone X500 extending from the southern boundary of Walker Lake along the western portion of the North Magazine to Route 95 and Thorne Road, east of the Industrial Area/Main Base. The eastern half of the Industrial Area/Main Base is Flood Zone A. Also a Zone A is associated with Corey Creek that runs along the western edge of the South and Central Magazines along US 359 and Mine Road. A small area designated as Zone X is south of the Industrial Area/Main Base and along the western edge of the South Magazine. The FEMA flood zones and descriptions are in Table 2-7).

**Table 2-7.
FEMA flood zones**

Zone	Description	Acreage on HWAD
A	Areas with annual probability of flooding of 1 percent or greater, subject to 100-year flood. Because detailed hydraulic analyses have not been performed, no Base Flood Elevations or flood depths are shown. Mandatory flood insurance purchase requirements and floodplain management standards apply.	13,163
AE	Areas with annual probability of flooding of 1 percent or greater, subject to 100-year flood, with base flood elevation determined. Mandatory flood insurance purchase requirements and floodplain management standards apply.	117
AO	Areas with annual probability of flooding of 1 percent or greater, subject to 100-year shallow flooding (usually sheet flow on sloping terrain) where average depths are between one and three feet. Average flood depths derived from detailed hydraulic analyses are shown in this zone. Mandatory flood insurance purchase requirements and floodplain management standards apply. Some Zone AOs have been designated in areas with high flood velocities such as alluvial fans and washes. Communities are encouraged to adopt more restrictive requirements for these areas.	11
D	Areas with possible but undetermined flood hazards. No flood hazard analysis has been conducted. Flood insurance rates are commensurate with the uncertainty of the flood risk.	126,834
X	Area of minimal flood hazard, usually above the 500-year flood level with annual probability of flooding of less than 0.2 percent. Are also used to designate base floodplains of lesser hazards, such as areas protected by levees from 100-year flood, or shallow flooding areas with average depths of less than one foot or drainage areas less than 1 square mile.	1,344
X500	Area with annual probability of flooding of 0.2 to 1 percent, between the limits of the 100-year and 500-year floods.	4,565

Source: FEMA 2012; Palm Beach County 2013

HWAD FEMA Flood Zones
 Hawthorne Army Depot
 Hawthorne, Nevada
 Figure 2-4

LEGEND

Hawthorne Army Depot	AE	X
Flood Zone A	AO	D
Flood Zone	0.2% Annual Chance Flood Hazard	

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, FEMA 2012, ESRI

2.6.3 Water Quality

2.6.3.1 Standards and Criteria

Nevada designates beneficial uses and applicable water quality standards and criteria to all natural streams and lakes, reservoirs or impoundments on natural streams, and other specified waterways in the state (unless excepted on the basis of existing irreparable conditions that preclude such use). The water quality standards for Nevada are in the Nevada Administrative Code (NAC), Chapter 445A.118–445A.2234 (NAC 2012; NDEP BWQP 2012; DOE 2010).

The NAC contains two types of water quality standards, narrative and numeric. The narrative standards are applicable to all surface waters of the state and consist mostly of statements requiring waters to be *free from* various pollutants including those that are toxic. The numeric standards for conventional pollutants cover most water bodies in Nevada with water body-specific numeric standards. These standards include both criteria designed to protect the beneficial uses and antidegradation requirements (NDEP BWQP 2012).

In the vicinity of HWAD, Cottonwood, Rose, and Squaw Creeks on Mount Grant are designated Class A waters. Class A waters are in areas of little human habitation, no industrial development, or intensive agriculture, where the watershed is relatively undisturbed by human activity. The beneficial uses of Class A waters are municipal or domestic supply, or both, with treatment by disinfection only; aquatic life; propagation of wildlife; irrigation; watering of livestock; and contact and noncontact recreation (NAC 445A.124) (DOE 2010).

The water quality standards for Walker Lake are listed in Table 2-8. Walker Lake, in its entirety, is on Nevada’s 2006 303(d) List of Impaired Waters. This list is a CWA section 303(d) requirement, which requires states to develop a list of water bodies needing additional work beyond existing control to achieve or maintain water quality standards (Michael Baker 2009). The specific water quality standards and beneficial uses of Walker Lake are defined in NAC 445A.1914. Designated beneficial uses for Walker Lake include contact and noncontact recreation; propagation of wildlife; and propagation of aquatic life (NAC 2012; DOE 2010).

**Table 2-8.
Water quality standards for Walker Lake**

Parameter	Requirements to maintain existing higher quality	Water quality standards for beneficial uses	Beneficial uses
Temperature ^a Single value	—	$\Delta T \leq 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Propagation of aquatic life
pH Single value	—	Within range 6.5–9.7 standard units	Propagation of aquatic life, recreation involving contact with the water and propagation of wildlife.
Dissolved oxygen ^b Single value	—	$\geq 5 \text{ mg/L}$	Propagation of aquatic life, recreation involving contact with the water, recreation not involving contact with the water, and propagation of wildlife.

Table 2-8. (continued).

Parameter	Requirements to maintain existing higher quality	Water quality standards for beneficial uses	Beneficial uses
Suspended solids Single value	--	≤ 25 mg/L	Propagation of aquatic life.
Nitrogen species (as N) Single value Single value	Total inorganic nitrogen ≤ 0.3 mg/L	Nitrate ≤ 90 mg/L Nitrite ≤ 0.06 mg/L	Propagation of aquatic life and propagation of wildlife.
Total ammonia (as N) – mg/L	—	varies ^c	Propagation of aquatic life.
Total phosphorus (as P) Single value	—	≤ 0.82 mg/L	Propagation of aquatic life.
<i>E. coli</i> – No./100 mL Annual geometric mean Single value	— —	≤ 126 ≤ 235	Recreation involving contact with the water and recreation not involving contact with the water.

Source: NAC, Chapter 445A.1914

Notes:

^a Maximum allowable increase in temperature above water temperature at the boundary of an approved mixing zone.^b When the lake is stratified, the dissolved oxygen applies only to the epilimnion.^c The ambient water quality criteria for ammonia are specified in NAC 445A.118.

2.6.3.2 Wastewater Management

Septic tanks are used in the HWAD magazine areas. Mineral County leases a sewer treatment plant with U.S. Army-owned, lined, treatment-holding ponds in HWAD's WADF, which is just south of Walker Lake and at the very northern end of the North Magazine area. All WADF facilities are tied into the sewer system. Leachfields are used in the magazine areas as well.

The main base area connects to the Mineral County system. The main base feeds into the county system via 8- to 15-inch pipelines. The Army installed these pipelines in the early 2000s and pays the county for sewer services. HWAD generates approximately 40,000 to 50,000 gallons of sewage per day (Michael Baker 2009).

2.6.3.3 Stormwater Management

Dikes and ditches control surface water flows on HWAD during intense thunderstorms. HWAD has an SWPPP, an ORCP, and an SPCCP in place that address its management of installation stormwater and spills or leaks to prevent contamination of surface water and groundwater resources.

The SWPPP identifies sources of pollution that could affect the quality of stormwater discharges associated with HWAD's industrial activities. Identified areas at HWAD where industrial activities might discharge pollutants in stormwater are outdoor storage, fueling stations, vehicle/equipment maintenance facilities/motor pools, wash rack areas, loading facilities, landfills, solid waste management units, aboveground and belowground storage tanks, indoor

storage areas, and hazardous waste storage facilities. The SWPPP also describes the practices used to reduce the pollutants in stormwater discharges associated with HWAD's industrial activity and to ensure compliance with the terms and conditions of HWAD's National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System General Industrial Permit, #NVR050000 dated April 16, 2008.

HWAD operations use large quantities of POL products, such as fuels and lubricants. HWAD prepared an ORCP in accordance with the regulations described in 40 CFR Parts 109 and 112. It describes the emergency organization and anticipated responses to spills, fires, explosions, or other emergencies involving these materials.

HWAD's SPCCP, prepared in accordance with 40 CFR 112.7, is required for owners and operators of facilities that gather, store, process, transfer, distribute, use, or consume oil and oil products and could discharge oil in quantities that could be harmful to navigable waters of the United States, or adjoining shorelines or water of the contiguous zone, or affecting certain natural resources. HWAD has more than the required quantity of greater than 1,320 gallons of POL that could affect navigable waters or natural resources. The SPCCP addresses how HWAD handles various types of facility drainage (Michael Baker 2009).

2.7 Wetlands

HWAD is in an arid climate with few wetland ecosystems. The wetlands on HWAD property are primarily adjacent to stream and spring depressions on Mount Grant watershed and the vegetated edges of Walker Lake. Figure 2-5 illustrates the surface water and potential wetland areas on HWAD that the USFWS delineated in 1999.

The installation has 710 acres of wetlands, 10,520 acres of deepwater habitat, and 314 acres of riparian habitat. This equates to approximately 8 percent of the installation's area. Palustrine emergent wetlands represent approximately 60 percent of the installation's wetlands. Linear wetlands and riparian habitat totaled 366.2 miles including rivers, streams, and vegetated habitats. Over half of the linear map features depicted on the maps are intermittent stream beds that are intermittently flooded (USFWS 1999). Table 2-9 identifies the type of wetland and associated acreage with each major habitat.

HWAD Wetlands
 Hawthorne Army Depot
 Hawthorne, Nevada
 Figure 2-5

- LEGEND**
- Lacustrine Deepwater Habitat
 - Palustrine Emergent
 - Palustrine Forested
 - Palustrine Deepwater Habitat
 - Palustrine Scrub-Shrub
 - Palustrine Unconsolidated Bottom
 - Palustrine Unconsolidated Shore
 - Riverine
 - Riparian Habitat
 - Hawthorne Army Depot

Source: HWAD GIS 2012, ESRI

Table 2-9.
Wetland habitats on HWAD

Wetland type	Acres	Percentage
Palustrine wetlands		
Emergent wetland	433.3	61.0%
Scrub-shrub wetland	161.2	22.7%
Unconsolidated shore	75.3	10.6%
Unconsolidated bottom	38.5	5.4%
Forested wetland	1.9	<1%
Total palustrine wetlands	710.2	100.0%
Deepwater habitats		
Lacustrine unconsolidated bottom	10519.9	99.9%
Lacustrine unconsolidated shore	6.9	<1%
Total deepwater habitat	10,526.8	100.0%
Riparian habitats		
Scrub-shrub mixed deciduous	101.2	34.9%
Forested mixed deciduous	74.7	25.7%
Forested aspen	60.3	20.8%
Emergent	46.1	15.9%
Scrub-shrub willow	3.4	1.2%
Scrub-shrub Russian olive	2.7	<1%
Scrub-shrub salt cedar	1.8	<1%
Total riparian habitat	290.2	100.0%
Total wetland and riparian habitat	11,527.2	100.0%

Source: USFWS 1999

Table 2-10 lists the plant species are indicative of the type of wetland plant species identified on HWAD. Table 2-11 lists examples of the dominant species in each wetland habitat type and common associates.

Table 2-10.
Wetland plant species identified on HWAD

Plant type	Common name	Scientific name
Trees		
	Aspen	<i>Populus tremuloides</i>
	Fremont cottonwood	<i>Populus fremontii</i>
	Russian olive	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i>
Shrubs		
	Coyote willow	<i>Salix exigua</i>
	Groundsel	<i>Senecio</i>
	Mohave rose	<i>Rosa mohavenis</i>
	Rabbitbrush	<i>Chrysothamus nauseosus</i>
	Red osier dogwood	<i>Cornus stolonifera</i>
	Sagebrush	<i>Artemisia tridentate</i>
	Salt cedar	<i>Tamarix pentandra</i>

Table 2-10. (continued)

Plant type	Common name	Scientific name
Shrubs	Shadescale	<i>Atriplex confertifolia</i>
	Willow	<i>Salix</i> sp.
Herbs		
	Baltic rush	<i>Juncus balticus</i>
	Bluegrass	<i>Poa</i> sp.
	Cattail	<i>Typha angustifolia</i>
	Cinquefoil	<i>Potentilla</i> sp.
	Foxtail	<i>Alopercurus</i> sp.
	Foxtail barley	<i>Hordeum jubatum</i>
	Hardstem bulrush	<i>Scirpus acutus</i>
	Richardson's rush	<i>Juncus alpinus</i>
	Rocky mountain iris	<i>Iris missouriensis</i>
	Rush	<i>Juncus</i> sp.
	Saltgrass	<i>Distichlis spicata</i>
	Sedge	<i>Carex</i> sp.
	Water sedge	<i>Carex aquatilis</i>
	Water starwort	<i>Callitriche nuttallii</i>
	Wild rye	<i>Elymus cinerea</i>
	Woodrush	<i>Luzula</i> sp.
	Yarrow	<i>Achillea</i> sp.
	Yellow monkey flower	<i>Mimulus longiflorus</i>

Source: USFWS 1999

Table 2-11.
Wetland habitats and associated species

Wetland type (Map code)	Dominant species	Common associates
Palustrine forested, wetland, temporarily flooded (PFO1A)	Fremont cottonwood	Russian olive, Willow, Mohave rose
Palustrine, scrub-shrub, wetland, seasonally flooded (PSS1C)	Willow	Rose, Bluegrass
Palustrine scrub-shrub, wetland temporarily flooded (PSS2A)	Salt cedar	Saltbush
Palustrine emergent, wetland, saturated (PEM1B)	Water sedge	Foxtail barley, Baltic rush, Rocky mountain iris, Bluegrass
Palustrine emergent, wetland, seasonally flooded (PEM1C)	Saltgrass	Foxtail barley, Baltic rush, water starwort
Riparian, lotic, forested, deciduous, aspen (Rp1FO6AS)	Russian olive	Freemont cottonwood, Salt cedar, Willow
Riparian lentic, scrub-shrub, deciduous salt cedar (Rp2SS6SC)	Salt cedar	Russian olive

Source: USFWS 1999

2.8 Wildland Fires and Prescribed Burns

Wildland fires are a threat to the species and ecological systems of the Great Basin, and they are a uniquely and extremely dangerous hazard to HWAD because of the installation's activities as a Tier II ammunition facility. HWAD has agreements with the Mineral County Office of Emergency Management, Nevada Division of Forestry, and the BLM concerning the prevention and control of wildland fires. HWAD has implemented management strategies such as mechanically removing woody fuels and conducting prescribed burns to reduce fire potential to minimize the occurrence/recurrence of uncontrolled fires (Nachlinger 2003). However, if an uncontrolled fire occurs, the first priority of wildland fire management is protecting the structures of the ammunition storage magazines, followed by protecting personal property, public utilities, watershed, and animal habitat (DZB 1994).

All wildland fires at HWAD are managed under the incident command system. Guidance for wildland fire emergencies and prevention at HWAD is detailed in the *Wildland Fire Response* (DZB 1994), the *Fire Prevention Manual* (DZHC 1996), and the *Emergency Response Plan* (DZHC 1996). A revised emergency response plan was being prepared during this INRMP update. The manuals describe the activities of a wildland fire response. HWAD also has a 2010 MOA with the Mineral County Office of Emergency Management for mutual aid in responding to wildland fires and other incidents (e.g., firefighting, emergency medical services, hazardous materials incidents, and rescues). A 2006 Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement specifies the command structure, annual operating plan, and payment between HWAD and the cooperating agencies (USFS, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and the BLM Carson City District) to help manage wildland fires occurring on the installation (Appendix D). HWAD is highly susceptible to wildland fires because of the vegetation and climate, so HWAD minimizes the recurrence of uncontrolled fires by posting warning signs during high-risk seasons, restricting open fires, regulating the use of fire and spark-producing tools, and requiring all recreational users to read and sign a wildland fire warning restriction permit (DZHC 1996).

The purpose of those manuals is to provide guidance for preventing as many fires as possible, controlling fires that do start and are burning out of prescription, and minimizing the size and destructiveness of fires that start and become large in spite of efforts to control them. If the wildland fire is determined to be larger than the resources available at HWAD, it should be reported to the Nevada Division of Forestry or the BLM (DZB 1994). Appendix D contains wildland fire and emergency management documents.

HWAD maintains a 2006 MOA with the WRPT for HWAD to provide emergency support, training, and for advance notice of train movement and unusual hazards with respect to HWAD's transportation of ammunition and explosives and other materials and equipment via railroad/highway through the Walker River Paiute Reservation. HWAD also has a 2004 MOU with the Mineral County Sheriff's Office for emergency management; and a 2004 MOA with Mount Grant General Hospital for emergency management. The MOAs, MOUs, and cooperative agreements are in Appendix D.

2.8.1 Personnel Responsibilities

The HWAD fire chief is responsible for the entire fire prevention and protection program. Wildland fire management and protection at HWAD is the responsibility of the HWAD Fire Department in accordance with the installation's fire regulations.

Working agreements are in place with Mineral County Fire Department that allow for reciprocal aid to be provided to HWAD as authorized by a representative of the HWAD Fire Department or Mineral County Fire Department. The HWAD fire chief is responsible for obtaining and maintaining documentation of those agreements.

2.8.2 Wildland Fire Management

This section describes the various assessments and actions necessary to properly manage and combat wildland fires occurring on the installation.

Initial Size-Up

Immediately after the occurrence and detection of a wildland fire, these actions are initiated:

- HWAD Fire Department responds
- Conduct a fire size-up
- Command staff at the incident consider need for additional resources and mutual aid

Once arriving at the scene, the senior Fire Department officer initiates the Incident Command System, assesses the fire, initiates attack of the fire, and informs the alarm dispatcher of the size of the fire.

Risk Assessment and Analysis

Assessment of wildland fires and predictions of how the fire will behave are necessary to ensure that HWAD personnel take the correct actions in addressing the fire. Short-term predictions of fire behavior are used in the initial assessment process to provide the following:

- Estimates of fire size and shape at a given time
- Determinations of resource needs, production rates, and requirements
- Placement of resources
- Estimates of fire behavior under differential weather patterns
- Estimates of ignition patterns, including spotting
- Developing prescriptions through historical weather records

One of the main factors in wildland fire risk assessment is determining the fuel available where the fire occurs.

Suppression Alternatives

After a fire has been detected and assessed, HWAD works with cooperating agencies to determine which of the following suppression alternatives to use:

- The Confine Alternative limits the spread of the fire in a prescribed area by using natural or preconstructed barriers. This alternative is the least aggressive method of suppression and is normally associated with fires burning in prescribed wildland fire behavior parameters. Weather and fuel conditions must indicate that the fire will remain in prescription for this alternative to be used.

- The Contain Alternative surrounds the fire with a control line as needed. This alternative allows for a flexible fire line extension. Weather and fuel conditions must indicate that the fire will remain in prescription for this alternative to be used.
- The Control Alternative uses an aggressive initial attack on a wildland fire that is burning out of prescription or is likely to get out of prescription. An aggressive control method is used when there is any doubt to how a fire will behave, or when the fire has a potential that is assessed as medium, high, or project potential.

2.9 Agricultural Grazing and Outleasing

No public grazing lands or agricultural grazing leases exist. HWAD prohibits grazing because of incompatibility with the installation's land use, operations and activities, mission security issues, environmental considerations, and strict water quality controls.

HWAD lands and resources are outleased for utility lines, water lines, and associated easements; Walker Lake Golf Course; and an easement for aerial crossing. In 1999 HWAD land was sold (excessed) for the Babbitt housing development and deeded to Mineral County (Hawthorne). Babbitt was demolished in 2003. HWAD has no additional plans to outlease property.

2.10 Fish and Wildlife

The purpose of fish and wildlife management is to establish sound conservation practices and policies to guide personnel in integrating the management of fish and wildlife resources with the military mission. The objective of fish and wildlife management is to use an ecosystem approach that emphasizes the management of entire ecosystems and communities, rather than the traditional, single-species management approach for planning fish and wildlife conservation practices in projects at HWAD.

NDOW's Nevada Wildlife Action Plan (WAP) was updated March 1, 2013 and serves as a comprehensive, landscape level plan, identifying the species of greatest conservation need and the key habitats on which they depend, with the intent to prevent wildlife species from becoming threatened or endangered. The WAP contains a conservation strategy to provide guidance to successfully conserve Nevada's key habitats and priority species. This conservation strategy has been designed for each key habitat, consisting of goals written in terms of desired landscape conditions, directional objectives (e.g. increase, decrease, maintain) that are measurable with respect to their overall trend by the end of the planning period and suggested management actions that could significantly contribute toward the movement of the objectives into the desired direction.

HWAD contains two of the 120 statewide Wildlife Management *Focal Areas* including the Wassuk Range and Walker Lake. Focal Areas provide information about the location of biologically diverse areas in Nevada, highlights landscapes containing endemic species, and recognizes important areas identified in prior conservation planning efforts. The 2013 WAP is at http://www.ndow.org/Nevada_Wildlife/Conservation/Nevada_Wildlife_Action_Plan/ (NDOW 2013).

2.10.1 Fisheries Management

Fish and benthos resources at HWAD are limited at Walker Lake because of the arid climate, the lake's high salinity, and reduced freshwater inflows. A diverse benthic community exists on Mount Grant because no fish inhabit the streams, and cattle are restricted from accessing the streams and stream banks. Appendix A lists the fish and primary benthos identified at HWAD.

A benthic invertebrate species survey was conducted on Mount Grant in 1979, which identified 82 aquatic macroinvertebrate species (Tetra Tech 1997). Mayfly (*Ironodes*) and caddisfly (*Wormaldia* sp.) genera were the most abundant macroinvertebrates. When the streambeds and wetlands dry out in the summer, the benthic community becomes dormant and survives in an egg or larval stage. Additional information regarding the creeks, catch basins, and reservoirs is in Section 2.6.

HWAD had annually stocked Rose Creek Reservoir with about 4,000 rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), until security restrictions after September 11, 2001, prohibited fishing. HWAD stocks Rose Creek Reservoir with tui chub with the possibility of reintroducing them into Walker Lake if stocking efforts in the reservoir are successful. Black Beauty and Station Reservoirs are treated with chlorine to comply with drinking water regulations (DZHC No date). Therefore, aquatic biota are not in these reservoirs. Cat Creek Reservoir is not stocked with fish.

Walker Lake is a highly alkaline, mineralized lake. The lake concentrations of several minerals exceed the federal and state aquatic life criteria for toxicity including arsenic, cadmium, molybdenum, total phosphorus, and selenium. Although numerical standards do not exist for TDS, NDOW has shown that TDS levels have impaired the aquatic life benefic use. Several species of fish and at least one species of zooplankton have been eradicated because of the elevated TDS levels (NDEP 2009). NDOW found that hatchery LCT experienced high death rates when released into Walker Lake because of the high levels of TDS. In the mid-1990s, NDOW began to acclimate the hatchery LCT to high TDS water before releasing into Walker Lake. While this acclimation has improved fish survival, the health and lifespan of the trout and its food sources are impaired because of the elevated TDS levels. Increasing TDS concentrations has caused significant biological changes in Walker Lake, including a reduction in biological diversity and the extinction of at least one zooplankton species. The declining water quality is also directly related to the loss of native species of fish (LCT, Tahoe sucker, Lahontan reside shiner, and Lahontan speckled dace) (NDEP 2009). The TDS level in 2013 have ranged from 20,000 to 50,000 mg/L, and sport fishing has been discontinued until TDS levels are reduced to where sport fish can survive in Lake Walker (Peterson, personal communication, 2012).

2.10.2 Wildlife Management

2.10.2.1 Mammals

Mammals inhabiting HWAD represent all trophic levels and contribute to the diverse ecosystem. No comprehensive inventory has been conducted for mammals inhabiting HWAD; however, other miscellaneous surveys conducted at HWAD have identified more than 70 species on HWAD and its land holdings Appendix A lists these mammals, and Table 2-12 lists the primary mammal species, their habitat, diet, and notes.

NDOW annually conducts Nelson desert bighorn sheep (*Ovis canadensis*) counts on Mount Grant. It estimates that 180 sheep reside on Mount Grant. The BLM manages feral horses (*equus caballus*), which roam the Walker Lake area.

American pikas (*Ochotona princeps*) have declined across the southern Great Basin, and USGS research continues to try to understand the mechanisms behind the ecoregional decline. HWAD sites are invaluable as a monitoring control, relative to other land uses, given their relative lack of ecological disturbance at higher elevations. Additional information regarding pika is below in Section 2.10.3, *Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species*.

Bats tend to nest in concrete storage warehouses. HWAD has identified 14 species on its land holdings and 3 are listed as Nevada special status species including the silver-haired bat (*Lasionycteris noctivagans*), long-eared myotis (*M. evotis*), and California myotis (*M. californicus*). The western big-bat (*Corynorhinus rafinesquei*), big brown bat (*Eptesicus fuscus*), spotted bat (*Euderma maculatum*), red bat (*Lasiurus borealis*), hoary bat (*L. cinerius*), little brown myotis (*Myotis lucifugus*), fringed myotis (*M. thysanodes*), Yuma myotis (*M. yumanensis*), long-legged myotis (*M. volans*), small-footed myotis (*M. subulatus*), and the Mexican freetail bat (*Tadarida mexicana*) have been observed at HWAD.

Table 2-12.
Primary mammal species on HWAD

Species	Habitat	Diet	Comments
American pika (<i>Ochotona princeps</i>)	Lives only in rocky (talus) slopes, at a minimum elevation of 8,250 msl	Generalist diet of forbs, grasses, sedges, and parts of some woody plants	Historical records of pikas include the southeast side of Big Indian Mountain. at 9,700 feet elevation and on Cory Peak at 8,500 feet elevation. Surveys by Dr. Beever (USGS) during 1994-present have documented pikas as low as 8,290 feet in 2007, up to within 420 feet elevation of the summit of Mount Grant. Standardized survey effort detected 29 individuals in 1998 and 17 individuals in 2007 -- a decline consistent with pika range retractions, extirpations, and declines in abundance in the southern Great Basin. Surveys at elevations less than 8,290 feet msl are needed to establish the absolute minimum of the species' distribution, within the Wassuk Range.
American black bear (<i>Ursus americanus</i>)	Mountainous terrain and dens below and in hollow trees, and beneath tree roots	Berries, nuts, tubers, small mammals, eggs, honey, garbage, and carrion.	Black bears were observed for the first time on Mount Grant in 1997. More bears have been observed in the past few years. HWAD coordinates with NDOW for bear removal.
Black-tailed jackrabbits (<i>Leups californicus</i>)	Lower desert scrub community along valley floor	Green vegetation along highways	Whiskey Flats, about 15 miles south of HWAD is known for former Native American hunting grounds.
Bobcat (<i>Lynx rufus</i>)	Pinyon-juniper and foothills	Small mammals, rodents, and birds	Population estimates ranges over 8 square miles.

Table 2-12. (continued)

Species	Habitat	Diet	Comments
Coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>)	Pinyon-juniper and more open landscapes	Rodents and sometimes deer and sheep	No surveys of the coyote population have been conducted at HWAD, but it is estimated to be large.
Feral horses (<i>Equus caballus</i>)	The southern end of Walker Lake	Browse forbs and grasses	Feral horses roam the Walker Lake area. HWAD monitors them, and BLM manages them.
Mountain lion (<i>Felis concolor</i>)	Higher elevations of Mount Grant	Mule deer, Nelson desert bighorn sheep, feral horses are preferred prey, but will prey on most wildlife. A mature lion feeds on about one deer per week	No surveys have been conducted of population size. HWAD does not encourage sport hunting. NDOW estimate fewer than five lions range off and on Mount Grant. NDOW evaluates the benefits and drawbacks of controlling the population on HWAD in the context of the population that inhabits western Nevada and eastern California.
Mule deer (<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>)	Pinyon-juniper mountainous areas in spring/summer, lower elevations in winter	Twigs, shrubs, and herbs	Resident mule deer range from 20 to 100 annually. Migratory deer that overwinter range from 200 to 300 animals. Population varies depending on weather severity, its direct effects on forage plant species and surface water availability, and indirect effects on birth rate and survival. Population has remained relatively stable over the years.
Nelson desert bighorn sheep (<i>Ovis canadensis</i>)	Higher elevations, pinyon-juniper mountainous areas, and rocky canyons of Mount Grant	A variety of plants, including grasses, sedges, and woody plants	Sheep were extirpated from the Wassuk Range before the Army withdrew the land. Sheep now on HWAD were reintroduced through a cooperative agreement with NDOW in the late 1960s. The estimated population of the sheep in 2012 was 180.
Ringtail (<i>Bassariscus astutus</i>)	Higher elevation pinyon-juniper habitat	Squirrels and rodents	No surveys have been conducted for population size.
Yellow-belly marmot (<i>Marmota flaviventris</i>)	Rocky terrain of valleys, slopes, and foothills	Grasses and forbs	--
White-tailed antelope ground squirrels (<i>Ammospermophilus leucurus</i>)	Common in open areas, inhabiting the lower desert scrub community along valley floor; especially around magazine storage area	Seeds, insects, and meat	--

Table 2-12. (continued)

Species	Habitat	Diet	Comments
White-tailed jackrabbit (<i>Lepus townsendii</i>)	Open areas above 7,000 feet in the upper sagebrush communities and grassy plains	Grasses and other green vegetation during the summer, supplementing their diet with buds, bark, and small twigs during winter	--

Source: (CH2MHill 2007), (Beever, personal communication 2013)

2.10.2.2 Birds

The MBTA (16 U.S.C 703-712) directs departments and agencies of the federal government to prohibits the *take* of bird species (as defined in 50 CFR 10.13). In a recently completed MOU between the DoD and USFWS, the federal agency taking actions that “have, or are likely to have, a measurable negative effect on migratory bird populations” must promote the conservation of migratory bird populations. HWAD abides by the provisions of the MOU to promote the conservation of migratory bird species.

Several surveys have been conducted to inventory birds at HWAD. Some of the surveys specify the location (either Mount Grant or Walker Lake), habitat (e.g., meadow, shoreline, pinyon-juniper), relative abundance, and incidental observations. HWAD has documented 185 bird species inhabiting its land holdings. The University of California at Davis conducted a bird survey in 2012 that included relative abundance on Mount Grant in four canyons where 75 species were identified (UC Davis 2012). Walker Lake is a significant migratory stop for a few species, especially the common loon and the American white pelican. Birds of prey, quail and similar game birds, birds that feed more on insects than seed, and neotropical migrants constitute most of the species. Appendix A includes the compiled inventory of birds, and Table 2-13 includes the list of primary bird species at HWAD, their habitat, and diet.

Table 2-13.
Primary bird species on HWAD

Species	Habitat	Diet	Comments
American white pelican (<i>Pelecanus erythrorhynchos</i>)	Walker Lake as an annual stopover point en route to breeding grounds at Anaho Island in Pyramid Lake, Nevada and in Canada	Fish	As many as 400 pelicans have been surveyed at the lake during their stopover.
Blue grouse (<i>Dendragapus obscurus</i>)	In and around evergreen trees; in spring they migrate to lower elevations to breed then return to higher elevations in the winter	Leaves (especially conifer needles) flowers, fruit, and insects (grasshoppers)	Low numbers of blue grouse inhabit Mount Grant. Species is native to northeastern Nevada and central California mountains. The population on Mount Grant could represent the easternmost range of the California mountain population.
California Quail (<i>Callipepla californica</i>)	Open woodlands, brushy foothills, stream valleys, and often near permanent water sources	Legumes, weed seeds, fruit, insects, spiders, and snails	California quail were introduced to Mount Grant around 1986 but the population size is unknown.
Chukar partridge (<i>Alectoris chukar</i>)	Mountain range, lower sagebrush communities	Lower sagebrush communities	Chukar partridge is the most common game bird at HWAD. Nonnative species introduced to Wassuk Range in 1945 and became established throughout the range including Mount Grant.
Common loon (<i>Gavia immer</i>)	Walker Lake is an annual stopover point for 1 to 2 months in spring and fall migration.	Fish	In 1987 NDOW began conducting spring and fall surveys.
Mountain quail (<i>Oreortyx pictus</i>)	Chaparral and pinyon-juniper woodlands	Bulbs, green vegetation, insects, fruits, and berries	Mountain quail have been observed, but the population size is unknown. Mountain quail migrate in the winter to lower elevations on foot.
Red-shouldered hawk (<i>Buteo lineatus</i>)	Eastern deciduous forested wetlands but are also attracted to Walker Lake	--	Have been identified on HWAD land as injured birds; however, they have been identified on various occasions. It is assumed that a small nesting population exists on or near HWAD.
Sage-grouse (<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>)	Riparian and wet meadow areas at 8,000 to 9,000 feet msl on the south and west sides of Mount Grant	--	NDOW monitors the annual spring population to set bag limits on hunting this species. Sage-grouse prosper in non-grazed meadows. Hunting sage-grouse is not permitted. Federal candidate species (USFWS 2013).

Table 2-13. Continued

Species	Habitat	Diet	Comments
Snowy plover (<i>Charadrius alexandrines</i>)	Walker Lake sand flats and sandy beaches of streams, lakes, and coasts	Insects, crustaceans, marine worms, and other aquatic biota	Snowy plovers have been identified on Walker Lake since 1980. State listed sensitive species (NNHP 2013).

Source: CH2MHill 2007

2.10.2.3 Reptiles and Amphibians

UNR conducted a survey in 1999 to identify the diversity and health of the reptile and amphibian populations at HWAD. Two species of amphibians and 16 species of reptiles were identified in the survey. Among the reptiles, eight species were lizards and eight were snakes (Espinoza and Tracy 1999). A list of species is in Appendix A.

2.10.3 Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species

The bald eagle was removed from the endangered species list in August 2007 because its population has recovered. Bald and golden eagles are protected under the MBTA and the Bald and Golden Eagle Act. HWAD monitors and USFWS manages the eagles in accordance with the 2009 *Post-delisting Monitoring Plan for the Bald Eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*) in the Contiguous 48 States* (USFWS 2009). A copy of this plan is in Appendix G. Golden eagles are on Mount Grant, and a couple of transient bald eagles have been observed overwintering on Walker Lake.

Appendix A presents the species that USFWS and NNHP list as threatened, endangered, and candidate in Mineral County. Yellow-billed cuckoo (*Cucyzyus americanus*), Hiko White River springfish (*Onchorynchus baileyi grandis*), and Railroad Valley springfish (*Crenichthys nevadae*) have not been observed on HWAD or its land holdings (Tetra Tech 1997).

Three bats are listed as Nevada special status species including the silver-haired bat (*Lasionycteris noctivagans*), long-eared myotis (*M. evotis*), and California myotis (*M. californicus*). The pallid bat (*Antrozous pallidus*) and the Townsend's big ear bat (*Corynorhinus townsendii*) are listed as state protected but have not been identified at HWAD (NNHP 2013). Townsend's big eared bat is listed as a sensitive species in USFS's Region 4 – Humboldt-Toiyabe sensitive species (NNHP 2013) which is near the southeastern boundary of HWAD (NNHP 2013).

The LCT does occur at HWAD and is federally listed threatened and state-protected but has been recently extirpated from Walker Lake because of high salinity levels. Greater sage-grouse is a federally listed candidate species (USFWS 2013). State-listed sensitive species observed on HWAD are the American pika, white-faced ibis (*Plegadis chihi*) and western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrines*). Management measures are under evaluation and development in coordination with NDOW, USFS, and USGS to improve habitat in the higher elevation of Mount Grant where pika have been observed (NDOW 2013, Peterson, personal communication, 2013a). White-faced ibis and western snowy plover are managed consistent with the MBTA. Table 2-14 presents the federally listed species for Mineral County (USFWS 2013).

Table 2-14.
Federally listed rare, threatened, and endangered species, Mineral County, Nevada

Group	Common name	Scientific name	Status
Birds	Yellow-billed cuckoo	<i>Cucyzyus americanus</i>	Candidate
Birds	Greater sage-grouse	<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>	Candidate
Fishes	Lahontan cutthroat trout	<i>Oncorhynchus clarki henshawi</i>	Threatened
Fishes	Hiko White River springfish	<i>Crenichthys baileyi grandis</i>	Endangered
Fishes	Railroad Valley springfish	<i>Crenichthys nevadae</i>	Threatened

Source: USFWS 2013

Greater Sage-Grouse. The greater sage-grouse is of concern at Mount Grant because it is listed as a federal candidate species by USFWS. Special management strategies have been identified as presented in the *Mount Grant Initial Conservation Assessment and Strategies* report (Nachlinger 2003; in Appendix G) and the *Sage Grouse Conservation Plan for Nevada and Eastern California* (NDOW 2004). This plan includes elements for sage-grouse conservation planning, assessment of risk factors and strategies and actions to reduce or eliminate these risk factors, implementation of and commitment to employ these strategies and actions, monitoring the effectiveness of these strategies, and ascertaining the health of sage-grouse populations (NDOW 2004). The NRCS launched the Sage-Grouse Initiative in 2010 (Appendix G). The initiative is a program for conserving at-risk wildlife through voluntary cooperation, incentives, and community support, achieving wildlife conservation through sustainable ranching and habitat preservation (SGI 2013).

The 2012 *Bi-State Action Plan – Past, Present, and Future Actions for Conservation of the Greater Sage-Grouse Bi-State Distinct Population Segment* (BTACNC 2012; in Appendix G) updates the two plans mentioned above. HWAD participates in bi-state meetings that include USFWS, NDOW, U.S. Department of Agriculture, BLM, and other agencies that compose the Bi-State Local Area Working Group that meets biannually (Peterson, personal communication 2013b). This group works together to develop strategies for monitoring, surveying, tagging, and improving habitat and survival for sage-grouse.

Mount Grant Population Management Unit (PMU) for Greater Sage-Grouse. The Mount Grant PMU is approximately 699,079 acres and is entirely within Lyon and Mineral Counties, Nevada. HWAD encompasses 48,936 acres, or 7 percent of the PMU. According to historical records, Mount Grant has never supported a large population of sage-grouse (NDOW 2004). However, HWAD is considered to have some of the best sage-grouse habitat on the Mount Grant PMU. The habitat is maintained because of the exclusion of public access and livestock grazing. Meadow restoration projects on Mount Grant are also anticipated to provide additional habitat. Current land management practices (i.e., exclusionary measures and habitat restoration) provide for the propagation of the species.

The Mount Grant PMU is used in conjunction with the Bodie PMU which is adjacent to the southwestern edge of the Mount Grant PMU. Three reliable leks have been counted annually from 2004 to 2011 with a long-term average of 20.6 males per lek (BTACNC 2012).

According to the 2012 Bi-State Action Plan, the following risk factors in Table 2-15 affecting sage-grouse and sage-grouse habitat were assessed in the Mount Grant PMU.

Table 2-15.
Risks and relative threat levels in the Mount Grant PMU

Risk	Threat level
Wildland fire	High
Pinyon-juniper encroachment	High
Infrastructure (linear)	High
Geothermal leasing and development	High
Invasive Species – Cheatgrass	Moderate
Grazing – wild horses	Moderate
Poaching	Low
Grazing – permitted livestock	Low
Predation	Low
West Nile Virus	Low
Recreation	Low
Human disturbance	Low

Source: BTACNC 2012

Wildland fire is considered a high risk in the lower elevations of Mount Grant and pinyon-juniper encroachment into sagebrush is considered a relatively high risk in the Mount Grant PMU. Ongoing mining and potential geothermal development also pose relatively high risks in this area. Potential geothermal leasing and development activities are likely to increase indirect threats such as vehicle traffic and associated infrastructure, road kills, and increase in avian predators. The bi-state plan mentions that military activities in the Wassuk Range have the potential to harm sage-grouse; however, HWAD limits and prohibits activities in prime sage-grouse habitats. Predation and West Nile virus pose the greatest risk of direct mortality to sage-grouse in the Mount Grant PMU (BTACNC 2012).

The majority of the telemetry work conducted in the bi-state area has occurred in the Bodie-Mount Grant PMUs. Between 2002 and 2009, multiple collaborations between agencies and universities were established by the USGS, BLM, UNR, and the University of Idaho to capture and monitor sage-grouse. Most marked sage-grouse occurred in California with 3,909 locations; more than 45 radio-marked sage-grouse were from the Bodie Hills area. Follow up monitoring suggests that the Mount Grant PMU provides winter habitat for these birds (BTACNC 2012). The Nation Greater Sage-Grouse Planning Strategy is moving forward and updates are available at <http://www.blm.gov/wo/st/en/prog/more/sagegrouse.html>.

Lahontan Cutthroat Trout. The decline of the LCT was originally because of human occupation in the region in the late 1800s (USFWS 1995). The primary causes of decline from the Lahontan Basin are diversion of water for irrigation, pollution from mining and milling operations, ecosystem degradation from livestock overgrazing, and construction of the Yerington weir in 1929, which prevented fish from accessing the East and West Walker River. Commercial fishing and introduction of non-indigenous species also played a role in LCT's decline.

The Walker River Basin Recovery Implementation Team developed by the USFWS a *Short-Term Action Plan for Lahontan Cutthroat Trout in the Walker River Basin* (2003). A copy of this report is in Appendix G. The decline of the LCT in the Walker River Basin was caused by overfishing,

diversion of river water to the Smith and Mason Valley agricultural economies, the construction of Weber Dam, which blocks spawning runs up Walker River, and the river diversions that accelerated the increases of TDS and alkalinity and reduced biodiversity in Walker Lake (USFWS 1995). LCT are the only salmonid species that can tolerate the high levels of dissolved solids and alkalinity. The LCT is a federally listed threatened species in Nevada and has been recently extirpated from Walker Lake because of TDS concentrations of ranging between 20,000 to 50,000 mg/L. This is the only location where LCT was observed on HWAD.

American pika. The American pika population has declined across the southern Great Basin, and USGS research continues to try to understand the mechanisms behind the ecoregional decline. HWAD sites are invaluable as a monitoring control, relative to other land uses, given their relative lack of ecological disturbance at higher elevations (Beever, personal communication, 2013).

The American pika population has declined across the southern Great Basin, and USGS research continues to try to understand the mechanisms behind the ecoregional decline. HWAD sites are invaluable as a monitoring control, relative to other land uses, given their relative lack of ecological disturbance at higher elevations (Beever, personal communication, 2013).

HWAD coordinates with USGS, USFS and NDOW to conduct surveys and improve habitat to increase population density for pikas on and around Mount Grant. USFS has installed a series of 18 data temperature loggers and a precipitation gage between the elevation of 9,765 feet msl and the summit of 11,329 feet msl (Millar 2004). USGS has installed numerous sensors to record climate and may propose modeling and studies to determine changes in pika species abundance and distribution (Beever, personal communication, 2013).

NDOW updated their WAP which includes updates to conservation challenges, research needs, and the anticipated conservation strategies for pika (NDOW 2013). The NDOW WAP also identified pikas as a talus dwelling sensitive species that would benefit from habitat enhancements in higher elevations with larger talus areas for pikas.

NDOW priority research needs for pika include:

- Long-term responses of alpine and tundra communities to global climate change
- Wildlife species that measurably respond to stresses in alpine and tundra habitats
- Minimum viable population size of disjunct populations in alpine habitat
- Population demographics of pika and model viability of individual populations
- Factors contributing to pika extirpation (NDOW 2013)

2.11 Outdoor Recreation

Activities and resources managed in recreational areas on HWAD are the following:

- Nine-hole Walker Lake Golf Course in the industrial area/main base
- Hiking on Mount Grant on approved roads with an escort only
- Nelson desert bighorn sheep hunting in Lower Cottonwood Canyon on Mount Grant (no other hunting or trapping allowed)
- Naturalist sightseeing on Mount Grant and Walker Lake by escort only

Activities and access from HWAD to Walker Lake Golf Course, Walker Lake, and Mount Grant are subject to security restrictions. Because of high security after September 11, 2001, recreational use on the installation has been highly limited and will continue to be subject to restrictions. Golfers must pass through the HWAD Industrial Area/Main Base Main Security Gate. Other access is granted to members of the WRPT for ceremonial activities on Mount Grant (CH2MHill 2007). All fishing, camping, and sightseeing activities are restricted. Off-road vehicle use is not permitted.

2.11.1 Fishing Program

Because of the existing conditions at HWAD, a Hazard Area overlay has been created to address potential safety hazards in areas, including Walker Lake. The Hazard Area overlay is northwest of the WADF and borders the southeastern section of Walker Lake. Because of previous ammunition explosive activities, this area is considered constrained from contaminated soils and UXO, making any development and human activities in this area potentially dangerous (Michael Baker 2009). Access to HWAD property at the southern end of Walker Lake is gated, fenced, and posted with signs stating “No Trespassing” or “Danger, Unexploded Munitions, Keep Out,” and a line of safety buoys runs across the water of Walker Lake at the HWAD northern boundary line. Because of these security reasons, no fishing occurs in the lake or from its shoreline in the HWAD property. The township of Walker Lake (about 11 miles north of HWAD on the western shore of Walker Lake) and the adjacent Walker Lake and the Sportsman’s Beach Recreational Area (operated by BLM) offer boating access to the central portion of the lake. Fishing in Walker Lake has also been adversely affected by the poor water quality of the lake (high salinity and low oxygen levels), preventing viable fish habitat (see Section 2.6, Water Resources).

2.11.2 Hunting Program

Sport hunting for Nelson desert bighorn sheep in Mount Grant’s Lower Cottonwood Canyon occurs within seasons and limits recommended by NDOW and established by the Nevada Board of Wildlife Commissioners. Since 2003, the only hunting allowed on Mount Grant is no more than a group of 10 people to hunt desert bighorn sheep (3 tags issued for HWAD). Participants in these activities are granted use of HWAD property through use permits issued through the commanding officer and are subject to security restrictions.

2.11.3 Nonconsumptive Recreational Activities

The Walker Lake Golf Course is a nine-hole course covering about 51 acres in the industrial area/main base, adjacent to the family housing. The fairways and tees consist of Kentucky bluegrass, and the greens consist of bent grass. Areas surrounding the fairways consist of natural desert vegetation. SOC manages the golf course, although use and management of pesticides (Appendix B) and watering must comply with Army regulations.

Camp Dixie and Rose Creek Cabin are the designated camping areas on Mount Grant. Camp Dixie is in Cottonwood Canyon. Camp Dixie is a rustic camp site that is equipped with a concrete shelter with a fireplace, a cleared area with stones for building campfires, and a restroom. However, running water is not available. Rose Creek Cabin is about 100 feet west of Rose Creek Reservoir on Mount Grant. Rose Creek Cabin is a wilderness cabin designed for a maximum of six persons with two rooms, kitchen, bathroom, screened-in porch, and fireplace. It has a 5,000-gallon water tank, a septic system and leach field, propane powered lanterns, water heater, and refrigerator. The refrigerator is partially powered by solar panels. The water source for the cabin

is surface flow from the watershed and is not potable. Rose Creek Cabin has been closed since September 11, 2001, because of security restrictions.

Naturalist sightseeing—including birding, observing wildflowers, gathering pine nuts, picnicking, hiking, and stargazing—is also subject to security restrictions (CH2MHill 2007).

2.12 Law Enforcement Program

SOC is responsible for law enforcement at HWAD. SOC employees provide installation security and enforcement of all Army regulations at the installation. A 2004 MOA with the Mineral County Sheriff's office outlines law enforcement at the facility (Appendix D).

Responsibility for wildlife management is divided between HWAD and NDOW. HWAD is responsible for wildlife management, habitat improvement, and enforcing hunting and trapping laws and regulations. The HWAD commanding officer issues use permits for organized hunts, and participants are subject to security regulations. HWAD and NDOW establish harvest quotas and organize hunts for desert bighorn sheep at HWAD and on adjoining property. Fishing and sightseeing activities are restricted.

HWAD adheres to all hunting and fishing laws prescribed by NDOW. The general public is no longer permitted to fish because of mission safety and security requirements. The HWAD commanding officer can authorize the general public permission for organized hunt, but hunting is prohibited with the exception of desert bighorn sheep as mentioned above. Hunting regulations are at www.huntnevada.com.

2.13 Invasive Species Management Program

Invasive species are plants and animals that have the ability to rapidly reproduce and ultimately out-compete native communities to dominate natural habitats and are most often imported from outside North America. Invasive plant species commonly found in Nevada are the following:

- Red brome (*Bromus rubens*)
- Cheatgrass (*B. tectorum*)
- Hoary cress or low whitetop (*Cardaria* spp.)
- Musk thistle (*Carduus nutans*)
- Diffuse knapweed (*Centaurea diffusa*)
- Spotted knapweed (*C. maculosa*)
- Russian knapweed (*C. repens* L.)
- Yellow starthistle (*C. solstitialis* L.)
- Squarrose knapweed (*C. virgate* spp. *Squarrosa*)
- Rush skeletonweed (*Chondrilla juncea* L.)
- Common crupina (*Crupina vulgaris*)
- Leafy spurge (*Euphorbia esula* L.)
- Dyer's woad (*Isatis tinctoria*)
- Dalmation toadflax (*Linaria dalmatica*)

- Yellow toadflax (*L. vulgaris*)
- Scotch thistle (*Onopordum acanthium*)
- Sulfur cinquefoil (*Potentilla recta* L.)
- Medusahead (*Taeniatherum caput-medusae*)
- Tall whitetop or perennial pepperweed (*Lepidium latifolium*)
- Purple Loosestrife (*Lythrum salicaria* L.)
- Tamarisk (*Tamarix* sp.)
- Eurasian or spiked watermilfoil (*Myriophyllum spicatum*)
- Giant salvinia (*Salvinia molesta*)

Noxious weeds are plant species known to be detrimental to rangeland and those weeds that are regulated by state and federal government agencies. Several noxious weeds and invasive species occur on HWAD. Two nuisance species found on HWAD that pose the greatest threat to native communities are tamarisk, found south of Walker Lake, in the cantonment area, and along various roadways throughout the installation; and cheatgrass, a nuisance species often found in big sage and western sage habitat of the lower Mount Grant watershed. Table 2-16 lists the weeds found on HWAD and are identified as a restricted or state-listed noxious species. Bull thistle is not federally or state-listed, but it is considered a major problem (Tetra Tech 2004). No federally listed noxious weeds have been identified on the installation.

Table 2-16.
Noxious weeds identified at HWAD

Common name	Scientific name	Occurrence
African rue	<i>Peganum harmala</i>	Terrestrial
Barbwire Russian thistle	<i>Salsola paulsenii</i>	Terrestrial
Cheatgrass	<i>Bromus tectorum</i>	Terrestrial
Common burdock	<i>Arctium minus</i>	Terrestrial
Common mullien	<i>Verbascum Thapsus</i>	Terrestrial
Common St. Consort	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	Terrestrial
Common sunflower	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Terrestrial
Flixweed	<i>Descurainia sophia</i>	Terrestrial
Halogeton	<i>Halogeton glomeratus</i>	Terrestrial
Hoary cress/whitetop	<i>Cardaria draba</i>	Terrestrial
Redstem filaree	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	Terrestrial
Rush skeletonweed	<i>Chondrilla juncea</i>	Terrestrial
Russian olive	<i>Elaeagnus augustifolia</i>	Wetland/terrestrial
Sweet clover	<i>Melilotus alba</i>	Terrestrial
Tamarisk	<i>Tamarisk</i> sp.	Terrestrial
Tansy ragwort	<i>Senecio jacobaea</i>	Terrestrial
Western salsify	<i>Tragopogon dubius</i>	Terrestrial

Source: Tetra Tech 2004

HWAD is relatively free of noxious weed species. The forested area on Mount Grant and much of the undeveloped greasewood habitat south and east of the magazine areas contain primarily native plant communities. Contributing factors are the lack of disturbance and minimal use of the Mount Grant watershed and high salinity in the soil, which prevent many common invasive plant species from establishing (Tetra Tech 2004).

Broadleaf weeds are a problem around most HWAD warehouses and railroad ballast. Occasionally, weeds are a problem around HWAD office buildings. Mowing is the preferred treatment, but HWAD uses Weedar 64 and Trimec herbicides because of their efficacy and low percentage of active ingredients.

Red imported fire ants (*Solenopsis invicta*) and other insect pests could also be considered invasive species because of their foreign origin and damaging effects. Control measures for all nuisance animals and plants are covered in greater detail in the HWAD *Pest Management Plan* (HWAD 2012b). HWAD follows the *Army Policy Guidance for Management and Control of Invasive Species* (U.S. Army 2001).

HWAD supports the National Strategy for Invasive Plant Management and its three goals—prevention, control, and restoration. If any noxious weeds are found on the installation, a high priority for control will be established, and control efforts will be maximized. Weeds along fence lines, on road shoulders, on paved surfaces, and such, require control using appropriate herbicides. Unwanted plants are controlled mechanically (mowing, trimmers) or by using mulch materials around ornamental plants.

2.14 Pest Management Program

Per AR 200-5, *Environmental Quality: Pest Management* (HQDA 1999), HWAD's IPMP defines and describes essential elements of the pest management program, such as health and environmental safety; pest identification; and pesticide storage, transportation, use, and disposal. The plan is used as a tool to reduce reliance on pesticides, to enhance environmental protection, and to maximize the use of integrated pest management (IPM) techniques. The plan is maintained as part of the Real Property Maintenance Program for HWAD. It also provides guidance for the judicious use of both chemical and nonchemical control techniques to achieve effective pest management with minimal environmental contamination. Adherence to the plan ensures effective, economical, and environmentally acceptable pest management and compliance with pertinent laws and regulations.

The IPMP for HWAD is a comprehensive document describing the pest control program and is updated annually or as necessary (See Appendix B). The pest management functions at HWAD are either performed or monitored by SOC for HWAD. The IPMP uses an IPM approach including the use of both chemical and non-chemical controls. Mechanical, physical, biological, and chemical controls are listed where applicable for specific pests in the pest control worksheets in the IPMP. Its implementation will prevent or manage pests, which if left uncontrolled, would adversely affect the mission and function of HWAD, human health and safety, or damage property, structures, or material. The IPMP contains applicable policies, requirements, environmental documentation, and major actions that affect the Pest Management Program. Also in the plan are provisions for the safety of personnel, equipment, materials, and facilities.

Pests identified at HWAD include disease vectors and other health-related pests (the top priority of pest control at HWAD), general household pests, structural pests, undesirable vegetation, ornamental plant and turf pests, animal pests, and other miscellaneous pests. The IPMP details the management plan outline for each pest, including treatment and eradication methods. A copy of the IPMP is in Appendix B.

Many nuisance species are found on HWAD. Rodents tend to burrow into magazines and munition containers and can damage the munitions. Surveys are conducted for evidence of rodent activity, and infested areas are treated with chemicals or traps are set, on the basis of the infestation severity. Rodents are also controlled in high-activity areas to reduce the threat of Hantavirus. Rodents are the main carrier of the virus, which is transmitted through the saliva or feces of rodents (Tetra Tech 1997).

California black bears are considered a nuisance because of their aggressive behavior toward humans, and they are a threat to training missions on Mount Grant and in the cantonment area. HWAD has partnered with NDOW to relocate bears caught on the installation.

Feral cats and dogs are captured and taken to the Mineral County Animal Control.

Common bird species, such as city pigeons (*Columba livia*) and other birds that nest in and deteriorate building exteriors are controlled by the manual removal of their nests.

Lizards that enter residential and other buildings are captured and released to areas outside the cantonment area.

Flying red ants that swarm during breeding season are controlled by chemicals only if workers need access to the area where ants are swarming. In the residential and cantonment areas, other ants, ground beetles, midges, gnats, earwigs roaches, spiders, ticks, wasps, bees, and hornets are controlled with chemical spot-treatment as needed according to the severity of the infestation. Scorpions are relocated to less populated areas.

Infestations of aphids, elm beetles, and colicoids on vegetation are controlled either by power-spray, fogging, or hand-sprayed insecticide.

2.15 Cultural and Paleontological Resources

Cultural resources at HWAD are managed under the 1996 ICRMP. The ICRMP was updated in 2002 and 2007, but the documents were not signed and finalized. The following provides a summary of HWAD prehistoric and historic archaeological, historic buildings and structures, and Native American cultural resources. For detailed information regarding cultural resources on HWAD, see the installation's ICRMP.

2.15.1 Prehistoric and Historic Background

Archaeological evidence indicates that people have been using the western Great Basin region, including the Walker Lake watershed, for the past 11,000 years. The prehistory of the Great Basin is divided into the Pre-Archaic (9500–5500 B.C.) and Archaic (the past 7,500 years) periods. Archaeological evidence of Pre-Archaic peoples indicates that populations were low, sparsely distributed, highly mobile, and organized as small groups that traveled together. Early Archaic (550–2000 B.C.) adaptations are inferred to have been a response to Middle Holocene climatic

warming and drying. Middle Archaic (2000 B.C. through A.D. 500) settlement patterns focused on residential camps, while Late Archaic (A.D. 500 through European-American contact) settlement patterns continued to become more logistically oriented. The region remained largely uninhabited by European-Americans until the latter half of the 1800s following emigration to California and subsequent mining booms (DOE 2010).

Several archaeological surveys have been conducted on the installation. Altogether, 116 prehistoric sites have been reported (15 eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places [NRHP], 91 ineligible sites, and 10 sites of unknown eligibility). In addition, 13 historic sites have been reported (3 eligible, 10 ineligible). None of these sites have been formally nominated for inclusion in the NRHP. Inventory and evaluation of archaeological sites under NHPA sections 106 and 110 are ongoing and are undertaken as needed or as funding allows (Michael Baker 2009).

Archaeological sites have been found up to nearly 14,000 feet msl in the Great Basin. Prehistoric sites may include game drives, village sites, lithic scatters, rock art, food and plant processing sites, hunting blinds, wickiups (yahnees), and rockshelters. Historic sites may include mine prospects, adits, mill sites, roads, ditches, wood-cutting camps, ranching features, historic period Paiute sites, sheep camps, arborglyphs, fish camps, and historic recreational use (Dillingham 2013).

2.15.2 Historic Buildings and Structures

Surveys of historic buildings and structures have been completed at HWAD. On the basis of these surveys, HWAD is considered eligible for listing in the NRHP because of its importance to the United States and Nevada military history and its physical integrity of landscape, infrastructure, and architectural resources (Michael Baker 2009).

No buildings or structures at HWAD are listed in the NRHP. Several inventories and reviews have been conducted at HWAD, which conclude that some structures at HWAD are eligible for listing in the NRHP. According to the HWAD ICRMP, 1,899 of 2,603 buildings and structures have been inventoried, with 1,790 potentially eligible for listing in the NRHP; 809 other properties need to be inventoried before their status as contributing or non-contributing can be determined (Michael Baker 2009; URS 2009).

An architectural inventory of HWAD was conducted in 1983. Using the evaluative criteria developed by the Army during the 1980s as the basis for inclusion, the study indicated that HWAD has no Category I (properties of major importance) or Category II (properties of importance) properties. However, buildings in the Industrial Area/Main Base and in the Ammunition Storage areas were considered Category III (properties of minor importance). In the former, approximately 34 building types were considered locally important; in the latter, 19 buildings/building types were also considered important. Those were documented using Historic American Buildings Survey/Historic American Engineering Record Level IV procedures. Those records are archived at the Library of Congress, and copies are maintained in the HWAD Cultural Resources Management files (Michael Baker 2009).

2.15.3 Native American Resources

Nevada has 25 federally recognized Native American tribes and colonies. Two federally recognized tribes exist in the study area: the WRPT and the Yerington Paiute Tribe. The tribes are self-governing and are associated with the Northern Paiute Tribe (DOE 2010). The Walker River Indian Reservation is north of HWAD in Mineral, Churchill, and Lyon Counties. The Yerington Paiute Tribe lands are northwest of HWAD in Lyon County (EPA 2012).

No traditional cultural properties or sacred sites have been formally identified at HWAD, and no systematic inventories of traditional cultural properties or sacred sites have been undertaken. Tribal resources may also include plants and animals gathered for traditional, religious or sacred reasons. Gathering locations could be on lands co-managed by Forest Service and DoD. Springs could also be culturally sensitive (Dillingham, personal communication, 2013). However, it is possible that some of the prehistoric archaeological sites could be considered as traditional cultural properties by local Native American groups (Michael Baker 2009).

As Walker Lake has receded, remains were exposed at the southern end of the lake within HWAD boundaries. HWAD has coordinated with Walker Paiute Tribe to repatriate remains, marking the location with a global positioning system (GPS) (to prevent future disturbance), and working with HWAD Explosive Ordnance Disposal Department to recover remains in the UXO area at the southern end of the lake (Peterson, personal communication, 2012).

2.15.4 Paleontological Resources

The Omnibus Public Lands Management Act of 2009 (16 U.S.C. 1132 note) contains provisions for the protection and preservation of paleontological resources. Under this law, the secretaries of the departments of Interior and Agriculture are directed to inventory, manage, and protect paleontological resources on the public lands they administer. In addition, the secretaries are directed to coordinate these efforts and to establish education programs to increase public awareness of the significance of paleontological resources. The law also prohibits the collection of paleontological resources from federal land without a permit, except in the case of noncommercial collecting that complies with other regulations for that federal land.

Paleontological resources are any fossilized remains, traces, or imprints of organisms, preserved in or on the earth's crust, that are of paleontological interest and that provide information about the history of life on earth (BLM 2013).

The BLM regards paleontological or fossil resources as a fragile, nonrenewable scientific record. The history of life on earth is an important component of America's natural heritage. If these resources are damaged, destroyed or improperly collected, their scientific and educational value may be greatly reduced or lost forever (BLM 2013).

Systematic paleontological investigations have not been conducted on HWAD. To date, no paleontological resources have been found or reported on HWAD (URS 2009).

3 FUTURE NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Future management for each resource details the goals and objectives, proposed management measures, and other management alternatives considered for implementation of this INRMP over the next 5 years and beyond. *Goals and Objectives* describe the proposed goals and objectives for each resource. Within each resource section, the subsection titled *Management Measures* describes the tasks proposed to meet resource-specific goals and objectives. That subsection provides the rationale for the management measures selected and their potential relationship or impact on other natural and cultural resources and the military mission.

Section 3.15 summarizes the highest priority management initiatives, including inventorying and monitoring programs for all resource areas, their relationship to each other and the military mission, and how they serve to achieve goals and objectives for the natural resources management program at HWAD.

3.1 Facilities and Developed Areas

HWAD's developed areas are managed in accordance with applicable plans and regulations. HWAD has prepared individual management plans to address specific resource or program management activities such as hazardous waste management, stormwater management, pest management, spill control and cleanup, and recycling. A master planning document was also prepared to integrate those plans.

3.1.1 Goals and Objectives

Goals and objectives for HWAD facilities and developed areas are described in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1.
Goals and objectives for facilities and developed areas

Goals	Objectives
Manage all existing and potential sources of environmental contamination to prevent releases.	Comply with all laws, regulations, and policies applicable to potential sources of environmental contamination.
Ensure the integrity of information related to environmental response actions.	Maintain complete records of all staff training and compliance activities.

3.1.2 Management Measures

HWAD will train employees and ensure that hired contractors are properly trained in applicable laws, regulations, policies, and procedures of handling potential environmental contaminants and preventing pollution. Follow all protocols in relevant HWAD management programs to minimize environmental contamination.

Report all activities with the potential to create environmental contamination immediately when they occur and initiate appropriate response actions as soon as possible after a release of pollutants that could cause environmental contamination.

At least one copy of the most current environmental program compliance data—including IRP, MMRP, and CC data—will be stored in a location remote from where original records are stored.

Active IRP sites will continue to be managed in accordance with applicable regulations, and closed or NFA sites will be monitored where necessary to ensure that compliance is maintained. Sites could be reentered into the IRP if future conditions or new information suggest it is necessary. HWAD should ensure that all information collected during remedial response and stored in site files is properly maintained and safeguarded. Actions regarding the site could occur years after the data have been gathered. Records should be sufficiently detailed and protected to provide a complete and accurate history of the remedial response in support of any future legal action and to aid the installation in responding to inquiries from Congress or requests from the public under the Freedom of Information Act.

Spills and other emergencies that occur at HWAD will continue to be coordinated in accordance with the MOA/MOU and cooperative agreements. Continue following the Defense National Stockpile Center Mercury Management standard operating procedures to reduce the potential of an accidental release.

3.2 **Vegetation Management**

AR 200-1 requires Army habitat management to conserve and enhance existing flora and fauna consistent with the Army’s goal to conserve, protect, and sustain biological diversity while supporting the military mission (HQDA 2007). To meet that requirement, activities will be directed toward maintaining healthy ecosystems and restoring degraded ecosystems. AR 200-1 also requires that primary consideration be given to managing indigenous listed, proposed, and candidate threatened and endangered species’ habitats, and to other environmentally sensitive areas and areas of special concern (HQDA 2007).

3.2.1 **Goals and Objectives**

The primary goals of vegetation management at HWAD are to maintain native plant communities and minimize loss of vegetative cover through ecosystem and erosion management principles. Goals and objectives for vegetation management at HWAD are listed in Table 3-2.

**Table 3-2.
Goals and objectives for vegetation management**

Goals	Objectives
Maintain reduced herbicide use in accordance with DoD policy	Continue to seek and implement cost-effective solutions and changes to keep expenditures for the natural resources program within a reasonable budget.
Eliminate nonnative species and improve habitat quality to the extent practical and feasible.	Restore and maintain native plant communities through the use of integrated ecosystem management principles while accommodating military training needs.

Table 3-2. (continued)

Goals	Objectives
Minimize potential losses caused by diseases and insect pests through early detection of damaging agents and development of appropriate IPM solutions.	Monitor for signs of new disease outbreaks and insect infestations.
Work with universities, state agencies, federal agencies, and nongovernmental organizations to gather basic data on natural resources; develop planning and evaluation tools.	Evaluate potential future coordination efforts with universities, and state, federal and non-governmental agencies for new research projects to broaden informational database of natural resources.

3.2.2 Management Measures

Vegetation management at HWAD is area specific. Therefore, methods and management for different areas are discussed separately. The issues common to and managed identically in most areas are included here. These issues are protection against fire and exotic plant species.

HWAD will continue practicing prompt sanitation methods to limit the spread of insect infestations and continue to control disease vectors through applications of appropriate chemical treatments when necessary (Appendix B).

Approximately 328 acres of improved areas, including the golf course, administrative buildings, and parking lots in the cantonment area of the installation require more intensive landscape management. Those areas are mowed and edged, and trees and shrubs are maintained. Semi-improved areas are those areas requiring less intensive maintenance including Mount Grant and the south shore of Walker Lake.

HWAD will continue to work with universities and cooperating agencies to update existing floristic inventory as additional plant species are identified. These surveys will also include updates to the geographic information systems (GIS) database to facilitate planning, implementation, and post-implementation evaluation of projects.

3.2.2.1 Fire Protection

Because HWAD is in a desert climate, high temperatures mainly in the summer months coupled with low precipitation, makes HWAD susceptible to wildland fires. The native vegetation is adapted to low moisture and high temperatures. However, fires caused by natural weather events and human error are threats. In addition, the sagebrush-pinyon woodlands are often high in woody fuels contributing to fire potential. The *Mount Grant Initial Conservation Assessment and Strategies* report presents strategies to reduce this hazard (Nachlinger 2003). Strategies include mechanical removal, prescribed burns under non-catastrophic prescriptions, and allowing for prescribed burns. HWAD works with the agencies to implement these strategies when feasible. HWAD guidance for fire emergencies and fire prevention is detailed in the *Emergency Response Plan for Hawthorne Army Depot* (see Appendix D) and the *Fire Prevention Manual* (DZHC 1994, 1996). Both manuals detail the activities and the centralized command for controlling the fire, health, and safety operations at HWAD. HWAD posts wildland fire warning signs during high-risk seasons and also maintains mutual aid agreements with local authorities for support in fire. Appendix D contains mutual aid agreements between HWAD and local and federal authorities for fire prevention and response procedures.

3.2.2.2 Vegetation Control

In accordance with the Presidential Memorandum of April 26, 1994, environmentally beneficial landscaping issued to the heads of executive departments and agencies, HWAD also practices IPM techniques to reduce the use of fertilizers and pesticides and water conservation techniques to minimize runoff.

Non-chemical control includes flail mowing, whereas chemical control is handled by the installation pest controller, who is trained and certified in accordance with AR 200-5 and Nevada state law (HQDA 1999). Fertilizers are not generally applied to natural cover on land that has not been irrigated; however, in some areas, the natural cover can be improved and encouraged to prevent erosion by applying ammonia sulfate in October and February. Fertilizer can be applied at any time from early spring until mid-summer, and from late September to late November.

Control of aggressive, opportunistic species, such as tamarisk, is continually evaluated through monitoring efforts. Tamarisk was initially planted in the early 1900s for erosion control, but it has since encroached on other habitats, including along the boundary of Walker Lake. In coordination with UNR and the WRPT, the Chinese beetle is used to control tamarisk on the installation. The previous INRMP indicated that NEPA procedures would be followed before the Chinese beetle was introduced; however, no documentation has been submitted to verify that NEPA procedures were followed.

3.2.2.3 Plant Species of Special Concern

No federally listed or state protected plant species have been identified at HWAD. The Mount Grant watershed is maintained in a sound ecological condition, but special habitats have not been identified at HWAD. Therefore, no plan for threatened or endangered vegetation species has been established or is expected.

3.2.2.4 Active Military Zones and Industrial Area

General maintenance is required to control noxious and weedy species from encroaching and deteriorating various facilities and habitats in improved areas. HWAD has had a vehicle wash station on the installation since 2010. Training vehicles are washed before leaving the cantonment area so weeds will not be transferred to other areas. Vehicle undercarriages are also spot checked for cleanliness when arriving off station.

As a safety precaution, vegetation is controlled to reduce danger from animals (e.g., snakes) that might bask and forage in shrubs around building entrances if the vegetation grows too high. A summary of herbicide use is shown in Table 3-3. Control of weeds is confined to broadleaved plants in lawns, Russian thistle, cheatgrass, dandelion, and mustardweed. Visual inspections begin in April or May when vegetative growth first appears. Monitoring continues throughout the growing season. The HWAD IPMP provides detailed information regarding pesticide use and safety and is considered a part of this INRMP and is included as Appendix B (HWAD 2012b).

**Table 3-3.
Routine vegetation control**

Location	Area	Treatment	Frequency
Industrial and administrative buildings	52 buildings, 1-foot wide border around building	Soil sterilant to spot-treat, as necessary, to eliminate encroachment of vegetation onto building foundations and exteriors	Annually (winter)
Fire hydrants	1,105 hydrants, 3-foot radius surrounding hydrant	Soil sterilant for hydrants not in mowed areas	Annually (winter)
Sidewalks and streets	Throughout administrative, industrial, and housing areas	Contact herbicide, as necessary, to control vegetation in cracks in streets and sidewalks	Annually (April to September)
Industrial, administrative, and housing areas	Open landscaped areas	Soil sterilant to control vegetation	Annually (winter)
Railroads	214 miles, 16-foot wide swath	Soil sterilant to eliminate vegetation encroachment on right-of-way	Annually (winter)

In the magazine and storage building areas, the growth of native vegetation is encouraged to minimize soil erosion. Because of the potential fire hazard and costs associated with maintaining a vegetative cover in a desert climate, no additional cover is added. HWAD's IPMP promotes the use of disease-resistant flora, natural deterrents, and preventive maintenance practices to achieve a healthy and aesthetically pleasing landscape without relying solely on synthetic pesticides and exotic flora.

Landscape trees and shrubs in the industrial, administrative, and housing areas are replaced as they degrade with age, disease, and damage. Trees suitable for planting include green ash (*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*), ginkgo (*Ginkgo biloba*), linden (*Tilia americana*), honey locust (*Gleditsia triacanthos*), Canada redbud (*Cercis canadensis*), mulberry (*Morus* sp.), golden rain tree (*Koelrueteria paniculata*), Lombardy poplar (*Liriodendron tulipifera*), Bolleana poplar (*Populus nigra*), Rocky Mountain juniper (*Juniperus scopulorum*), Arizona cypress (*Cupressus arizonica*), and Jeffrey pine (*Pinus jefferyi*). Suitable shrubs include lilac (*Syringa* sp.), forsythia (*Forsythia* sp.), goldenchain (*Laburnum* sp.), spirea (*Spirea* sp.), Japanese snowbell (*Styrax japonica*), honeysuckle (*Lonicera* sp.), and some rose (*Rosa* sp.) species. Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*), which is the primary lawn grass, will be phased out as a more suitable replacement is identified; fescue is being considered. The plant list will be reevaluated by reviewing their suitability in relation to the desert habitat, requirements for fertilizer, insecticide treatment, and irrigation. The following are additional factors that HWAD will consider in selecting trees and shrubs for landscape planting:

- Size and maturity
- Deciduous or evergreen (wind resistance)
- Growth rate (pruning requirements)
- Hardiness (tolerance to cold)
- Adaptability to soil and climate conditions
- Habits (flowering, fruiting, type of root system, and shedding)
- Density of shade cast (effect of intensity of shade on growth of grass)

Appendix E contains the U.S. Army Technical Manual 5-630 (*Natural Resources Land Management*), which provides specific criteria for water-efficient plantings and minimizing irrigation at installations that are in arid climates including golf courses (U.S. Army 1982). Appendix E also contains elements of the *General Landscape Plants Maintenance Guide* used at HWAD. HWAD improved grounds—except the Conelly housing area—are served by irrigation systems. The systems include the use of quick coupling, pop-up, or standard heads, depending on the location requirements. Windbreaks are irrigated by applying water in furrows. A drip system has been installed on several short runs of tree-lined windbreaks.

Lawns are irrigated as needed. The first irrigation in the spring and the last irrigation in the fall are sufficient in duration to soak the soil to a depth of 12 to 18 inches. Intervening irrigations are sufficient to penetrate to 6 to 10 inches. During any irrigation, the applications rate is low enough so that water penetrates to the depth desired without any accumulation on the surface or runoff.

Trees and shrubs are irrigated deeply and only frequently enough to ensure adequate moisture for plant growth.

3.3 Soil Conservation and Erosion Control Management

The primary goals of soil conservation and erosion control management at HWAD are to identify eroded soils, protect soil resources, and prevent soil erosion and potential effects on water quality, habitat, and mission objectives.

3.3.1 Goals and Objectives

HWAD manages soils with the intent to minimize soil disturbance and to restore the natural vegetative cover in disturbed areas where management is feasible. HWAD's goals and objectives for soil conservation and erosion control management are listed in Table 3-4.

Table 3-4.
Goals and objectives for soil conservation/erosion control management

Goals	Objectives
Continue to incorporate lessons learned from former soil erosion problems into erosion control practices.	Routinely review installation grounds to identify areas subject to erosion and identify areas in need of additional restoration. Use non-invasive or native plant species for erosion control.
Maintain and where possible, increase vegetative cover on installation lands to reduce soil erosion and facilitate maintenance, restoration, and revegetation.	Encourage the use of installation-generated organic matter to apply to enhance soil quality and promote vegetative growth.
Reduce exposure of pollutants to stormwater and runoff and minimize erosion.	Continue to implement best management practices (BMPs) to minimize erosion, conserve soil resources, and protect vegetation consistent with the SWPPP.

3.3.2 Management Measures

The overall objective of soil conservation and management on HWAD is to avoid soil disturbance. Soils on HWAD are highly subject to wind and water erosion, as the desert climate prevents a protective vegetative cover from developing and protecting the soil surface from erosion. Where those areas are disturbed as a result of anthropogenic activities or natural causes, soils will be stabilized and repaired in a timely manner to avoid excessive erosion. Sources of erosion and sedimentation, runoff, and dust will continue to be controlled to prevent damage to land, water resources, equipment, and facilities on the installation.

HWAD will continue to apply a soil stabilizer in the magazine areas where loading and unloading activities occur, which can disrupt the vegetation and increase soil erosion. The soil stabilizer is free of oil, acid, alkali salt, and other substances that could harm plants and wildlife. HWAD uses a more proactive approach and uses gravel for the stabilizer. It is well-suited for railroad beds and the runoff is controlled by absorption. The rock keeps the soil from moving except for extreme acts of nature such as torrential rains or flash flooding. HWAD maintains 2 feet of earth cover. HWAD will also continue to maintain the system of ditches in the magazine and storage areas to control drainage and reduce soil erosion (Peterson, personal communication, 2013c).

HWAD will continue to install stormwater monitoring programs and control measures as necessary to maintain Multi-Sector General Permit and Construction General Permit compliance. Construction projects are followed up with restoration of the surface soils and seeding or plantings to revegetate the area quickly. Minimal road maintenance activities are conducted on unpaved roadways (e.g., maintain road drainage, clear vegetation and boulders, reconstruct when major erosion conditions warrant). Where vegetative cover is removed or deteriorates in developed areas, it is replaced with a plant species that is native and climate-tolerant. Quick replacement minimizes the opportunity for erosion from wind or runoff. Appendix F includes the SWPPP BMPs erosion prevention requirements and additional erosion control measures that are implemented on installation property.

HWAD implements the following erosion control measures for installation activities:

- Implement required BMPs in construction contracts on construction sites
- Install sediment fencing, stacked hay bales, and mulching and geotextile matting around all construction sites
- Inspect BMPs and revegetate disturbed sites
- Routinely inspect for signs of erosion
- Maintain the system of ditches in the magazine and storage areas to control drainage and reduce soil erosion
- Inspect all structural and nonstructural erosion controls routinely, consistent with the SWPPP

3.4 Water Resources Management

3.4.1 Goals and Objectives

The primary goal of water resources management at HWAD is to protect and conserve the installation's water resources. HWAD's goals and objectives for surface water and groundwater are presented in Table 3-5.

**Table 3-5.
Goals and objectives for water resources management**

Goals	Objectives
Maintain the Mount Grant watershed in an ecologically balanced condition to support the water quality for the military mission.	Conduct activities that enhance or restore Mount Grant.
Manage Walker Lake to support the military mission and improve habitat	Coordinate with state and federal agencies regarding the water quality of Walker Lake.
Reduce erosion and sedimentation in water resources.	Continue evaluation of effectiveness of existing BMPs to reduce sedimentation and erosion of streams and assess possibilities of additional management practices.

3.4.2 Management Measures

The purpose of water management is to establish sound conservation practices and policies to guide personnel in integrating the management of installation water resources with the military mission and the surrounding ecosystem requirements. Potable water is a scarce resource for HWAD and the surrounding area. The objective of water management is to use water conservation practices in daily water consumption to protect and enhance water resources at HWAD.

The importance to ecological and human health of maintaining healthy water bodies at HWAD is reinforced by federal and state laws and regulations. In addition, AR 200-1 promotes the importance of maintaining healthy water resource systems on Army installations (HQDA 2007). Protecting and improving HWAD water quality in the installation's streams is especially important because the streams are the drinking water supply for HWAD. Water quality unable to support a diverse and healthy population of aquatic life would have an indirect adverse effect on all wildlife and invertebrate species; therefore, maintaining the water's high quality is important to preserve the ecological integrity of the water resources on HWAD.

HWAD assesses water quality on the installation. The assessment program includes routine potable water and groundwater sampling and monitoring across the installation. Information and data from such programs help to characterize the condition of water resources, characterize the health of associated aquatic life, and identify water quality concerns.

HWAD will continue to treat the Mount Grant watershed reservoirs' potable water supplies with chlorine to comply with drinking water regulations. Potable water quality will continue to be monitored per the measures listed in Table 2-6. HWAD will continue to restrict and monitor access to the Mount Grant watershed and reservoir areas in accordance with security procedures to protect water quality and the water supply. The installation will maintain vegetative buffers along streams in the Mount Grant watershed to allow pollution and sediment in runoff to be filtered through existing vegetation before entering receiving streams.

HWAD will continue groundwater monitoring sampling procedures and frequency in accordance with the installation's *Work Plan for Basewide Groundwater Monitoring Program*.

To support the recharge of Walker Lake, HWAD will continue to release excess water (after HWAD requirements are met) from Mount Grant to Walker Lake.

The HWAD Explosive Ordnance Disposal Department will continue to survey the UXO area at the south end of Walker Lake. Found ordnance will be disposed of in accordance with the MMRP. HWAD maintains a line of security buoys across the northern boundary in the lake to restrict access from the lake to the south shore because of the UXO concerns. Access to the lake from boat ramps in the town of Walker Lake is allowed up to the security buoys. Other than monitoring the integrity of the security buoys, HWAD applies no other management activities to the lake.

3.5 **Wetland Management**

Wetlands are critically important for protecting living resources because they provide essential breeding, spawning, nesting, and wintering habitat for many fish and wildlife species. Wetlands also enhance the quality of surface water by impeding erosive forces of moving water, trapping waterborne sediment and associated pollutants, maintaining base flow through the gradual release of stored floodwaters and groundwater, and providing a natural means of flood control and storm damage protection by absorbing and storing water during high-runoff periods.

DoD natural resources policy states that wetlands will be protected to the extent possible. All activities affecting wetlands require environmental analysis in accordance with AR 200-1 and compliance with applicable federal and state laws and regulations (HQDA 2007).

3.5.1 **Goals and Objectives**

The primary goal of wetland management at HWAD is to protect and conserve its wetland resources. HWAD’s goals and objectives for surface water and groundwater are presented in Table 3-6.

**Table 3-6.
Goals and objectives for wetland management**

Goals	Objectives
Protect, maintain, enhance wetlands, and ensure no net loss of these habitats.	Continue weekly inspections of wetlands on Mount Grant. Continue water quality management procedures that protect wetlands from excessive nonpoint source runoff.

3.5.2 **Management Measures**

The purpose of wetland management is to protect, maintain, and enhance the wetlands at HWAD. The primary objective for managing wetlands is in accordance with the CWA, as amended, to maintain and restore the chemical, physical, and biological integrity of the water. Maintaining biological integrity is required to support the water quality for the military mission and is the best way to protect the water quality for the wetland ecosystems. HWAD will manage Mount Grant to be used as the model for managing wetlands on the installation. The wetlands on HWAD are recognized as a vital source of water and habitat for wildlife. The monitoring practices used for Mount Grant watershed are also used to manage the wetlands on the installation.

At least three times per week, HWAD inspects the wetlands on Mount Grant for the following:

- Damage to the inlet screens to the water collection pipes from catch basins, which limit the entry of large objects and animals
- Damage to the creek beds
- Dead animals
- Damage to the fence line and resulting encroachment by cattle
- Evidence of unauthorized personnel
- Any change that threatens, or potentially threatens, the health of the watershed

3.6 Wildland Fire and Prescribed Burn Management

Wildland fire prevention and suppression is a matter of concern for military support activities and natural resources management at HWAD. Wildland fires can interfere with ongoing military support activities and have indirect and direct effects on habitats and species. From an ecological standpoint, positive effects from wildland fires can occur, provided the fuel loads are not excessive, such as returning nutrients to the soil, releasing seeds of fire-dependent species, increasing diversity, and an overall revitalization of habitat. Wildland fire prevention and suppression involve minimizing fire occurrence by educating HWAD personnel on fire prevention techniques, reducing natural fire fuels, being well prepared for fires, and when necessary, rapidly suppressing and containing the spread of wildland fires that do occur.

3.6.1 Goals and Objectives

Goals and objectives for wildland fire/prescribed fire management at HWAD are listed in Table 3-7.

**Table 3-7.
Goals and objectives for wildland fire/prescribed burn management**

Goals	Objectives
Reduce wildland fire hazards caused by natural weather events and human error.	Manage prescribed burns and habitat to prevent wildland fires.
Maintain multiagency coordination with fire management.	Reduce response time and increase aid to fighting wildland fires.

3.6.2 Management Measures

HWAD will continue to manage wildland fires in accordance with the *Wildland Fire Response*, the *Fire Prevention Manual*, and the *Emergency Response Plan*. HWAD’s Fire Department is responsible for the entire fire prevention and protection program (DZHC 1996, 1997). Updated versions of the emergency response plan will be included in Appendix D, when available.

Perform mechanical removal of woody fuels that contribute to fire potential (sagebrush-pinyon woodlands). Continue prescribed burns under non-catastrophic conditions. HWAD should allow for prescribed burns when feasible.

Maintain MOAs, MOUs, and cooperative agreements with state and federal agencies, Mineral County, and other cooperating agencies for fire and emergency management.

3.7 Agricultural Grazing Outleasing Management

Agricultural grazing is incompatible with the ongoing military support activities at HWAD and environmental considerations. No public grazing lands or agricultural grazing leases are on HWAD lands.

HWAD lands and resources are outleased for utility lines, water lines, and associated easements; Walker Lake Golf Course; and an easement for aerial crossing. HWAD land was sold for the Babbitt housing development and deeded to Mineral County (Hawthorne).

3.7.1 Goals and Objectives

The goals and objectives for agricultural grazing and outleasing management at HWAD are in Table 3-8.

**Table 3-8.
Goals and objectives for agricultural grazing and outleasing management**

Goals	Objectives
Maintain outleased areas and easements.	Continue practices for maintaining the groomed areas through which easements cross.

3.7.2 Management Measures

HWAD has no plans for additional outlease or further sale of properties.

3.8 Fish and Wildlife Management

The Fish and Wildlife Management program at HWAD sustains and improves fish and wildlife populations and their habitats consistent with accepted scientific principles, in compliance with applicable laws and regulations, and in consideration of the natural resources management program as outlined in AR 200-1 (HQDA 2007). Habitat management conserves and enhances existing flora and fauna consistent with the Army’s goal to conserve, protect, and sustain biological diversity while supporting the military mission.

3.8.1 Fisheries Management

3.8.1.1 Fisheries Goals and Objectives

The primary goal of fisheries management at HWAD is to protect and conserve its fishery resources. HWAD’s goals and objectives for fisheries management are presented in Table 3-9.

**Table 3-9.
Goals and objectives for fisheries management**

Goals	Objectives
Improve habitat quality for fish species to maintain healthy and balanced wildlife populations and enhance biodiversity.	Continue to focus on ecosystem based management, emphasizing overall ecological integrity of installation habitats.
	Continue to coordinate with federal and state fish and wildlife management agencies.

3.8.1.2 Fisheries Management Measures

HWAD's primary objectives for managing fish and benthos resources is to (1) minimize the impact of military mission on wildlife and its habitat, (2) maintain conditions that help to buffer the effects of the dewatering processes on the fish and benthos communities, and (3) support monitoring efforts to document the health of the fish and benthos communities.

HWAD confers with cooperating governmental agencies for wildlife materials and professional expertise.

Rose Creek Reservoir is an artificial reservoir subject to draining and cleaning every 3 to 5 years, depending on the level of sedimentation. As funding becomes available, population assessments of biotic flora and fauna at HWAD might be conducted. Those surveys would assist in determining causes of imbalances in the creek, reservoir, and wetland systems.

HWAD has introduced tui chub (*Gila bicolor*) into Rose Creek Reservoir to evaluate if restocking efforts for Walker Lake might be feasible in the future. HWAD will continue to monitor the success rate of tui chub reproduction in Rose Creek Reservoir for possible reintroduction to the lake.

LCT are unable to survive in Walker Lake because of elevated TDS levels. Monitoring of the water quality of the lake will continue to determine if sport fishing can be reintroduced at Walker Lake.

The federal recovery plan for the LCT focuses on (1) a self-sustaining, network trout population of wild, indigenous strains, established in interconnected habitat, i.e., in streams, lakes, mainstem and tributaries of the Walker River Basin. (2) Connectivity exists between suitable spawning and rearing habitats to support natural reproduction and recruitment, to restore self-sustaining lacustrine trout in lakes, mainstem, and tributaries of Walker River Basin. (3) A self-sustaining lacustrine population is naturally reproducing with an age class structure consisting of at least four year classes, a stable or increasing population size supported by documented reproduction and recruitment. These conditions must demonstrated to have been met for a minimum of 20 years. (4) Water is obtained through water right purchases or other means to protect and secure a stable Walker Lake ecosystem and meet life history and habitat requirements of trout. (5) A flow regime for the mainstem Walker River is implemented that facilitates trout migration, life history, and habitat requirements. (6) A commitment is secured from respective responsible entities to operate and maintain reservoirs and fish passage facilities in the basin in a manner that facilitates migration and reproductive behavior of trout. (7) Threats to trout and its habitat have been reduced or modified to a point where they no longer represent a threat of extinction or irreversible population decline (WRBRIT 2003).

3.8.2 Wildlife Management

3.8.2.1 Wildlife Management Goals and Objectives

The primary goal of wildlife management at HWAD is to protect and conserve its wildlife resources. HWAD's goals and objectives for wildlife management are presented in Table 3-10.

Table 3-10.
Goals and objectives for wildlife management

Goals	Objectives
Support monitoring efforts to document the health and biodiversity of game and non-game wildlife communities.	Continue collecting and maintain records of the number and type of mammals harvested annually.
Improve habitat, improve populations of species of conservation priority, and control predators if necessary.	Continue coordinating with state and federal agencies for fish and wildlife management.
Improve habitat quality for wildlife species to maintain healthy and balanced wildlife populations to and enhance biodiversity.	Continue to improve the diversity and quality of native forage for wildlife species. Continue to incorporate baseline information into natural resources planning and decision making. Continue to focus on ecosystem based management, emphasizing overall ecological integrity of installation habitats.
Control non-native mammal species to prevent degradation of installation land with respect to safety, training, and wildlife management.	Continue to document and map occurrences of key exotic/non-native species that are observed.

3.8.2.2 Wildlife Management Measures

HWAD's primary objectives for managing mammals, birds, and predator species is to (1) maintain conditions that will buffer the effects of the military mission on the wildlife communities, (2) control hunting and trapping activities to both support sport hunting and maintain and enhance wildlife community levels, and (3) support monitoring efforts to document the health and biodiversity of the wildlife community.

HWAD will continue to improve the diversity and quality of native forage for wildlife species and incorporate baseline information into natural resources planning and decision making.

HWAD collects and maintains records of the number and types of mammals harvested annually from HWAD lands. The Security Division uses this information to evaluate the health of the game mammal populations and habitats and to determine the optimal levels of population control. Management of individual species will continue in coordination with NDOW and USFWS. NDOW provides monitoring support and sets limits for large and small game mammals and birds. HWAD maintains records of reports of the number and types of mammals observed by hunters to update its listing of mammals and its knowledge of mammal habits and population levels. Hunting activities are subject to security restrictions on HWAD. The activities are prohibited except for limited Nelson desert bighorn hunts.

The only control for bats is to limit access to buildings. Inspections are conducted during the summer and winter months and if there is an access problem, the access points used by the bats are plugged to limit building entry. The pest controller conducts the inspections along with the production supply depot operations personnel to the buildings when doing storage and shipping functions and facilities personnel manage the repairs. There are 3 state protected bat species and they are discussed below in Section 3.9, Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species Management (Peterson, personal communication, 2013c).

Predator Control. Predator control is coordinated with NDOW. Populations of native predators will remain constant, provided that no epidemics or other imbalances occur. Predator populations do not exceed levels that the habitat can support; although it might be near its carrying capacity. The California black bear is an introduced species to the area that is considered a nuisance. HWAD will continue to coordinate management with NDOW to ensure that no species is hunted below population levels that can recover and sustain a healthy and viable population.

Mountain lion hunting is not allowed at HWAD, and the animal will be removed by a government trapper, if necessary. HWAD commanding officer and recommendations by NDOW typically regulate mountain lion hunting on HWAD, but because of security restrictions, mountain lion hunting is not allowed. Rather than harvesting mountain lions as a strategy to benefit reestablishing the local bighorn sheep population, NDOW has opted for releasing additional bighorn sheep to increase the breeding population.

Trapping on HWAD occurs only for predator control and is not conducted regularly.

NDOW supports two security requirements to discourage prospective hunters: (1) access to HWAD hunting areas is limited to specified periods, and (2) hunters first must secure permission from HWAD, in addition to the state-required licensing. Those additional requirements could reduce the number of hunters. However, security of the installation lands and the limited access to the hunting areas are significant elements in HWAD's management practices that result in the excellent health and diversity of the Mount Grant ecosystem. These management practices support the validity of the Army stewardship abilities, and installation security must not be compromised. However, HWAD will modify permit restrictions as needed to accommodate hunters and researchers, as security measures allow.

Management of mule deer through harvesting will continue to protect critical areas from over foraging. Emphasis will be given to winter harvesting; NDOW allows mule deer hunting from early November to early December. If evidence of over foraging is observed and cannot be kept in check by sport hunters, HWAD will coordinate with NDOW to ensure that the ecosystem integrity is maintained. Security restrictions at HWAD do not allow for mule deer hunting.

NDOW and NRCS recommend thinning of some pinyon-juniper areas to open these habitats and increase the quality of the habitat for wildlife. Pinyon-juniper thinning that can also protect the riparian areas from deteriorating and causing increased erosion to waterways. Thinning benefits wildlife by opening up areas where grass and forb species have been crowded out by an over-mature pinyon-juniper canopy, allowing them to obtain enough sunlight and moisture to grow. A healthy understory of grasses and forbs is a better food source for wildlife. For water quality, the increase in grasses, forbs, and their roots helps stabilize the soil surface from runoff and erosion, reducing the soil and litter that could otherwise erode into the waterways, thereby degrading the water quality. Therefore, HWAD will evaluate the need for resources required and best method and schedule for thinning riparian areas.

Nelson Desert Bighorn Sheep. Management of Nelson desert bighorn sheep will continue to focus on reestablishing the herd by monitoring population growth, increasing the herd numbers and improving genetic diversity with additional outside stock and neighboring populations, and allowing hunting. Because there is an opportunity for augmentation of the herd through NDOW efforts, management favors increasing the herd numbers from outside stock. Hunting bighorn sheep is the only hunting allowed by HWAD on Mount Grant. Groups of approximately 10 people are allowed to take one bighorn sheep per party and 3 tags have been issued to HWAD.

In accordance with the cooperative agreement signed in 1988 between HWAD and NDOW, HWAD does not allow domestic sheep (*Ovis aries*) grazing within the reservation boundaries in the Mount Grant area. Appendix C contains a copy of the cooperative agreement for the reintroduction of Nelson desert bighorn sheep. The cooperative agreement includes this provision, because domestic sheep carry and transmit a form of pneumonia to which the Nelson desert bighorn sheep are susceptible. HWAD supports the agreement by prohibiting domestic sheep inside its boundary and seeks support from USFWS and NDOW to manage the buffer zone

Feral Horses. Management of feral horses consists of monitoring population levels and range and water quality. The Gillis Range feral horse population extends onto the portion of Walker Lake managed by the installation. The population is expected to increase such that the herd will require culling to avoid damage to wetlands and water quality. In the past, the feral horses occurred on the east side of lake but recently have been returning to the south and east side because of receding lake levels. The BLM has primary responsibility to control the feral horse population; if monitoring efforts identify the need for additional management, HWAD will notify and coordinate activities with BLM.

Wildlife Reintroduction. The Rocky Mountain elk (*Cervus canadensis*) is no longer considered a potential candidate for introduction onto HWAD. In 1990 John Nelson, the acting HWAD commanding officer, signed an agreement with USACE Sacramento District to develop NEPA documentation to address introducing Rocky Mountain elk to Mount Grant. The feasibility investigation indicated that this introduction was not in the best interest of the installation; therefore, the effort was not pursued. No changes have occurred since 1990 to warrant readdressing the issue. NDOW would like to maintain the option of introducing elk in the future.

NDOW has considered reintroducing pronghorn antelope (*Antilocapra americana*) to Mount Grant to establish a hunting population and increase biodiversity. Since 2008, the south end of Walker Lake has 50 to 60 antelope grazing. The Old Bomb Area south of the South Magazine area has 10 to 20 transient antelope. HWAD and NDOW have no plans to release pronghorn in the near future on Mount Grant.

Birds. The primary objective of managing birds at HWAD is to maintain conditions that buffer the effects of the military mission on the bird communities, control hunting activities to both support sport hunting and maintain and enhance wildlife community levels, and support monitoring efforts to document the health and biodiversity. The greater sage-grouse is a candidate species listed by USFWS and discussions related to the sage-grouse are in Section 3.9.2 below.

Consistent with the goals of the MBTA, HWAD will continue to implement the provisions of the act. Protection of migratory birds and their habitats is also accomplished indirectly through the protection of nongame and game species.

The chukar population is managed similar to the sage-grouse. NDOW sets bag limits for chukar harvesting, allowing hunting from early October to the middle or end of January, although hunting at HWAD is not allowed because of security restrictions.

Management of blue grouse supports the NDOW ban on blue grouse hunting, consistent with Mineral County. Blue grouse are considered fairly tame because they can be approached rather closely and are known to sometimes freeze or become rigid when approached rather than flying away. Because of this behavior, blue grouse might be easier to observe than other more secretive species. As funding becomes available, this population will be monitored, and its natural history will be investigated further to determine if habitat restoration or enhancements should be pursued.

California quail populations in the Mount Grant watershed could be supplemented after a proposing agency funds studies to document impacts to demonstrate that there would be no significant negative environmental impacts. NDOW formerly considered releasing California quail trapped in the wild at Mount Grant to supplement the existing reintroduced population. However, small populations of California quail have been identified throughout Nevada. NDOW has no plans for releasing California quail, and HWAD would support future NDOW reintroduction efforts for this species. NDOW allows California quail hunting from early October to the middle or end of January, but is not authorized because of security restrictions.

HWAD updates its listing of birds of prey, neotropical migrants, local songbirds, and incidental observations through surveys, hunters, and birder reports. HWAD has proposed additional management actions to further protect bird habitats beyond the action of access restrictions by creating additional riparian habitat and thinning pinyon-juniper habitat in the upper elevations of Mount Grant. Additional management actions could include consultation with NDOW or USFWS to develop BMPs.

HWAD monitors and USFWS manages bald eagles in accordance with the 2009 *Post-delisting Monitoring Plan for the Bald Eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*) in the Contiguous 48 States* (USFWS 2009).

Rock dove populations require control in the industrial and active military zones. These abundant bird species and other birds nest above building doorways and deteriorate building exteriors. Nuisance bird species are controlled by manually removing their nests from building tops and ledges.

Reptiles and Amphibians. The primary objective for managing reptiles and amphibians at HWAD is to maintain conditions that buffer the effects of the military mission on the reptile and amphibian communities, and support monitoring efforts to document the condition of the reptile and amphibian communities. The 1999 study conducted by UNR (Espinoza and Tracy 1999) found that the greatest threat to reptiles was being run over by vehicles.

The condition of reptile and amphibian communities is not well documented at HWAD, but as funding becomes available, the installation might monitor existing reptile and amphibian populations. A snake awareness program might be proposed to educate personnel of these species' beneficial use as natural predators of insects, small mammals, and other prey considered pests to humans.

3.9 *Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species Management*

As required by AR 200-1, the Army ensures that it carries out mission requirements in harmony with the requirements of the ESA (HQDA 2007). All Army land uses, including military training and testing, and recreation are subject to ESA requirements for the protection of listed species and critical habitat. In fulfilling its conservation responsibilities, the Army is required to work closely and cooperatively with the USFWS and NMFS in planning projects or activities to ensure ESA compliance. In conserving biological diversity, installation commanders and Army natural resource managers must develop and implement policies and strategies to maintain viable populations of native plants and animals, maintain natural genetic variability in and among populations, maintain functioning representations of the full spectrum of ecosystems and biological communities, and integrate human activities with biological diversity conservation. No critical habitat has been identified on HWAD.

3.9.1 *Goals and Objectives*

The primary goal for rare, threatened, and endangered species management at HWAD is to protect and conserve its most sensitive wildlife resources. HWAD's goals and objectives for rare, threatened, and endangered species management are presented in Table 3-11.

Table 3-11.
Goals and objectives for rare, threatened, and endangered species management

Goals	Objectives
Protect and enhance habitat and populations of those plant and animal species listed as rare, threatened, and endangered or those with the potential to be listed.	Assess the need for monitoring or research for those species with the potential to become listed. Continue to evaluate additional survey needs throughout the next 5 years. If threatened or endangered species or their habitat is identified at HWAD, determine if an Endangered Species Management Plan is needed.

3.9.2 *Management Measures*

HWAD's primary objective for managing special-status species is to (1) maintain conditions that buffer the effects of the military mission on the species and their habitat, (2) support monitoring efforts to document the health of species, and (3) enhance the habitats of the species. Appendix A lists rare, threatened, and endangered species known to occur at and around HWAD area, according to information from USFWS and NNHP.

Three bats are listed as Nevada special status species including the silver-haired bat, long-eared myotis, and California myotis. The pallid bat and the Townsend's big ear bat are listed as state protected but have not been identified at HWAD (NNHP 2013). Townsend's big eared bat is listed as a sensitive species in USFS's Region 4 – Humboldt-Toiyabe sensitive species (NNHP 2013) which is near the southeastern boundary of HWAD. No management measures are proposed for the bats except to leave them undisturbed. A list of bats is in Appendix A.

The Hiko white river springfish is the only species native to the HWAD area that is federally listed as endangered and is state-protected (USFWS 2013). However, this species has not been observed on HWAD land holdings and is presumed extinct in Mineral County, except for a refuge at Blue Link Spring in eastern Mineral County. The other federally protected species native to the

HWAD area is the LCT, which is federally listed threatened and state-protected but has been extirpated from Walker Lake because of high salinity levels. State-listed sensitive species observed on HWAD are the white-faced ibis and western snowy plover and are managed consistent with the MBTA.

HWAD has no formal Endangered Species Management Plan for the LCT. This INRMP provides the BMPs for this species. HWAD habitat protection measures combined with the monitoring research of USFWS and NDOW are consistent with the federally designed recovery plan for the LCT. As the USFWS implements the short-term action plan for LCT in the Walker Lake Basin, HWAD will work with USFWS and NDOW to evaluate the remaining elements of the plan and will coordinate its efforts to determine more specific data on LCT. HWAD will evaluate the condition of the buffer zones around the lake and the potential for Cottonwood Creek to serve as LCT habitat. HWAD will not prepare an Endangered Species Management Plan for the LCT. However, if the installation can assist in the recovery of this species, one will be prepared.

Managing and increasing the population of and habitat quality for sage-grouse is a high priority at HWAD. To reduce population loss from poachers, HWAD has proposed to close off Wheeler Pass, the gully between the Mount Grant main gate, and Militch ruins to minimize the number of poachers entering the area. HWAD would also like to improve habitat in the Mount Grant North Cat area by installing rock dikes or similar infrastructure to minimize snowmelt runoff and to create riparian habitat in the meadow area. The pinyon-juniper communities at higher elevations of Mount Grant might be removed to increase population and minimize predation. In the summer of 2012, 18 sage-grouse were collared and are being tracked using telemetry to track them to understand their movements from season to season (Peterson, personal communication, 2013b). The National Greater Sage-Grouse Planning Strategy is moving forward, and updates are at <http://www.blm.gov/wo/st/en/prog/more/sagegrouse.html>.

Because of the concern related to the sage-grouse on Mount Grant and because of security reasons, hunting has been strictly limited and is not permitted by HWAD. Management strategies to protect the sage-grouse were presented in the *Initial Conservation Assessment and Strategies* (Nachlinger 2003) and the *Greater Sage Grouse Conservation Plan for Nevada and California* (NDOW 2004). These strategies include instituting a more natural fire regime, reducing and managing nonnative plant invasions, establishing sagebrush in perennial grasslands, managing riparian areas, and eliminating inappropriate livestock use. HWAD follows those strategies whenever feasible.

Conservation strategies for the greater sage-grouse have been updated in the 2012 *Bi-State Action Plan – Past, Present, and Future Actions for Conservation of the Greater Sage-Grouse Bi-State Distinct Population Segment*. A list of priority conservation strategies has been proposed in the Mount Grant PMU through actions designed to (BTACNC 2012)

- Minimize large scale habitat loss from wildland fire by implementing fuel reduction treatments, using green strips in strategic locations to protect sage-grouse habitat, and by prioritizing sage-grouse habitat for aggressive initial fire suppression
- Minimize direct habitat loss and disturbance because of mineral and geothermal development
- Conserve and improve available meadow habitats
- Treat pinyon-juniper encroachment to increase the availability of nesting habitat especially at lower elevations and to facilitate connectivity in and among populations

- Reduce impacts of existing infrastructure

Additional benefits could be realized by implementing conservation measures designed to

- Minimize the spread of noxious weeds
- Maintain feral horse numbers in designated territory boundaries
- Improve grazing management practices in site-specific areas
- Reduce human disturbance in key seasonal use areas
- Minimize potential sources of direct mortality

3.10 Outdoor Recreation

Recreational opportunities on HWAD are limited because of security restrictions. However, HWAD continues to protect and maintain the natural resources on which those recreational activities rely.

3.10.1 Goals and Objectives

Goals and objectives for outdoor recreation at HWAD are listed in Table 3-12.

Table 3-12.
Goals and objectives for outdoor recreation

Goals	Objectives
Identify and encourage low impact programs and activities for multiple uses of natural resources.	Continue to encourage conservation research and collaborative restoration opportunities with educational institutions, public agencies, and nongovernmental organizations.
Manage Mount Grant watershed recreation activities.	Limit access to Mount Grant via security restrictions.

3.10.2 Management Measures

HWAD will continue to make installation resources available to universities and other organizations for studying ecosystems and wildlife. That will be conducted as a continuous effort as local universities and organizations show interest in installation land. Doing so can provide HWAD with monitoring information about specific characteristics or responses to management efforts. Projects proposed and funded by universities and organizations, such as UNR and TNC, can supplement installation expertise and staff. The information gained from the group’s activities will supplement installation databases and general knowledge of the ecosystems present, could include annual bird or mammal surveys and management of plant or animal species, and could be used to promote conservation.

HWAD will continue to limit access to Mount Grant in accordance with security procedures to protect the water supply and military training missions. Hunting will be allowed on Mount Grant to groups of no more than 10 people to hunt bighorn sheep (3 tags per year). Public access for traveling to top of Mount Grant is limited but allowed (no off-road vehicles). Access will

continue to be granted to members of the WRPT for ceremonial activities on Mount Grant. All these activities must be authorized by HWAD.

Golfing will continue to be permitted at the Walker Lake Golf Course. Golfers will continue to enter through the HWAD Industrial Area/Main Base Main Security Gate.

3.11 Law Enforcement Program

Effective enforcement of laws and regulations applicable to natural resources enhances the overall natural resources program, protects natural and cultural resources, and provides public safety by enforcing off-limit areas and protecting areas from criminal destruction of natural resources.

3.11.1 Goals and Objectives

The primary goal for law enforcement at HWAD is to enforce natural resources laws and regulations. The objectives that will be implemented to ensure that the goal is achieved are presented in Table 3-13.

**Table 3-13.
Goals and objective for law enforcement**

Goals	Objectives
Protect the natural resources of HWAD by enforcing laws and regulations.	Ensure that all laws and regulations pertaining to natural resources at HWAD are in accordance with the laws and regulations of the United States and Nevada.

3.11.2 Management Measures

Federal and state natural resources laws should be reviewed regularly, and pertinent or applicable changes should be considered for incorporation into HWAD’s regulations. In addition, incident reports should be reviewed to ensure that adequate actions have been taken in each instance, and enforcement activities should be evaluated to determine their adequacy in protecting HWAD’s natural resources.

Maintain staffing levels of trained and capable natural resource law enforcement personnel sufficient to effectively monitor and enforce all natural resource laws and regulations. Ensure that all natural resources law enforcement personnel meet the requirements for training and weapons qualifications according to their experience and rank, and receive appropriate continuing education to enhance understanding of natural resources and ecosystem management.

Enforce natural resources laws and regulations at HWAD, conduct patrols adequate to cover the installation and prioritize them to ensure protection of sensitive resources; educate military personnel and the public about natural resource protection and how to report violations; file reports for all known violations and law enforcement actions.

3.12 Invasive Species Management

EO 13112 (Invasive Species) was signed in February 1999 to prevent the introduction of invasive species; provide for their control; and minimize the economic, ecological, and human health effects from such species. EO 13112 defines invasive species as alien species whose introduction causes or is likely to cause economic or environmental harm or harm to human health. Per EO 13112, each federal agency whose actions might affect the status of invasive species must, to the extent practicable and permitted by law, use relevant programs and authorities to

- Prevent introduction of invasive species
- Detect and respond rapidly to and control populations of such species in a cost-effective and environmentally sound manner
- Monitor invasive species populations accurately and reliably
- Provide for restoration of native species and habitat conditions in ecosystems that have been invaded
- Conduct research on invasive species and develop technologies to prevent their introduction and to provide environmentally sound control
- Promote public education on invasive species and the means to address them

The control of invasive species is a priority for the pest management staff at HWAD. Management actions for the pest management program are included in the IPMP, which is updated annually or as needed. Invasive species have not had been managed under a formal management plan, but will be if needed.

3.12.1 Goals and Objectives

The goals and objectives for preventing new infestations and controlling existing invasive species infestations are provided in Table 3-14.

**Table 3-14.
Goals and objectives for invasive species management**

Goals	Objectives
Control invasive plant, insect, and mammal species to prevent degradation of land with respect to safety, training, and wildlife management.	Control invasive species on improved grounds using mechanical and biological control methods and approved chemical control methods.
Prevent new infestations of invasive species.	Report new infestations of invasive species to HWAD personnel.
Reduce tamarisk growth at HWAD.	Develop a management plan to reduce tamarisk from growing and spreading (if not already prepared).

3.12.2 Management Measures

Managing invasive species is integrated into pest management, water resources, and restoration activities on the installation.

The previous INRMP indicates UNR and the Nevada Department of Agriculture were preparing a management plan for the eradication and control of tamarisk along Walker Lake. This plan should be included in Appendix C if it has been prepared.

Continue to document and map occurrences of key exotic/invasive species that are observed during survey efforts or incidentally encountered; use this information to schedule and prioritize management actions for such species.

Prohibit planting of invasive species in ornamental landscaping, in wildlife supplemental food plots, and in revegetation projects.

Continue to wash all vehicles at the indoor vehicle wash station before leaving the industrial area to minimize transport of nonnative and invasive species.

3.13 Pest Management

Per AR 200-5, Environmental Quality: Pest Management, HWAD's IPMP is a comprehensive document defining the essential elements of the pest management program, such as health and environmental safety; pest identification; and pesticide storage, transportation, use, and disposal (HQDA 1999). Implementation will prevent or manage pests that interfere with the military support of HWAD, adversely affect human health, or damage property, structures, or material (HQDA 1999). The plan is used as a tool to reduce reliance on pesticides, enhance environmental protection, and maximize the use of IPM techniques. The plan also provides guidance for the judicious use of both chemical and nonchemical control techniques to achieve effective pest management with minimal environmental contamination. Adhering to the plan will ensure effective, economical, and environmentally acceptable pest management and compliance with applicable laws and regulations.

3.13.1 Goals and Objectives

The goal of the pest management program is to protect human health and suppress or prevent damage to real estate and natural resources caused by pests. The objective of the pest management program is to use IPM techniques to eliminate, suppress, or control pests with judicious use of both chemical and nonchemical control techniques. The goals and objectives for pest management are listed in Table 3-15.

**Table 3-15.
Goals and objectives for pest management**

Goals	Objectives
Protect human health and suppress or prevent damage to real estate and natural resources caused by pests.	Use IPM techniques to eliminate, suppress, or control pests with judicious use of both chemical and nonchemical control techniques.
Reduce the quantity of toxic pesticides used on the installation and promote more effective pest control practices.	Evaluate the effectiveness of control programs. Implement new pesticide reduction methodologies and equipment initiatives.
Remove or reduce exotic/invasive wildlife species on the installation.	Monitor invasive species and pests to determine if existing controls are appropriate.

3.13.2 Management Measures

Pests, weeds, and plant diseases are identified and controlled using chemical and nonchemical controls according to the most recent version of the IPMP (2012, see Appendix B). HWAD will continue to apply pesticides and herbicides in accordance with the IPMP.

HWAD works with NDOW to capture and release black bears where the black bear is considered a nuisance or threat to HWAD.

HWAD will continue to encourage natural ecological controls when possible to help regulate levels of insect populations. To the extent possible, habitat for natural control agents will be provided by implementing ecosystem management goals and objectives. SOC will review new information and research on IPM options as it becomes available to explore additional natural controls for pest populations.

Continue to remove individual pest wildlife species, especially coyotes. Consider improving fences around industrial area to minimize coyotes from passing through.

3.14 Cultural and Paleontological Resources

HWAD will continue to manage cultural resources in accordance with the ICRMP. Information on the installation's cultural resources goals, objectives, and management measures are in the HWAD ICRMP. Cultural resources management at HWAD is provided in accordance with a number of federal legislation; federal regulations and guidelines; EO and presidential memoranda; U.S. Army regulations, protocols, and guidelines; and installation-specific guidance. The most significant of these are

- NHPA sections 106 and 110
- Archaeological Resources Protection Act
- American Indian Religious Freedom Act
- Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act
- EO 11593 (Protection and Enhancement of Cultural Environment)
- DoD Directive 4710.1 (Archaeological and Historic Resources Management, 1984)
- AR 200-4 (Cultural Resources Management) (HQDA 1998)
- AR 420-40 (Historic Preservation) (HQDA 1984)

The ICRMP is designed to complement other HWAD plans (such as the INRMP) and serve as the HWAD commander's decision document for actions that could affect cultural resources. The ICRMP is an internal Army compliance and management plan designed to integrate the entirety of the installation's cultural resources program with ongoing mission activities, allow for ready identification of potential impacts the installation's mission could have on the cultural resources management program, and identify compliance actions necessary to maintain the availability of mission-essential properties and acreage.

No paleontological resources have been identified at HWAD and no management measures are proposed. HWAD will comply with all state and federal requirements.

3.15 Summary of Management Measures

Below is a summary of resource-specific management measures major projects and initiatives proposed as part of natural resources management over the next 5 years at HWAD. Details regarding all management measures for each resource are in their respective sections above.

Facilities and developed areas

- Reduce the potential of hazardous waste releases from mercury storage by following the MOA between the Defense National Stockpile Center and the U.S. Army Joint Munitions Command for the Storage of the National Defense Stockpile Inventory Mercury.
- Continue cooperative agreements emergency and fire management with the Mineral County, the town of Hawthorne, WRPT, and state and federal agencies.

Vegetation Management

- Continue coordinating with the town of Hawthorne, Mineral County, and state and federal agencies regarding wildland fire management and emergency response.

Water Resources and Wetland Management

- Continue maintaining the Mount Grant watershed in an ecologically balanced condition to support a potable water supply to support the military mission.
- Continue water quality monitoring of groundwater and potable water sources.
- Continue conducting UXO surveys at Walker Lake to minimize potential hazards.

Wildland Fire and Prescribed Burning Management

- Continue cooperative agreements emergency and fire management with the Mineral County, the town of Hawthorne, and state and federal agencies.

Fish and Wildlife Management

- Monitor the success of the introduction of tui chub into Rose Creek Reservoir and potential future introduction to Walker Lake.
- Continue to monitor TDS levels in Walker Lake to determine if LCT might be reintroduced and if sport fishing could return.
- Continue cooperative agreements with natural resources agencies for wildlife surveys and management assistance.
- Continue to monitor American pikas as an indicator of how wildlife at higher elevations are faring under contemporary climate change and ascertain what actions may be done to facilitate their persistence and conservation.

Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species Management

- Continue to monitor and conduct surveys for threatened and endangered species and their habit to determine if additional management measures should be introduced at HWAD.
- Implement conservation strategies for the greater sage-grouse by continuing multi-agency coordination with the sage-grouse conservation initiative.

Invasive Species Management

- Develop a management plan to reduce tamarisk from growing and spreading. Previous INRMPs indicate that UNR and the Nevada Department of Agriculture were preparing a management plan along Walker Lake. It is undetermined if this was developed and evaluated under the NEPA process.

Pest Management

- HWAD should continue coordinating with NDOW about the management and removal of California black bear on Mount Grant and in the Industrial area. Evaluate whether a formal management plan should be developed.

Cultural Resources Management

- The cultural resource manager at HWAD consults as required for all projects in accordance with the ICRMP.

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4 IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Achieving No Net Loss to the Military Mission

To ensure the preparedness of the Armed Forces and consistent use of the installation, the Sikes Act section 101(b)(1)(I) states that each INRMP must provide for “no net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission of the installation” to the extent appropriate and applicable.

DoD policy stipulates appropriate management objectives to protect the mission capabilities of installation lands (from which annual projects are developed) should be clearly articulated in the planning process and should be high in INRMP resourcing priorities. The effectiveness of the INRMP in preventing *net loss* must be evaluated annually. Where applicable, mission requirements and priorities identified in the INRMP must be integrated into other environmental programs and policies. It is not the intent that natural resources be consumed but are instead sustained for the use of mission requirements. To achieve this, environmental programs and policies must have the goal of preserving the environment for the purpose of the mission.

There might be instances in which a net loss is unavoidable because of the need to fulfill regulatory requirements other than the Sikes Act, such as complying with a Biological Opinion under the provisions of the ESA or protection of wetlands under the provisions of the CWA.

No net loss in the capability of installation lands to support the military mission is expected as a result of implementing this INRMP.

4.1.1 Integrated Land Use and Natural Resources Decisions

HWAD continues to promote compatible uses of the installation by allowing hunting and other outdoor recreational pursuits to occur in conjunction with military support operations. While providing these ancillary uses of installation land, HWAD must also ensure that the installation

- Maintains vegetative cover to prevent and minimize erosion, ensuring the long-term sustainability of installation lands
- Maintains healthy, vigorous and biologically diverse habitats, and vegetative buffers for installation activities
- Ensures compliance with the CWA by preventing degradation of its water bodies, which serve as drinking water sources and provide recreational opportunities

The integrated land uses mentioned below affect funding and decision making of the ACO. In addition, Army regulations require compliance with federal regulations, such as the ESA and CWA, and resources must be put forth to ensure compliance with these and other federal laws and regulations. The expenditure of resources for these land uses is a necessity.

Habitat management supports the mission, provides for healthy, biologically diverse habitats, controls erosion, and supports multiple recreational activities such as hunting and sightseeing. These integrated land uses at HWAD and limited funding require the ACO to prioritize all management activities and funding decisions to ensure that the training lands are maintained and the installation is in compliance with all applicable federal regulations.

4.2 Supporting Sustainability of the Military Mission

As stated in Section 1.2, the goal of the HWAD INRMP is to ensure that natural resources and the military training support areas are managed to provide the optimum environment to sustain the military mission. The management measures in this INRMP have been developed to successfully achieve the stated objectives necessary to meet this goal.

The overlap of similar management measures for different resource areas is indicative of the relationship the components of an ecosystem have with one another. The need for integrated natural resources management is evident from the complexity of these relationships. For example, the Mount Grant watershed supports the military mission by providing a source of clean, potable water and serving as a valuable training area. The area also provides recreational opportunities such as hunting. In addition to being essential to support the military mission, the condition of Mount Grant and Walker Lake directly influence the quality of wildlife habitat and diversity of wildlife inhabiting HWAD. The condition of vegetated watersheds directly influences water quality, the condition of fisheries, and sensitive habitats such as wetlands. These habitats are necessary to maintain and increase biodiversity at HWAD.

Managing Mount Grant, Walker Lake, and other habitats using an ecosystem approach will maintain, protect, and enhance natural resources. Results from habitat assessments and surveys serve as indicators of the overall ecological health of installation property. Areas of degraded habitat and watersheds result in the loss of ecological integrity and biodiversity, and degraded water quality. Adaptive ecosystem management, soil stabilization, and revegetation projects improve the health of small-scaled habitats and watershed conditions over the larger scale. Soil stabilization and revegetation along waterways and in upland areas mitigate erosion, decreasing sediment loads to streams, lakes, ponds, and wetlands. The effects of small-scaled habitat improvements extend throughout the watershed benefitting wildlife, aquatic life, and improving the vigor of the ecological system.

4.2.1 Impacts to the Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use

HWAD works cooperatively with the military mission and sustainable land use to ensure that both installation needs are fulfilled.

4.3 Fish and Wildlife Consultation Requirements

The Sikes Act section 101(a)(2) states the INRMP must be prepared *in cooperation with* and reflect the *mutual agreement* of the USFWS and state and fish wildlife agencies “concerning conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources.” Mutual agreement is required only with respect to those elements of the plan subject to the authority derived from a source other than the Sikes Act, such as the ESA, where USFWS and state fish and wildlife agencies have authority to conserve, protect, and manage these resources. Nothing in the Sikes Act is intended to enlarge or diminish the existing authority of USFWS or state fish and wildlife agencies on military installations. If USFWS or the state fish and wildlife agency withhold their agreement with an INRMP because of objections to elements of the INRMP clearly outside the scope of the agency’s authority, the installation may finalize the INRMP and proceed to manage its natural resources in accordance with terms of the plan.

4.3.1 Endangered Species Act Consultation

The Sikes Act does not require an ESA consultation as part of an INRMP; however, DoD policy stipulates that in most cases INRMPs should incorporate, by reference, the results of an installation's previous species-by-species ESA consultations, including any reasonable and prudent measures that might have been identified in an incidental take statement. Consequently, neither a separate biological assessment nor a separate formal consultation should be necessary concerning most INRMPs or INRMP revisions. Nonetheless, because the INRMP might include management strategies or other actions designed to balance potentially competing needs of multiple species, listed or not, it might be prudent to engage in informal consultation with the USFWS during the INRMP revision process to confirm that such proposed actions will not affect listed species or designated critical habitat. If the INRMP includes management strategies or other actions that might affect listed species or designated critical habitat and these actions have not been the subject of previous consultations, an ESA section 7 consultation on these actions would be required before they may be implemented.

4.3.2 DoD Policy on Specific Coordination Requirements

In accordance with DoD policy guidance each installation must

- Establish and maintain regular communication with the appropriate USFWS and state fish and wildlife agency offices to address issues concerning natural resources management that are not addressed in the INRMP. At a minimum, this communication must include annual coordination with all cooperating offices.
- Invite the USFWS and NDOW to participate cooperatively in the scoping, design, and preparation of the INRMP. Doing so will inform these offices about the DoD mission, invite them to consider solutions to difficult resource management problems, and expedite final INRMP coordination.
- Advise all appropriate internal and external stakeholders of the intent to prepare or revise an INRMP within 30 days of starting such an action. When providing this notification to USFWS and state fish and wildlife agencies, each DoD installation must concurrently request the USFWS and state fish and wildlife agencies to participate in the development or revision of the INRMP.
- Notify appropriate USFWS and NDOW of its intent to provide a draft INRMP for review and coordination at least 60 days before delivering the document.

For the USFWS, the field office is the appropriate office for initial contact by installation for development and review of the INRMP. Pursuant to USFWS Sikes Act guidance, the field office must review the INRMP and provide preliminary agreement concerning the conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources detailed in the INRMP before review in the regional office and final action by the regional director.

4.4 GIS Management, Data Integration, Access, and Reporting

Efficient data collection, storage, management, and analysis are essential for conducting a comprehensive natural resource management program. Selected management measures useful for facilitating the integration and implementation of resource-specific management measures are outlined below.

4.4.1 Data Collection and Analysis

Complete integration of natural resources data facilitates the comprehensive analyses of the complex relationships between ecosystem components. Data collection provides a portion of the data necessary for these analyses and is a vital component of the land management program. This program is planned to continue through and beyond the 5-year scope of this INRMP.

4.4.2 Use of Imaging Tools

Using GPS will improve the accuracy of data collection, and the use of infrared photography and satellite imagery will significantly enhance the evaluation and integration process.

4.4.3 Update GIS Coverage

GIS is a useful tool for evaluating the relationship between various natural resource management activities and the military mission. GPS technology allows field staff to accurately map geographic features and to delineate various habitats in the field or to mark the exact location of a resource, such as wetlands and cultural features. GIS databases and map coverages for all natural resources are updated as the data become available.

GIS databases and map coverages can serve as powerful management tools for helping to integrate and implement resource-specific management measures presented in this INRMP. An overlay of the coverage for natural and cultural resource areas can graphically illustrate the complexity of the environment and provide the means to readily identify and resolve potential conflicts between natural resource issues and mission requirements.

4.4.4 Enforcement Education and Training

To ensure enforcement of laws and regulations necessary to protect the HWAD's natural resources, sufficient staffing levels of trained and capable natural resources law enforcement personnel should be maintained. Therefore, a need exists for natural resources enforcement education, training, and weapons qualifications. Education and training procedures should be evaluated and updated as necessary.

4.5 Training of Natural Resource Personnel

DoD Instruction 4715.3 states, "Necessary supplemental training to ensure proper and efficient management or protection of natural resources shall be provided quickly." Any new natural resource law enforcement officers hired at HWAD will qualify with personal sidearms semiannually and shotguns annually. Officers will have a minimum of 40 hours of refresher training each year.

4.6 Organizational Enhancement, Roles, and Responsibilities

The ecosystem approach described in this INRMP to manage natural resources at HWAD can be implemented by the installation's existing organization. The ACO has the primary role and responsibility for implementing this INRMP, which addresses the period from fiscal year 2013 to 2018. No major changes in organization are expected or necessary to implement this INRMP.

4.6.1 Staffing

HWAD does not have a core staff of professionally trained natural resources management personnel to implement this INRMP, but it relies on personnel in a variety of positions for managing the installation's natural resources. The ACO and the operating contractor have the primary responsibility for implementing the actions in the INRMP, and the ACO also oversees the natural resource activities performed by the real property officer and the security division manager. Additional natural resource responsibilities are shared by the HWAD Security Department, HWAD Contract Administration and Operations Division, HWAD Maintenance, Planning, and Housing. This team is also integrated with the master planning board to ensure more thorough input. The Natural Resources Conservation and Beautification Committee has the following members:

- Commander, chair (SJMHW-CO)
- Civilian executive assistant (SJMHW-XC)
- Chief, Contract Administration and Operations Division (SJMHW-CAO)
- Facilities management specialist (SJMHW-ORE)
- Environmentalist (SJMHW-OR)
- Security officer (SJMHW-55)
- Safety representative (SJMHW-SF)
- Recorder (SJMHW-OR)

4.6.2 Outside Assistance

Implementing a number of the projects discussed in this INRMP will require active outside assistance from state and federal agencies, private consortiums and organizations, universities, and contractors. HWAD is a GOCO facility, and additional coordination might be required with contractor personnel because their roles at the installation could change. Using these resources is the most efficient and cost-effective method for temporarily acquiring expertise. Some parties will be reimbursed for their assistance as noted in an MOU and contractual agreements; others will supply assistance in accordance with cooperative agreements.

4.7 Annual Review and Management Performance Evaluation

The Sikes Act section 101(b)(2) [16 U.S.C 670a(b)(2)] states that each INRMP “must be reviewed as to operation and effect by the parties thereto on a regular basis, but not less often than every 5 years.” Per DoD policy, the requirement to *review* the INRMP does not entail a revision of every INRMP. The Sikes Act specifically directs that the INRMPs be reviewed “as to operation and effect,” emphasizing that the review is intended to determine whether existing INRMPs are being implemented to meet the requirements of the Sikes Act and contribute to the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations.

DoD policy requires installations to review INRMPs annually in cooperation with the other parties to the INRMP. Annual reviews facilitate *adaptive management* by providing an opportunity for the parties to review the goals and objectives of the plan, and to establish a realistic schedule for undertaking proposed actions. Appendix I will contain any annual updates for the INRMP over the next 5 years.

DoD Instruction 4715.3 outlines the metrics for natural resources conservation management and the requirements to provide effective annual reviews of the INRMP. These metrics are used to assess the overall health and trends of each installation's natural resources program and to identify and correct potential funding and other resource shortfalls. The Sikes Act requires each installation with significant natural resources to report annually on the status of its INRMP implementation.

The installation must report progress toward meeting natural resources conservation program measures of merit to Deputy Under Secretary of Defense (Installations and Environment) at each environmental management review and to Congress in the Defense Environmental Programs Annual Report to Congress. HWAD must report the following:

- The installation name and location
- If the installation meets Sikes Act requirements
- If annual feedback has been received from USFWS
- If annual feedback has been received from NDOW
- Funding requirements in reporting per fiscal year to implement the INRMP
 - Amount required for recurring projects
 - Amount required for non-recurring projects

HWAD will use Natural Resources Conservation metrics to assess INRMP implementation, measure conservation efforts, ensure no net loss of military testing and training lands across the installation, understand installation mission support, and indicate the success of partnerships with USFWS and NDOW. Seven focus areas assess requirements, goals, and objectives of the Sikes Act annually for each installation with an INRMP. At a minimum, the installation will use the focus areas to assess the following:

- INRMP project implementation
 - Are INRMP projects, including follow-up inventorying and monitoring work, properly identified, developed, and submitted for funding?
 - Has project funding been received, obligated, and expended?
 - Have projects been completed and do they meet expected objectives?
- Federally listed species and designated critical habitat
 - Are conservation efforts effective?
 - Does the INRMP provide conservation benefits necessary to preclude critical habitat designation?
 - Are species at risk identified, and are steps being undertaken to preclude listing?
- Partnerships and effectiveness
 - Has the INRMP review team (i.e., DoD, USFWS, NDOW, BLM, USFS, SHPO, and WRPT) been effective in ensuring the INRMP's implementation?
 - Are other partnerships needed to meet INRMP goals?
 - Have other partnerships been effectively used to meet INRMP goals?

- Fish and wildlife management and public use
 - Are public recreational opportunities such as hunting, fishing, and wildlife viewing available to base residents and employees?
 - Are public recreational opportunities such as hunting, fishing, and wildlife viewing available to the public?
- Team adequacy
 - Does the installation's natural resources team have adequate resources to fully implement the INRMP?
 - Does the installation's natural resources team have adequate training to fully implement the INRMP?
 - Does the installation encourage retaining existing natural resource personnel to maintain corporate knowledge and manage resources with the most qualified professionals to support the military mission?
- Ecosystem integrity
 - To what extent are the installation's native ecological systems intact?
 - In what ways are an installation's various habitats susceptible to change or damage from different stressors?
 - What stressors affect each habitat type?
- INRMP impact on the installation mission
 - To what degree (i.e., high, medium, or low) are the INRMP and its associated actions supporting the installation's ability to sustain the current and potential future military mission?

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Appendix A Species Lists

UC Davis Bird Survey on Mount Grant (2012)

Mineral County Species List (2013)

USFWS Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species for Mineral County, NV
(2013)

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

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UC Davis Bird Survey on Mount Grant

Summary of presence and very rough estimate of relative abundance of birds on and off points during
 Abundance data have high uncertainty; please contact Erica Fleishman if abundance data might be useful.
 Each canyon was sampled three times between late May and early July

Only detections at point-count locations will be included in analyses; this summary includes some records
 Bodie refers to the dirt road running south from Lucky Boy Grade; 18 points sampled between 03327
 Corey Peak: 8 points sampled between 0347226 / 4256384 and 0344690 / 4257689

Powell: 10 points sampled between 0357219 / 4243310 and 0352016 / 4246385

For more information or complete data please contact Erica Fleishman, efleishman@ucdavis.edu, (530) 895-1234

maximum number of detections during a given sampling occasion

species	Cottonwood	Bodie	Corey Peak	Powell
California Gull			27	
Cooper's Hawk		1		
Red-tailed Hawk	2	2	3	2
American Kestrel			1	
Prairie Falcon	1	4		
Mountain Quail	27	10		2
Chukar	6	1		
Greater Sage-Grouse	8			
Killdeer		1		
Mourning Dove	2	2		
Northern Saw-whet Owl			1	
Common Nighthawk		1		
Common Poorwill		1		
White-throated Swift		1		
Broad-tailed Hummingbird	3			
Red-breasted Sapsucker	5	2		
Red-breasted or Red-naped Sapsucker	1	1		
Hairy Woodpecker	4	1	1	1
Northern Flicker	7	2	3	5
Olive-sided Flycatcher		1		
Western Wood-Pewee	5	2		
Gray Flycatcher			3	7
Dusky Flycatcher	13	1	6	
Ash-throated Flycatcher		1		1
Plumbeous Vireo	4	4	2	2
Warbling Vireo	12	5	4	2
Steller's Jay	16	15	3	4
Western Scrub-Jay	7	2	4	6
Pinyon Jay		32	6	85
Clark's Nutcracker	55		9	5
American Crow	1			
Common Raven	4		7	2
Violet-green Swallow	3	27	6	
Cliff Swallow		25		
Mountain Chickadee	12	11	6	9
Bushtit	7	16	3	5
White-breasted Nuthatch		3	3	

2013 Mineral County Species List

Scientific Name	Common Name	G-Rank	S-Rank	USFWS	State	BLM	USFS
Plants							
<i>Astragalus callithrix</i>	Callaway milkvetch	G3	S3				
<i>Astragalus cimae</i> var. <i>cimae</i>	Cima milkvetch	G2T2	S2				
<i>Astragalus johannis-howellii</i>	Long Valley milkvetch	G2	S2				W
<i>Astragalus lentiginosus</i> var. <i>sesquimetralis</i>	Sodaville milkvetch	G5T1	S1	RA	CE	S	
<i>Astragalus pseudiodanthus</i>	Tonopah milkvetch	G2Q	S2			C	W
<i>Boechea bodiensis</i>	Bodie Hills rockcress	G2	S2			N;C	S;I
<i>Boechea dispar</i>	pinyon rockcress	G3	S1S2				W
<i>Boechea shockleyi</i>	Shockley rockcress	G3	S3				I
<i>Camissonia nevadensis</i>	Nevada suncup	G3	S3				
<i>Cusickiella quadricostata</i>	Bodie Hills draba	G2	S2			N;C	S;W
<i>Cymopterus cinerarius</i>	gray wavewing	G2G3	S1?				
<i>Eriogonum ampullaceum</i>	Mono buckwheat	G3	S1				
<i>Eriogonum ampullaceum</i>	Mono buckwheat	G3	S1				
<i>Eriogonum beatleyae</i>	Beatley buckwheat	G2Q	S2				
<i>Goodmania luteola</i>	yellow spinecane	G3	S1				
<i>Grusonia pulchella</i>	sand cholla	G4	S2S3Q		CY		
<i>Helianthus deserticola</i>	dune sunflower	G2G3Q	S3				
<i>Helianthus deserticola</i>	dune sunflower	G2G3Q	S3				
<i>Mentzelia candelariae</i>	Candelaria blazingstar	G3?Q	S3?				
<i>Mentzelia candelariae</i>	Candelaria blazingstar	G3?Q	S3?				
<i>Oryctes nevadensis</i>	oryctes	G2G3	S2S3			N	
<i>Oxytheca watsonii</i>	Watson spinecup	G3?	S3?				
<i>Penstemon arenarius</i>	Nevada dune beardtongue	G2G3	S2S3			N	S
<i>Penstemon rubicundus</i>	Wassuk beardtongue	G2G3	S2S3				S
<i>Phacelia glaberrima</i>	Reese River phacelia	G3?	S3?				
<i>Phacelia monoensis</i>	Mono County phacelia	G3	S3			N;C	S;I
<i>Polyctenium williamsiae</i>	Williams combleaf	G2Q	S2		CE	C	I;S
<i>Senecio pattersonensis</i>	Mono ragwort	G2	S1				W
<i>Streptanthus oliganthus</i>	Masonic Mountain jewelflower	G3	S2			N;C	S;I
Invertebrates							
<i>Euphilotes enoptes primavera</i>	early blue	G5T1	S1			N	
<i>Lycaena rubidus incana</i>	White Mountains ruddy copper	G5T1	S1				

2013 Mineral County Species List

Scientific Name	Common Name	G-Rank	S-Rank	USFWS	State	BLM	USFS
<i>Plebejus icarioides albihalos</i>	White Mountains icarioides blue	G5T2T3	S1				
<i>Plebejus saepiolus albomontanus</i>	White Mountains saepiolus blue	G5T2	S1				
<i>Pseudocopa eodes eunus flavus</i>	Nevada alkali skipperling	G3G4T3	S1				
<i>Pyrgulopsis wongi</i>	Wongs pyrg	G2	S1			N	I
Fishes							
<i>Crenichthys baileyi grandis</i>	Hiko White River springfish	G2T1	S1	LE	YES	S	
<i>Oncorhynchus clarkii henshawi</i>	Lahontan cutthroat trout	G4T3	S3	LT	YES	S	T
Mammals							
<i>Antrozous pallidus</i>	pallid bat	G5	S3		YES	N;C	I
<i>Corynorhinus townsendii</i>	Townsend's big-eared bat	G4	S2		YES	N;C	S;l;L
<i>Lasionycteris noctivagans</i>	silver-haired bat	G5	S3B			N	
<i>Microdipodops megacephalus nasutus</i>	Fletcher dark kangaroo mouse	G4T2	S2		YES	N	
<i>Microdipodops pallidus</i>	pale kangaroo mouse	G3	S2		YES		
<i>Myotis californicus</i>	California myotis	G5	S4			N	
<i>Myotis californicus</i>	California myotis	G5	S4			N	
<i>Myotis ciliolabrum</i>	western small-footed myotis	G5	S3			N;C	
<i>Myotis evotis</i>	long-eared myotis	G5	S4			N;C	
<i>Myotis volans</i>	long-legged myotis	G5	S4			N	
<i>Ochotona princeps</i>	American pika	G5	S2		YES		
<i>Parastrellus hesperus</i>	western pipistrelle	G5	S4			N	
Birds							
<i>Charadrius nivosus nivosus</i>	Western Snowy Plover	G4T3	S3B		YES	N	
<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	Peregrine Falcon	G4	S2		YES	N	S
<i>Gavia immer</i>	Common Loon	G5	S2N		YES		S
<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	Bald Eagle (Contiguous US Pop)	G5	S1B,S3N		YES		S
<i>Plegadis chihi</i>	White-faced Ibis	G5	S3B		YES	P	

**USFWS Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species for Mineral County, Nevada
2013**

Appendix A

Group	Name	Population	Status	Lead Office	Recovery Plan Name	Recovery Plan Stage
Birds	Yellow-billed Cuckoo (<i>Coccyzus americanus</i>)	Western U.S. DPS	Candidate	Sacramento Fish And Wildlife Office		
Birds	Greater sage-grouse (<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>)	entire	Candidate	Wyoming Ecological Services Field Office		
Birds	Greater sage-grouse (<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>)	Bi-State	Candidate	Klamath Falls Fish And Wildlife Office		
Fishes	Lahontan cutthroat trout (<i>Oncorhynchus clarkii henshawi</i>)	Entire	Threatened	Nevada Fish And Wildlife Office	Lahontan Cutthroat Trout (<i>Oncorhynchus clarkii henshawi</i>) Recovery Plan	Final
Fishes	Hiko White River springfish (<i>Crenichthys baileyi grandis</i>)	Entire	Endangered	Nevada Fish And Wildlife Office	Recovery Plan for the Aquatic and Riparian Species of Pahranaagat Valley	Final
Fishes	Railroad Valley springfish (<i>Crenichthys nevadae</i>)	Entire	Threatened	Nevada Fish And Wildlife Office	Railroad Valley Springfish (<i>Crenichthys nevadae</i>) Recovery Plan	Final

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Fish			
Tahoe sucker	<i>Catostomus tahoensis</i>	Extirpated	USAEHA 1979, & Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Tui chub	<i>Gila bicolor</i>		USFWS 2013 & NDOW 1991
Lahontan cutthroat trout	<i>Onchorhynchus clarki henshawi</i>	Federally-threatened state-protected	USFWS 2013 & NDOW 1991
Benthos			
Mayfly	<i>Ironodes sp.</i>		USAEHA 1979
Caddisfly	<i>Wormaldia sp.</i>		USAEHA 1979

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Mammals			
White-tailed antelope squirrel	<i>Ammospermophilus leucurus</i>		USAEHA 1979, Blair and Kimball 1991
Pronghorn- antelope	<i>Antilocapra americana</i>		USAEHA 1979
Pallid bat	<i>Antrozous palliudus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Ringtail cat	<i>Bassariscus astutus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Coyote	<i>Canis latrans</i>		(CESC) 1991
Golden-mantled squirrel	<i>Citellus lateralis</i>		USAEHA 1979
Townsend ground squirrel	<i>Oitellus townsendi</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Western big-eared bat	<i>Corynorhinus rafinesquei</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Meriam kangaroo rat	<i>Dipodomys merriami</i>	Walker valley	USAEHA 1979
Great Basin kangaroo rat	<i>Dipodomys microps</i>	Walker valley	USAEHA 1979
Ord kangaroo rat	<i>Dipodomys ordi</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Big brown bat	<i>Eptesicus fuscus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Feral horse	<i>Equus caballus</i>		CECS 1991
Porcupine	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i>		usrws and NDOW 1991
Spotted bat	<i>Euderma maculata</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Least chipmunk	<i>Eutamias minimus</i>		USAEHA 1979
Panamint chipmunk	<i>Eutamias paniminti</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Mountain lion	<i>Felis concolor</i>		Blair and Heindl 1992
Bobcat	<i>Felis rufus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Sagebrush vole	<i>Lagurus curtatus</i>		USAEHA 1979
Silver-haired bat	<i>Lasionycteris noctivagans</i>		USAEHA 1979
Red bat	<i>Lasiurus borealis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Hoary bat	<i>Lasiurus cinerius</i>		USAEHA 1979
Blacktail jackrabbit	<i>Lepus californicus</i>		Blair and Kimball 1991
Whitetail jackrabbit	<i>Lepus townsendi</i>		USAEHA 1979
Bobcat	<i>Lynx rufus</i>		Blair and Kimba" 1991
Yellowbelly. marmot	<i>Marmota flaviventris</i>		Blair and Kimball 1991

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Mammals			
Striped skunk	<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Dark kangaroo mouse	<i>Microdipods megacephalus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Pale kangaroo mouse	<i>Microdipods pallidus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Longtail vole	<i>Microtus longicaudus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Mountain vole	<i>Microtus montanus</i>		USAEHA 1979
Shorttail weasel	<i>Mustela erminea</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Longtail weasel	<i>Mustela frenata</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Mink	<i>Mustela vison</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
California myotis	<i>Myotis californicus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Long-eared myotis	<i>Myotis evotis</i>		USAEHA 1979
Little brown myotis	<i>Myotis lucifugus</i>		USAEHA 1979
Small-footed myotis	<i>Myotis subulatus</i>		USAEHA 1979
Fringed myotis	<i>Myotis thysanodes</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Long-legged myotis	<i>Myotis vofans</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Yuma myotis	<i>Myotis yumanensis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Bushytail wood rat	<i>Neotoma cinerea</i>		CESC 1991
Desert wood rat	<i>Neotoma lepida</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Mule deer	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>		USAEHA 1979
Northern grasshopper mouse	<i>Onychomys leucogaster</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Southern grasshopper mouse	<i>Onychomys torridus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Desert bighorn sheep	<i>Ovis canadensis</i>	Reintroduced 1968	USAEHA 1979
Longtail pocket mouse	<i>Perognathus formosus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Little pocket mouse	<i>Perognathus fongimembris</i>	Valley floor	USAEHA 1979
Great Basin pocket mouse	<i>Perognathus parvus</i>	Sage brush and pinyon pine habits in valley and watershed	USAEHA 1979
Canyon mouse	<i>Peromyscus crinitus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Deer mouse	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>	Walker valley and watershed areas	USAEHA 1979
Pinyon mouse	<i>Peromyscus truei</i>	Watershed	USAEHA 1979

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Mammals			
Western pipistrel	<i>Pipistrellus hesperus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Raccoon	<i>Procyon lotor</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Western harvest	<i>Reithrodontomys</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
California mole	<i>Scapanus latimanus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Merriam shrew	<i>Sorex merriami</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Northern water shrew	<i>Sorex palustris</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Spotted skunk	<i>Spilogale putorius</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Pygmy rabbit	<i>Sylvilagus idahoensis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Mountain cottontail	<i>Sylvilagus nuttalli</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Mexican treetailbat	<i>Tadarida mexicana</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Badger	<i>Taxidea taxus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Valley pocket gopher	<i>Thomomys bottae</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Northern pocket gopher	<i>Thomomys talpoides</i>		UUSFWS and NDOW 1991
Gray fox	<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>		UUSFWS and NDOW 1991
Black bear	<i>Ursus americanus</i>		NNDOW and HWAD 1997
Kit fox	<i>Vulpes velox</i>		ESC 1991

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Cooper's hawk	<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Sharp-shinned hawk	<i>Accipiter striatus</i>	Terrestrial	Nevada Working Group Partners in Flight (NWGPF) 1997, GBBO 1998, and GBBO 2003
Spotted sandpiper	<i>Actitis macularia</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Clark's grebe	<i>Aechmophorus clarkii</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, and GBBO 2003
Western grebe	<i>Aechmophorus occidentalis</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; Stockwell 1994; NWGPF 1997; GBBO 1998 and GBBO 2003
Red-wing blackbird	<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Wood duck	<i>Aix sponsa</i>		GBB02003
Chukar	<i>Alectoris graeca</i>	Terrestrial, foothills	USAEHA 1979, USFWS & NDOW 1991, GBBO 2003
Sage sparrow	<i>Amphispiza belli</i>	Terrestrial, shrubs in foothills	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Pintail or Northern pintail	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; & GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
American widgeon	<i>Anas americana</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, GBBO 2003
Northern shoveler	<i>Anas clypeata</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; & GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Green-winged teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Cinnamon teal	<i>Anas cyanoptera</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Blue-winged teal	<i>Anas discors</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Mallard	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Gadwall	<i>Anas strepera</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Great white-fronted goose	<i>Anser albifrons</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
American pipit	<i>Anthus rubescens</i>		GBB02003
Scrub jay	<i>Aphelocoma coerulescens</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Golden eagle	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	Terrestrial, Walker Lake	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Great blue heron	<i>Ardea herodias</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Long-eared owl	<i>Asio otus</i>	Terrestrial, Mount Grant	USFWS and NDOW 1987, NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Lesser scaup	<i>Aythya affinis</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Redhead	<i>Aythya americana</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Ring-necked duck	<i>Aythya collaris</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and NWGPF 1997, GBBO2003
Greater scaup	<i>Aythya marila</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Canvasback	<i>Aythya valisineria</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Juniper titmouse	<i>Baeolophus ridgwayi</i>		GBBO2003
Cedar waxwing	<i>Bombcyla cedrorum</i>		GBBO2003
American bittern	<i>Botaurus lentiginosus</i>		GBBO2003
Brant	<i>Brents berincla</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Canada goose	<i>Branta canadensis</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979, USFWS & NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; & NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Great horned owl	<i>Bubo virginianus</i>	Walker Lake	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Cattle egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Bufflehead	<i>Bucephala albeola</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

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Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Common goldeneye	<i>Bucephala clangula</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Barrow's goldeneye	<i>Bucephala islandica</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Red-tailed hawk	<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Red-shouldered hawk	<i>Buteo lineatus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Rough-legged hawk	<i>Buteo /agopus</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Ferruginous hawk	<i>Buteo regalis</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Swainson's hawk	<i>Buteo swainsoni</i>	Terrestrial, higher elevations	USAEHA 1979
Green-backed heron	<i>Butorides striatus</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Dunlin	<i>Calidris alpina</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Western sandpiper	<i>Ca/idris mauri</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, GBBO 2003
Lea~t sandpiper	<i>Calidris minutilla</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, GBBO 2003
California quail	<i>Calli pep/a ca/ifornica</i>	Walker Lake	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Pine siskin	<i>Carduelis pinus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Lesser goldfinch	<i>Carduelis psa/tria</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
American goldfinch	<i>Cardue/us tiistis</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Cassin's finch	<i>Carpodacus cassinii</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
House finch	<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>	Terrestrial a	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Great egret	<i>Casmerodius a/bus</i>		Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Hermit thrush	<i>Catharus guttatus</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Canyon wren	<i>Catherpes mexicanus</i>		GBBO2003

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Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Willet	<i>Catoptrophorus semipalmatus</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Sage grouse	<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>	Terrestrial, foothills	USAEHA 1979, USFWS and NDOW 1991
Brown creeper	<i>Certhia americana</i>		GBBO2003
Western snowy plover	<i>Charadrius a/exandrinus</i>	State-protected species; breeds on dry lake bed on east side; Shoreline	USFWS and NDDW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Semipalmated plover	<i>Charadrius semipalmatus</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Killdeer	<i>Charadrius vociferus</i>	Terrestrial	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Snow goose	<i>Chen caerulescens</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Ross' goose	<i>Chen rossii</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Black tern	<i>Chlidonias niger</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Green-tailed towhee	<i>Chlorura chlorura</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979
Lark sparrow	<i>Chondestes grammacus</i>	Semi-open sage brush grassy areas	USAEHA 1979
Common nighthawk	<i>Chordeiles minor</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979
Northern harrier	<i>Circus cyaneus</i>	Shoreline	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Marsh wren	<i>Cistothorus petustrts</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Didsquaw	<i>Clangula hyemalis</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDDW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Evening grosbeak	<i>Coccothraustes vespertinus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Common flicker, Northern flicker	<i>Co/apter auratus</i>	Terrestrial, Rose canyon, Walker Lake	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

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Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Rock dove	<i>Columba livia</i>	Terrestrial, urban areas, Walker Lake	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998
American crow, Common crow	<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, USAEHA 1979, GBBO 2003
Common raven	<i>Corvus corax</i>	Terrestrial, throughout depot	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Sanderling	<i>Crocethia alba</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979
Steller's jay	<i>Cyanocitta stettlet</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Tundra Swan	<i>Cygnus co/umbianus</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991, GBBO 2003
Blue grouse	<i>Dendragapus obscurus</i>	Meadow	FWS and NDOW 1991
Hairy woodpecker	<i>Dendrocopos vil/osus</i>	Terrestrial, cottonwoods, lower canyons	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Yellow-rumped warbler	<i>Dendroica coronata</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Black-throated gray warbler	<i>Dendroica nigrescens</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979
Yellow warbler	<i>Dendroica petechia</i>	Terrestrial, Cottonwood and Rose Creek, willow canyons	USAEHA 1979
Snowy egret	<i>Egretta thula</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Empidonax flycatchers	<i>Empidonax spp.</i>	Terrestrial, foothills and canyons	USAEHA 1979
Traill's flycatchers	<i>Empidonax trai/lii</i>	Terrestrial, Cottonwood canyon	USAEHA 1979
Horned lark	<i>Eremophila alpestris</i>	Terrestrial, valley floor	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Brewer's blackbird	<i>Euphagus cyanocephalus</i>	Terrestrial	USFWS and NDDW 1991, GBBO2003
Merlin	<i>Falco columbarius</i>		GBBO2003
Prairie falcon	<i>Falco mexicanus</i>	Walker Lake	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
American kestrel, Sparrow hawk	<i>Falco spervetius</i>	Shoreline, Terrestrial, open country	NWGPF 1997, USAEHA 1979, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

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Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
American coot	<i>Fulica americana</i>	Walker Lake	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDDW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998
Wilson's snipe	<i>Gallinago delicata</i>	Terrestrial	GBBO2003
Common snipe	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Terrestrial	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998
Arctic loon, Pacific loon	<i>Gavia artica</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1989; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, GBBO2003
Common loon	<i>Gavia immer</i>	Sensitive; Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard; 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Red-throated loon	<i>Gavia stellata</i>	Shoreline	Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Northern pygmy owl	<i>Glaucidium gnoma</i>	Walker Lake	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Pinyon jay	<i>Gymnorhinus cyanocephala</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO
Bald eagle	<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>		HWAD 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO2003
Black-necked stilt	<i>Himantopus mexicanus</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Barn swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Harlequin duck	<i>Histrionicus histrionicus</i>	State-protected species; Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1990
Varied thrush	<i>Ixoreus naevius</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Dark-eyed junco	<i>Junco hyema/is</i>	Terrestrial, canyon thickets	USAEHA 1979, GBBO 2003
Dark-eyed junco gray-headed	<i>Junco hyema/is caniceps</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Dark-eyed junco	<i>Junco hyemalis dorsalis</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Dark-eyed junco slate-colored	<i>Junco hyemalis hyemalis</i>	Walker Lake	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Dark-eyed junco Oregon	<i>Junco hyema/is oregonus</i>	Walker Lake	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

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Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Northern shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>		GBB02003
Loggerhead shrike	<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	Terrestrial, desert floor and lower foothills	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBB0 1998
Herring gull	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003
California gull	<i>Larus californicus</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003
Ring-billed gull	<i>Larus delawarensis</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003
Glaucous gull	<i>Larus hyperboreus</i>	Shoreline	GBB0 2003
Western gull	<i>Larus occidentalis</i>	Shoreline	GBB02003
Bonaparte's gull	<i>Larus philadelphia</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Franklin's gull	<i>Larus pipixcan</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Rosy finch	<i>Leucosticte arctoa</i>	Walker Lake area	GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003
Long-billed dowitcher	<i>Limnodromus scolopaceus</i>	Walker Lake	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Marbled godwit	<i>Limosa fedoa</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Hooded merganser	<i>Lophodytes cuculatus</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Red crossbill	<i>Loxia curvirostra</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBB0 2003
Belted kingfisher	<i>Megaceryle alcyon</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996
Lewis' woodpecker	<i>Melanerpes lewis</i>	Walker Lake area	GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003
Swamp sparrow	<i>Melospiza georgiana</i>	Walker Lake area	GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003
Lincoln's sparrow	<i>Melospiza lincolni</i>	Terrestrial, willows, Cottonwood Creek	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBB0 1998, GBB0 2003

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Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Song sparrow	<i>Melospiza me/odia</i>	Terrestrial, margins of willows, Cottonwood Creek	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF, 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Common merganser	<i>Mergus merganser</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO1998, GBBO 2003
Red-breasted merganser	<i>Mergus serrator</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and GBBO 1998, GBBO2003
Northern mockingbird	<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>	Walker Lake	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Townsend's solitaire	<i>Myadestes townsendi</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Ash-throated flycatcher	<i>Myiarchus cinerascens</i>	Terrestrial, desert shrub areas	USAEHA 1979
Clark's nutcracker	<i>Nucifraga columbiana</i>	Terrestrial, higher	USAEHA 1979; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996;
Long-billed curlew	<i>Numenius american us</i>	Walker Lake	Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003 USAEHA 1979
MacGillavray's warbler	<i>Oporornis tolmiei</i>	Terrestrial, willows, Cottonwood canyon	
Mountain quail	<i>Oreortyx picius</i>	Terrestrial	USFWS and NDOW 1991
Sage thrasher	<i>Oreoscoptes montanus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Ruddy duck	<i>Oxyura jamaicensis</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Osprey	<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, GBBO 2003
Black-capped chickadee	<i>Parus atricapillus</i>	Terrestrial, high altitudes	USAEHA 1979
Mountain chickadee	<i>Parus gambel/i</i>	Terrestrial, pines	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO2003
Plain titmouse, juniper titmouse	<i>Parus inornatus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998
House sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Savannah sparrow	<i>Passerculus sandwichensis</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Fox sparrow	<i>Passerella iliaca</i>	Terrestrial, denser thickets	USAEHA 1979

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Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
American white pelican	<i>Pelecanus erythrorhynchus</i>	State-protected species; shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Double-crested cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Poor-will	<i>Phalaenoptilus nuttallii</i>	Terrestrial, desert floor	USAEHA 1979
Red-necked phalarope	<i>Phalaropus lobatus</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Wilson's phalarope	<i>Phalaropus tricolor</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996
Black-billed magpie	<i>Pica pica</i>	Terrestrial	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Downy woodpecker	<i>Picoides pubescens</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Spotted towhee,	<i>Pipilo erythrophthalmus</i>	Terrestrial, near	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF
Rufous-sided towhee		reservoirs; Walker Lake	1997, and GBBO 1998
White-faced ibis	<i>Plegadis chihi</i>	State-protected species; shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Black-bellied plover	<i>Puvialis squatarola</i>	Terrestrial	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Horned grebe	<i>Podiceps auritus</i>	Shoreline	Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Clark's grebe	<i>Podiceps cfarkii</i>		Stockwell 1994, and GBBO 1998
Eared grebe	<i>Podiceps caspicus</i>	Shoreline	USAEHA 1979; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Red-necked grebe	<i>Podiceps grisegena</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 198-7
Eared grebe	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998
Pied-billed grebe	<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard1996; NWGPF 1997; and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

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Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Sora	<i>Porzana carolina</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Bushtit, common bushtit	<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>	Terrestrial, valley floor	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO2003
Great-tailed grackle	<i>Quisca/us mexicanus</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Virginia rail	<i>Ral/us limico/a</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
American avocet	<i>Recurvirostra americana</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996,
Ruby-crowned kinglet	<i>Regulus calendula</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Rock wren	<i>Sa/pinctes obso/etus</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Say's phoebe	<i>Sayornis saya</i>	Terrestrial, edges of valley floor	USAEHA 1979, NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Broad-tailed hummingbird	<i>Seiasphorus playcercus</i>	Terrestrial, foothills	USAEHA 1979
Mountain bluebird	<i>Sia/ia currucoides</i>	Terrestrial, pines	USAEHA 1979, USFWS and NDOW 1991; CESC 1991, GBBO 2003
Red-breasted nuthatch	<i>Sitta canadensis</i>	Terrestrial, pines	USAEHA 1979; NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
White-breasted nuthatch	<i>Sitta carolinensis</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 2003
Burrowing owl	<i>Speotyto cunicularia</i>	Terrestrial, deserts foothills	USAEHA 1979
Red-naped sapsucker	<i>Sphyrapicus nuchalis</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Red-breasted sapsucker	<i>Sphyrapicus ruber</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Brewer's sparrow	<i>Spizella breweri</i>	Terrestrial, desert shrubs and lower foothills	USAEHA 1979
Caspian tern	<i>Sterna caspia</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Forster's tern	<i>Sterna torsteri</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1991; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Commonem	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Walker Lake area	Stockwell 1994
Westem meadowlark	<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>	Terrestrial, desert and lower foothills	USAEHA 1979; NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
European starling	<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Violet-green swallow	<i>Tachycineta tha/assina</i>	Terrestrial, around reservoirs	USAEHA 1979

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Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Birds			
Bewick's wren	<i>Thryomanes bewickii</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Brown thrasher	<i>Toxostoma rufum</i>		GBB02003
Lesser yellow legs	<i>Tringa flavipes</i>	Walker Lake	Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996
Greater yellow legs	<i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	Walker Lake	Stockwell 1994; Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996, GBBO 2003
Winter wren	<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i>		GBB02003
American robin	<i>Turdus migratorius</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Barn owl	<i>Tyto alba</i>	Walker Lake area	GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003
Orange-crowned warbler	<i>Vermivora celata</i>	Terrestrial, cabyons	USAEHA 1979
Wilson's warbler	<i>Wisonia pusilla</i>	Terrestrial, willow thickets	USAEHA 1979
Sabine's Gull	<i>Xemasabini</i>	Shoreline	USFWS and NDOW 1990
Mourning dove	<i>Zenaidura macroura</i>	Terrestrial Joothills	USAEHA 1979, GBBO 2003
White-throated sparrow	<i>Zonotrichia albicollis</i>	Terrestrial	GBB02003
Golden-crowned sparrow	<i>Zonotrichia atricapilla</i>	Terrestrial	GBB02003
White-crowned sparrow	<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>	Terrestrial	NWGPF 1997, and GBBO 1998, GBBO 2003

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Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Reptiles and Amphibians			
Zebra-tailed lizard	<i>Callisaurus draconoides</i>		
Nevada shovel-nosed snake	<i>Chionactis occipitalis talpina</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Western whiptail	<i>Cnemidophorus tigris</i>		USAEHA 1979
Great Basin whiptail	<i>Cnemidophorus tigris</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Western yellow-bellied racer	<i>Coluber constrictor Mormon</i>	NDOW sensitive	USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Panamint rattlesnake	<i>Crotalus cerastes</i>	NDOW sensitive	USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Mojave Desert sidewinder	<i>Crotalus mitchelli stephensi</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Western rattlesnake	<i>Crotalus viridis</i>		Blair and Heindl 1992
Great Basin rattlesnake	<i>Crotalus viridis futosus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Great Basin collared lizard	<i>Crotaphytus bicintores</i>		Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Collared lizard	<i>Crotaphytus collaris</i>		USAEHA 1979, Blair and Heindl 1992
Leopard lizard	<i>Crotaphytus wislizenii</i>		USAEHA 1979; Blair and Heindl 1992
Long-nosed leopard lizard	<i>Crotaphytus wislizenii</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Ring-necked snake	<i>Diadophus punctatus rigalus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Western skink	<i>Eumeces skiltonianus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Skilton skink	<i>Eumeces skiltonianus</i>		Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Sierra alligator lizard	<i>Gerrhonotus coeruleus palmeri</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Desert night snake	<i>Hypsiglena torquata deserticola</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
California kingsnake	<i>Lampropeltis getulus californiae</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Sonoran mountain kingsnake	<i>Lampropeltis pyromelana</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
California mountain kingsnake	<i>Lampropeltis zonata</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991
Coachwhip	<i>Masticophis flagellum</i>		Blair and Heindl 1992
Red racer	<i>Masticophis flagellum piceus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Desert striped whipsnake	<i>Masticophis taeniatus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Reptiles and Amphibians			
			Tracy 1999
Desert horned lizard	<i>Phrynosoma platyrhinos</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Western leaf-nosed snake	<i>Phrynosoma munitum</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Gopher snake	<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Great Basin gopher snake	<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Long-nosed snake	<i>Rhinocheilus lecontei</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Western (Mojave)	<i>Salvadora hexalepis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
patch-nosed snake	<i>moievensis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Sage brush lizard	<i>Sceloporus graciosus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Northern sagebrush lizard	<i>Sceloporus graciosus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Desert spiny lizard	<i>Sceloporus magister</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Western fence lizard	<i>Sceloporus occidentalis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Great Basin fence lizard	<i>Sceloporus occidentalis</i> <i>biseriatus</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Western ground snake	<i>Sonora semiannulata</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Utah black-headed snake	<i>Tantilla planiceps</i> <i>utahensis</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Sierra garter snake	<i>Thamnophis couchi</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Western terrestrial garter snake	<i>Thamnophis elegans</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Mountain garter snake	<i>Thamnophis elegans</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Wandering garter snake	<i>Thamnophis elegans</i> <i>vagrans</i>		USFWS and NDOW 1991, Espinoza and Tracy 1999

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

Common name	Scientific Name	Notes	Source
Reptiles and Amphibians			
Valley garter snake	<i>Thamnophis sirtalis tncn!</i>		
California lyre snake	<i>Trimorphodon vandenburghi</i>		<i>vandenburghi</i>
Side-blotched lizard	<i>Uta stansburiana</i>		USAEHA 1979, Blair and Heindl, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Northern side- blotches lizard	<i>Uta stansburiana</i>		Blair and Kimball 1991
Southern long-toed salamander	<i>Ambystoma macrodactylum sigillatum</i>		USAEHA 1979
Rocky Mountain Rubbre Boa	<i>Charina bottae utahensis</i>		Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; Stockwell 1994
Western Toad	<i>Buto boreas</i>		Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; Stockwell 1994
California toad	<i>Buto boreas halophilus</i>		Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; Stockwell 1994
Red spotted toad	<i>Buto punctatus</i>		Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; Stockwell 1994
Sierra Nevada Salamander	<i>Ensatina eschscholtzi planensis</i>		Brussard, Reed, and Vinyard 1996; Stockwell 1994
Pacific Chorus Frog	<i>Pseudacris regilla</i>		USFWS & NDOW 1991
Red-legged frog	<i>Rana aurora</i>		USFWS & NDOW 1991
Bullfrog	<i>Rana catesbeiana</i>		USFWS & NDOW 1991
Leopard Frog	<i>Rana pipiens</i>		USAEHA 1979, Espinoza and Tracy 1999
Great Basin spadefoot	<i>Scaphiopus intermontanus</i>		USAEHA 1979, Espinoza and Tracy 1999

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

References

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- NDOW (Nevada Division of Wildlife) and Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD). 1997.
- Nevada Working Group of Partners in Flight (NWGPF). 1997. Facsimile of Walker Lake Christmas Count, 1996B1997.
- Personnel Sighting (Walt Mandeville, NDOW, and Jim Purrell, HWAD) during Summer of 1997 Reconnaissance.
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- U.S. Army Environmental Hygiene Agency (USAEHA). 1979. Ecological Assessment No. 32-24-0270-81. Hawthorne Army Ammunition Plant, Hawthorne, Nevada. September 4 through 14.

Hawthorne Army Depot Species Occurrence List

Appendix A

USFWS (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service) and NDOW (Nevada Division of Wildlife) 1991 and earlier.

Notes:

Bird species that are included in this inventory using this citation include only species that were identified as documented sightings. Amphibians, reptiles, and mammals that are included in this inventory using this citation include species that are known to occur in the HWAD area, but have not necessarily been documented as occurring on the installation .

Species with USFWS and NDOW 1991 include those that were identified in the previous natural resources management plan based on historical listings provided by USFWS and NDOW. No documentation other than the 1991 NRMP was available as a reference for these citations. When the 1991 plan identifies a year that the species was observed, the year was used as the date following the AUSFWS and NDOW@ citation. When the 1991 plan did not identify the year that the species was observed, the year 1991 was used as the citation.

Appendix B

Pest Management

Pest Management Plan for the Hawthorne Army Depot (2012) (on the enclosed CD)

HWAD Invasive Species Survey Report (2004) (on the enclosed CD)

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Appendix B – The Pest Management Plan for the Hawthorne Army Depot (2012) and the HWAD Invasive Species Survey Report (2004) for the INRMP are on the enclosed CD.

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Appendix C

MOAs, MOUs, and Cooperative Agreements for Wildlife

Cooperative Agreement for the Reestablishment of Desert Bighorn Sheep on
Lands Administered by the U.S. Army Ammunition Plant Hawthorne, Nevada
(1988)

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COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT FOR THE
REESTABLISHMENT OF DESERT BIGHORN SHEEP
ON LANDS ADMINISTERED BY THE U.S. ARMY AMMUNITION PLANT
HAWTHORNE, NEVADA

The Nevada Department of Wildlife proposes to transplant 20-25 desert bighorn sheep onto lands in the Mount Grant area which are administered by the U.S. Army Ammunition Plant, Hawthorne, Nevada. Transplant stock would be obtained from Lone Mountain in Esmeralda County and transported to the site and released by Department personnel. Approximately three of the animals would be equipped with radio telemetry transmitters to facilitate follow-up efforts.

The following conditions would apply to this cooperative effort to reestablish sheep on the Mount Grant area:

1. The Nevada Department of Wildlife will provide all manpower and funding necessary for the initial release and augmentory releases of sheep on Mount Grant within the boundaries of the military reservation.
2. The U.S. Army will allow the Nevada Department of Wildlife access to this area as needed to monitor the bighorn sheep population.
3. The U.S. Army will control public access to this area to the extent necessary to provide protection to the bighorn sheep resource.
4. The U.S. Army will consult the Nevada Department of Wildlife prior to initiating any activities, military or otherwise, on the Mount Grant area which may adversely impact the bighorn sheep resource.
5. The U.S. Army will not permit domestic sheep grazing within the confines of the military reservation on the Mount Grant area.
6. The Nevada Department of Wildlife will regularly provide the Army with information regarding the status and trends of bighorns on the Mount Grant area.

7. At such time that the Department of Wildlife determines there is a harvestable surplus of bighorn sheep on the Mount Grant area, they will consult and coordinate with the U.S. Army regarding a hunting season. The U.S. Army would allow limited public access to those people successful in obtaining bighorn sheep tags for the Mount Grant area. The Department of Wildlife and the U.S. Army would jointly administer a hunt of this type.
8. Upon approval this agreement becomes an addendum to the COOPERATIVE PLAN FOR CONSERVATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF FISH AND WILDLIFE ON THE U.S. ARMY AMMUNITION PLANT, HAWTHORNE, NEVADA, which was agreed to by both agencies in June of 1984.

10-26-88

Date

Commanding Officer
Army Ammunition Plant
Hawthorne, Nevada

10-31-88

Date

Plant Manager
D.Z.B. Corporation
Operating Contractors of Hawthorne
Army Ammunition Plant

11-3-88

Date

Region I Manager
Nevada Department of Wildlife

*

Date

Regional Director
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

* Signature not required. See attached Cooperative Plan.

Appendix D

Fire and Emergency Procedures and Agreements

DZB Wildland Fire Response (1994) [updated version pending]

DZHC Emergency Response Plan (1996) [updated version pending] (on the enclosed CD)

MOA between HWAD and Mount Grant General Hospital (2004)

MOU between U.S. Army, DZHC, and Mineral County Sheriff's Office (2004)

Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement between HWAD, USFS, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and BLM Carson City District (2006) (expired, new version pending as of Spring 2013)

MOA between the Defense National Stockpile Center and the U.S. Army JMC (2006)

MOA between HWAD and WRPT (2006)

MOA between HWAD and Mineral County Office of Emergency Management (2010)

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July 19, 1994

Wildland Fire Response

The purpose of this procedure is to provide guidance and direction for a DZB Fire Department response to a wildland fire.

GENERAL

Fire sizeup at wildland fires is extremely important. First due fire units and command personnel are urged to conduct sizeup as soon as possible and relay information and instructions to other responding units.

Fire Department response to a wildland fire will require the initial attack to be made by the first fire suppression unit to arrive on the scene. Units arriving after the first unit will be assigned as necessary.

All wildland fire operations will be managed under the incident command system. (For further information see IOP-IS/FMD/FPP/446).

Priority protection will be afforded to structure protection, personnel property, public utilities, water shed, and animal habitat.

Considerations for additional resources and mutual aid will be made by command staff at the incident.

If on initial sizeup the wildland fire is larger than the amount of resources currently available, report the fire to the Nevada Division of Forestry or the United States Bureau of Land Management through the Plant Manager.

APPARATUS ASSIGNMENTS

A wildland fire response to the Mt. Grant area, New Bomb, Old Bomb, etc., will include the following apparatus and the minimum number of personnel on an initial assignment:

312	(Brush Truck)	2	Firefighters
307	(Crash Truck)	2	Firefighters
C-2	(Command)	1	Fire Officer

On initial sizeup, if more equipment and personnel are needed, additional apparatus and personnel can be requested at the discretion of the incident commander. (Call back personnel, as needed, to keep the staffing level at Fire Station #1 up to the minimum manning requirement.) Responding apparatus and personnel can include:

308	(Brush Truck)	2	- Firefighters
Water Tender	(1000 Gal.)	1	- Non-Firefighter Employee
Water Tender	(3000 Gal.)	1	- Non-Firefighter Employee

Mutual Aid will be called as necessary.

FIRE DANGER EXTREME

DUE TO THE HIGH VEGETATION GROWTH THIS SEASON, THE FOLLOWING WILL BE STRICTLY ENFORCED...

NO OPEN CAMPFIRE

NO USE OF BBQ BRIQUETTES

NO OFF ROAD USE OF RECREATION VEHICLES

- * THE USE OF UL LISTED GAS COOK STOVES OR PROPANE BBQ GRILLS ARE THE ONLY OPEN FLAME DEVICES ALLOWED.
- * IT IS RECOMMEND THAT A SHOVEL, GALLON OF WATER, AND FIRST AID KIT BE ON HAND IN YOUR VEHICLE WHILE IN THIS AREA.

I HAVE READ AND UNDERSTAND THE ABOVE RESTRICTIONS.

SIGNATURE _____ DATE _____

Memorandum of Agreement between
Hawthorne Army Depot
And
Mount Grant General Hospital

SUBJECT: AGREEMENT FOR MUTUAL AID

This agreement, entered into this Y day of June, 2004, between the Secretary of the Army, acting according to the authority of Section 1856, Title 42, United States Code, and Mount Grant General Hospital, is to secure for each the benefits of mutual aid to voluntarily coordinate services with each of the signatories in a good faith effort to minimize risk to patient care and hospital operations in the event of a natural disaster(s) and weapons of mass destruction that include but are not limited to mass casualties from terrorism. It is agreed that:

1. SCOPE AND APPLICABILITY

- a. Both agencies agree that in the event of natural disaster(s), weapons of mass destruction (WMD) and/or mass casualty incidents (MCI), affecting hospital services as a result of the above incidents which impacts the operational capabilities of any other agency, the affected agency may request assistance from the other agency as set forth herein.
- b. In the event of a disaster, an affected agency should first contact the Safety Officer, Mt. Grant General Hospital. If the incident is broader than the agreed agencies determine that they can handle by working together, then they will contact the Mineral County Office of Emergency Management (MCOEM) who then will coordinate with the State of Nevada Emergency Operations Center (NEOC).
- c. All agencies will use the guidelines established herein to coordinate the care and services necessary to deal with the incident. Agencies shall agree to take all appropriate actions during an incident without regard to race, color, creed, national origin, age, sex, religion, or handicap, to assist other Agencies as necessary. No Agency shall be required to provide treatment, care, medical supplies, equipment, services or personnel over and above that which is necessary to meet its own needs, existing or anticipated, or beyond its own resources.
- d. In the event of a disaster, each of the Agencies agree to provide assistance as set forth herein, at their sole cost and expense for a period to be determined by the affected Agency's EOC based upon the needs of affected Agencies.

Memorandum of Agreement between
Hawthorne Army Depot
And
Mount Grant General Hospital

- e. In the event that the affected Agency is unable to continue patient care for some or all of its patients, the Agency will agree to act as receiving facilities for these patients. The EOC of affected Agencies will coordinate the transfer of patients and will assign them to the other Agencies' facilities.
- f. Each Agency agrees to follow the guidelines set forth herein to the extent possible. There shall be no cause of action or basis of liability for breach of this Agreement.
- g. This Agreement is not intended to replace each facilities emergency operations plan or to adversely effect existing transfer agreements between facilities, but is intended to support those plans and agreement.

2. GUIDELINES

It is agreed that:

- a. Accept as many casualties as possible.
- b. Accept as many transfers as possible.
- c. Provide emergency treatment/care within the capabilities of the facility.
- d. Provide emergency physician and medical support services.
- e. Provide diagnostic services as available.
- f. Provide transportation as available and requested.
- g. Notify the Agencies when vacancies no longer exist.
- h. Provide medical record for patient transferred/received (copy acceptable if time permits.)
- i. Provide other medical services that may be necessary and requested.

3. EMERGENCY MEDICAL SUPPLIES AND EQUIPMENT

- a. Provide emergency medical supplies and equipment within resource capabilities.

4. COST OF SERVICES, EQUIPMENT AND PERSONNEL

- a. An Agency receiving services, equipment and personnel, will reimburse the cost of it to the Agency providing services, equipment and personnel.

Memorandum of Agreement between
Hawthorne Army Depot
And
Mount Grant General Hospital

5. COMMUNICATION SERVICES

In the event the Agencies' normal lines of communication are disrupted, each Agency will:

- a. Monitor Emergency Room Radios for emergency information transmitted.
- b. Notify local fire, police and other municipal services.
- c. Provide emergency communication equipment, if available, to the effected agency.
- d. Request support from Agencies Emergency Operations Center.

6. ADMINISTRATIVE SERVICES

Agencies will provide the following administrative services for them selves and will assist by:

- a. Maintaining a current listing of all casualties or transfers made.
- b. Maintaining a current listing of all discharges, their assigned areas and location.
- c. Maintaining a current listing of all deaths.
- d. Maintaining a record of all treatment administered, including medical supplies, or charges made.
- e. Contact family members of patient/personnel and inform them of the disposition of each.
- f. Other information or record keeping, as may be requested or deemed necessary

7. EMERGENCY MEDICAL INFORMATION

Agencies experiencing a disaster and seeking assistance will:

- a. Notify Agencies of the incident, and those casualties, if any, and/or transfers are being made, or will be made.
- b. Provide all medical information and/or records as necessary or requested.
- c. Coordinate emergency transportation as necessary or requested.
- d. Maintain a current listing of all patients and/or personnel and the disposition of each.
- e. Assign medical personnel as requested.
- f. Notify the attending physicians of the disaster and the disposition of their patients.

Memorandum of Agreement between
Hawthorne Army Depot
And
Mount Grant General Hospital

- g. Notify each agency when the disaster is over.
- h. Provide or coordinate other services/duties that may be necessary or requested.

Memorandum of Agreement between
Hawthorne Army Depot
And
Mount Grant General Hospital

DAVID W. DORNBLASER
Lieutenant Colonel, U.S. Army
Commanding

1 June 04

Date

CLIFFORD CICHOWLAZ, General Manager
Day & Zimmermann

1 June 04

Date

KEN RAMSEY, Director
Depot Protection, Day & Zimmermann

6/1/04

Date

RICHARD MUNGER
Director, Mount Grant General
Hospital

6/8/04

Date

LARRY MARSHALL
Fire Chief, Day & Zimmermann
Fire & Emergency Services

6-8-04

Date

M.O.U BETWEEN THE US ARMY, DAY & ZIMMERMANN HAWTHORNE CORPORATION AND THE MINERAL COUNTY SHERIFF'S OFFICE

1. PURPOSE

A. It is the intent of this document to define the coordination and cooperation between the Mineral County Sheriff's Office (MCSO), the Mineral County District Attorneys Office (MCDA), the Commander of Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD), and Day & Zimmermann Hawthorne Corporation (DZHC), Operating Contractor of HWAD.

2. REFERENCES

A. Department of the Army Contract #DAAA09-99-D-0022.

B. Army Regulation 525-13, 10 September 1998, Antiterrorism Force Protection

3. SITUATION

A. Applicable county, state, and Federal laws, rules and regulations prescribe functions, authority and jurisdictions, which control the preservation of order effort on HWAD. Simply stated, the Commander of HWAD has ultimate responsibility for the safety and security of all persons and property on the Depot. DZHC has the contractual obligation to provide preservation of order services, and the MCSO has the authority and responsibility for providing law enforcement services for the entire county, which includes concurrent jurisdiction at HWAD. The Mineral County District Attorney bears the obligation to investigate/prosecute any person involved in criminal activity in Mineral County, Nevada.

B. This agreement does not alter such matters. The preservation of order on HWAD is of mutual concern to all parties; however, the investigation of criminal incidents on HWAD may involve matters relating to the functioning of command or operation of the Depot that are non-criminal in nature. In such instances, it is essential that certain administrative procedures be initiated or be continued as separate actions while investigation of the criminal incident continues. Similarly, reporting requirements for criminal and non-criminal incidents by the Commander, HWAD are governed by the Army regulations that may be of no concern to DZHC, MCSO, or the District Attorney. Thus, it is recognized that dividing lines are not always clear, and generally there are legitimate areas of overlap of interest.

C. This memorandum recognizes the above situation, and makes provisions for working effectively with it. It is not intended to restrict the parties involved, but to enhance interrelationships through cooperation and coordination. The following are the objectives of this memorandum:

1. To provide a basis for cooperation and coordination between the MCSO, HWAD, DZHC, and between the various personnel assigned the task of preserving an acceptable level of order on HWAD.
2. To preclude uncoordinated or unnecessary duplicate investigation of the same incident by two or more agencies.
3. To preclude compromise of investigative effort being made by one of the parties.
4. As a baseline for cooperation and coordination, there will be a free flow of information, on a close hold, **"OFFICIAL USE ONLY"** basis between the parties on the nature and content of enforcement or investigative activity, except where law restricts transfer of information.
5. It is mutually recognized that the Commander, HWAD has unique reporting requirements and responsibilities, which include the notification and referral of criminal incidents to other Federal agencies, such as the Federal Bureau of Investigation, US Army Criminal Investigation Division, the US Army Intelligence Service and the Defense Investigative Service. The Commander, HWAD will be advised, through appropriate HWAD channels, of all crimes occurring on the Depot.

4. SCOPE

A. This agreement encompasses all currently recognizable interfaces between parties involved, and it is intended that any unforeseen problems that might arise will be resolved through negotiation between the parties, using this document as basic guidelines. Prior planning may be required for certain types of routine or emergency situations. Such planning documents, to include special orders, standing operating procedures, or other instructional material will be sectioned to this agreement.

5. AGREEMENTS, SUPPORT, AND RESOURCES REQUIREMENTS

A. Coordination and liaison will be accomplished by the following, or by alternate(s) in the event of the absence of designated individual(s):

1. The Mineral County Sheriff
2. The Mineral County District Attorney
3. The ACO Security Officer, HWAD
4. The DZHC Physical & Industrial Security Manager

B. The MCSO will provide 24 hour routine and standard law enforcement services for the areas of HWAD that are generally located to the west of U.S. 95, including the areas commonly known as, Conelly, Public Quarters, Thorne Road and unimproved real estate.

C. MCSO will not be responsible for checking security of the fences, gates, shops and administrative buildings within the Industrial Area.

D. The MCSO will respond to calls for assistance from DZHC in other areas of the Depot.

E. The MCSO will respond to HWAD for assistance for critical incidents that may be beyond DZHC Security's abilities. SRT duties cannot be provided by MCSO, but the MCSO will agree that sufficient resources will be used to set up a perimeter and initially contain a critical incident. MCSO further agrees to quickly receive additional manpower support from adjacent counties agencies as well as the Nevada Highway Patrol if a situation exceeds their capabilities.

F. The Mineral County Animal Control will provide animal control services for the housing areas, and will respond to requests for assistance in other areas of HWAD. (The Commander of HWAD and the DZHC General Manger can and will enforce tenant agreements relating to household pets; however, equipment and personnel to handle stray or dangerous animals are not available at HWAD).

G. The MCSO has the right and duty to serve various warrants and summons on HWAD. The Government staff and DZHC will cooperate to the fullest by making employees available at convenient locations for serving such documents. In the event the MCSO has reason to believe that the person to be served may flee or be dangerous, DZHC will be notified and will make arrangements for service at the work site. Access to fenced housing areas for the purpose of serving such documents at individual homes will not be impeded.

H. The MCSO will be notified of fatal vehicle accidents occurring inside the fenced areas of the Depot.

I. The MCSO will advise DZHC of any accidents or traffic citations involving the operation of government owned or DZHC owned vehicles assigned to HWAD.

J. Nothing in this agreement will interfere with the right of individuals living or working on HWAD to call on the MCSO for personal reasons, nor shall it impede the MCSO from handling such calls as routine law enforcement matters.

K. Upon request of the MCSO, DZHC may provide assistance in controlling traffic at accident scenes along state and county roads, when such roads are in close proximity to HWAD.

6. TERM OF AGREEMENT

A. This agreement will be reviewed one (1) year from the date of approval. This agreement may be terminated by any party, without cause, by giving the other party thirty-day (30) written notice.

7. INDEMNIFICATION AND HOLD HARMLESS

A. The parties hereto agree to indemnify and hold harmless the other parties to this MOU for any acts performed by its officers and employees that occur while acting under the scope of this agreement. By entering into this agreement, the parties do not waive sovereign immunity and intend to assert all defenses as set forth in statute.

Acknowledgment:

LTC Johnny M. Summers
Commander
Hawthorne Army Depot

CLIFFORD P. CICHOWLAZ
General Manager
Day & Zimmermann Hawthorne Corporation

FRED TRDLA
Sheriff
Mineral County

CHERI EMM-SMITH
District Attorney
Mineral County

KEVIN WADLOW
Chairman
Board of Mineral County Commissioners

The Mineral County Board of Commissioners approved this agreement in open meeting on _____ 2004.

Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot,
US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and
06-FI-11041702-029
Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District

1. PURPOSE: All parties have fire protection responsibilities within their jurisdictions. The Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD) borders lands managed by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM) and the U.S. Forest Service (USFS). Cooperation among these agencies is essential in combating fires which endanger the natural resources within our common borders.

2. AUTHORITY:

- a. Fire Protection Act of May 27, 1955 (42 U.S.C. 1856).

3. MUTUAL AID: Mutual Aid for the purpose of this agreement is to provide for cooperation in the prevention, detection, and suppression of wild-land fires within the protection areas of agencies signatory to this agreement.

4. GENERAL PROVISIONS

- a. BLM/USFS agrees:

- (1) Upon discovery, or report, will respond with firefighting resources to any wild-land fire within the depot.

- (2) To provide mutual aid initial attack with no reimbursement for the first 12 hours. Mutual aid forces will be released at the earliest possible opportunity.

- (3) To provide information about current land management fire restrictions to the HWAD Fire Department.

- b. HWAD FD agrees:

- (1) Upon discovery, or report, will respond with firefighting resources to any wild-land fire within BLM/USFS land.

- (2) To provide mutual aid initial attack with no reimbursement for the first 12 hours. Mutual aid forces will be released at the earliest possible opportunity.

- (3) HWAD will abide by and implement BLM/USFS fire restrictions except at the OB/OD ranges.

- (4) To provide facilities for housing BLM/USFS personnel and equipment for an extended period and to provide meals when needed.

Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot,
US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and
06-FI-11041702-029
Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District

5. MUTUAL UNDERSTANDING

- a. Fires within 1 mile of jurisdictional boundaries will be responded on by the closest available resources.
- b. Incident command will be established by the first arriving officer. Command will be transferred to the arriving jurisdictional representative. HWAD FD may elect to establish a joint command within the depot.
- c. All personnel in support of wildland fires will wear leather lace-type boots with skid resistant soles with tops at least eight inches (8") high, leather gloves, hard hats, fire resistant shirt and pants and have a fire shelter in accordance with National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) on while on the fireline.
- d. All protection units will, to the extent possible, provide fire prevention programs, inspections, and enforcement as necessary to adequately address the fire problem in their Direct Protection Areas. In addition, units are encouraged to undertake joint prevention activities in areas of mutual interest whenever practical.
- e. Interagency training activities can be mutually beneficial and units are encouraged to participate in shared local level training at each other's facilities on an on-going basis. They are encouraged allocate available slots in appropriate formalized training sessions for personnel of the other agencies.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the following agencies have executed this agreement as of the last date written below:

Donald T. Hicks 6/1/06
DONALD HICKS Date
Field Manager, Carson City Field Office
Bureau of Land Management

Kathy Nichol 5/9/06
ROBERT VAUGHT Date
Forest Supervisor
Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest

Johnny M. Summers 5/17/06
JOHNNY M. SUMMERS Date
Lieutenant Colonel, U.S. Army
Commanding

/s/ Cheryl F. Probert 5-3-06
Concurrence Date
CHERYL PROBERT
District Ranger

THE AUTHORITY AND FORMAT OF THIS INSTRUMENT
HAS BEEN REVIEWED AND APPROVED FOR SIGNATURE
Jean Bent 5/3/06
AGREEMENTS COORDINATOR

Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement
06-FI-11041702-029
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot,
US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and
Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District

ANNUAL OPERATING PLAN

1. PURPOSE

- a. This Operating Plan is to provide for cooperation in the prevention, detection, and suppression of wildland fires within the protection areas of agencies signatory to this agreement.
- b. This plan provides the officers and employees of the agencies guidelines and information necessary to properly execute the terms of the agreement.

2. DEFINITIONS AND DESCRIPTIONS

- a. Hawthorne Army Depot hereinafter referred to as the HWAD Fire District.
- b. US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest hereinafter referred to as the Forest Service.
- c. Bureau of land Management, Carson City District hereinafter referred to as the BLM District.
- d. Protecting Agency – The agency responsible for providing direct fire protection in a given area pursuant to this agreement.
- e. Supporting Agency – An agency providing suppression assistance or other support and resources to the protecting agency.
- f. Jurisdictional Agency - The agency, which has overall land and resource management and/or protection responsibility as, provided by law.

3. STATEMENT OF MUTUAL BENEFITS AND INTERESTS

- a. The HWAD Fire District has the responsibility for prevention, protection and suppression of structure, vehicle fires, explosive fires, rescues, hazardous materials incidents, medical aids and other non-wildland fires within the established district. These structures and lands protected by the HWAD Fire District are intermingled or adjacent to lands protected by the Forest Service and/or BLM District.
- b. The Forest Service has the responsibility for prevention, protection and suppression of wildland fires on National Forest administered lands.

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Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District

- c. The BLM District has the responsibility for prevention, protection and suppression of wildland fires on Bureau of Land Management administered lands, and on adjacent or intermingled HWAD Fire District and/or BLM District lands identified through the agreement.
- d. Therefore it is mutually advantageous, and in the public interest, for the agencies to coordinate their efforts in the prevention, detection, and suppression of wildfires in and adjacent to their areas of responsibility.

4. GENERAL PROVISIONS

- a. In accordance with the Fire Management Plan, HWAD will upon discovery or report of a fire respond the necessary firefighting resources to any wildland fire within the base boundary or at the request of Minden Dispatch
- b. **REQUEST ASSISTANCE.** Outside initial attack areas, when requested by the protecting agency, the supporting agency will, within their capability, provide initial action or other support on wildland fires. Such requested assistance is reimbursable.
- c. **INDEPENDENT ACTION.** Except as otherwise described in this agreement, any agency on its own initiative and without reimbursement may go upon lands protected by another agency to suppress wildfires, if the fire is a threat to property within that agencies protection responsibility. In such instances, the agency taking action will promptly notify the protecting agency.
- d. If any agency takes action on a fire independently, the supporting agency will furnish the protecting agency a preliminary report (oral) within 24 hours of the action taken and a written incident report with 10 days.
- e. **NOTIFICATIONS.** Each agency will promptly notify the protecting agency of fires burning on or threatening lands for which that agency has protection responsibility. When taking action, the supporting agency will, as soon as possible, notify the protecting agency in accordance with this agreement; detailing what equipment and personnel have been dispatched to the incident location.
- f. **COMMUNICATIONS.** All agencies agree to share the use of communication systems, radios and radio frequencies for the execution of this agreement. Sharing of frequencies must be approved only by authorized personnel for each Party.

**Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement
06-FI-11041702-029
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot,
US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and
Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District**

Agency	Frequencies	
	RX	TX
HWAD	142.325	141.025
Bureau of Land Management	169.775	169.775
Humboldt Toiyabe N.F.	169.875	170.475

- g. **PRESERVATION AND DETERMINATION OF EVIDENCE.** All agencies will attempt to protect point of origin of the fire and evidence pertaining to the fire cause.
- h. **TRAINING.** Each agency will advise the other of applicable cross training opportunities for personnel.
- i. **BILLING PROCEDURES.** To reimburse the supporting agency for the use of equipment and personnel for the actual costs incurred by the supporting agency. The supporting agency will bill for actual costs thru their respective internal billing systems. Specific billing information will be provided when requested. There is no reimbursement between the Bureau of Land Management and Forest Service. Reimbursement will be between the Forest Service and Hawthorne Army Depot or the Bureau of Land Management and Hawthorne Army Depot.
- j. **FIRE RESTRICTIONS AND CLOSURES.** All agencies will coordinate restrictions and closures.
- k. **FUELS MANAGEMENT.** The protection agency will inform all agencies of prescribed fires it is managing. Support during a prescribed burn is not covered under this agreement.
- l. **EMPLOYMENT POLICY.** Employees of the agencies to this agreement will at all times be subject only to the laws, regulations, and rules governing their employment, regardless of incident location, and shall not be entitled to compensation or other benefits of any kind other than specifically provided by the terms of their employment.
- m. **CLAIMS.** Claims for damage will be processed as determined by applicable Federal law. Protection agency employees acting under the terms of this agreement are not considered Federal employees and are not covered under the Federal Tort Claims Act.

Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement
06-FI-11041702-029
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot,
US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and
Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District

- n. **EXAMINATION OF RECORDS.** Each agency will give the other, or their authorized representative, access to, and the right to examine all records, books, papers and documents related to this agreement.
- o. **FUNDING LIMITATION.** Nothing herein will be considered as obligating either agency to expend or as involving either agency in any contract or other obligation for the future payment of money in excess of funding approved and made available for payment under this agreement and any modification thereto.
- p. **MODIFICATIONS.** Modifications to this agreement will be made by mutual consent of all agencies, by the issuance of a written modification, signed and dated by all agencies, prior to any changes being made.
- q. **CIVIL RIGHTS.** The agencies will comply with all State of Nevada and Federal statutes and orders relating to nondiscrimination
- r. **DURATION OF AGREEMENT.** The Cooperative Fire Agreement shall commence on the date the last agency signs the agreement and will remain in effect for fire (5) years from that date.
- s. **DURATION OF ANNUAL OPERATING PLAN.** All units will meet annually prior to March 30, to review the Operating Plan and update it as necessary. If there are no changes to the Operating Plan a letter stating that will suffice and letter will be placed in the file.
- t. **TERMINATION.** All agencies retain the right to terminate their participation under this agreement by providing 30 days written notice to the other agencies.
- u. **LEGAL AUTHORITY.** The protecting agency certifies that person executing this on their behalf has the legal authority to enter into this agreement.

6. MAPS

The following items should be shown on each map:

- a. Protection boundary.
- b. Reciprocal initial attack areas.
- c. Restricted areas.

7. CONTACTS FOR COOPERATORS

Cooperative Fire Protection Agreement
06-FI-11041702-029
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot,
US Forest Service, Humboldt-Toiyabe National Forest, and
Bureau of Land Management, Carson City District

- a. HWAD Fire District
 - HWAD Guard Operations Center Dispatch (775) 945-7911
 - HWAD Fire Chief (775) 945-7487
(775) 945-9433 Cell
 - HWAD Assistant Chief (775) 945-7417
 - HWAD Safety & Occ Health Spec (775) 945-7020

- b. Forest Service
 - Sierra Front Interagency Dispatch (775) 883-5995
 - Bridgeport Ranger District Office (760) 932-7070
 - District Fire Management Officer (760) 932-1202
 - a) Bill Bryant (760) 932-7724 Home
(760) 616-0007 Cell
 - Assistant Fire Management Officer (760) 932-1204
 - a) Todd Baumer (760) 932-7336 Home
(760) 616-0008 Cell

- c. BLM District
 - Minden, Bureau of Land Management Dispatch (775) 883-5995
 - Minden, Bureau of Land Management Office (775) 885-6000

8. PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT

All personnel in support of wildland fires will wear leather lace-type boots with skid resistant soles with tops at least eight inches (8") high, leather gloves, hard hats, fire resistant shirt and pants and have a fire shelter in accordance with National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) on while on the fireline.

9. FIRE PREVENTION ACTIVITIES

All protection units will, to the extent possible, provide fire prevention programs, inspections, and enforcement as necessary to adequately address the fire problem in their Direct Protection Areas. In addition, units are encouraged to undertake joint prevention activities in areas of mutual interest whenever practical.

10. INFORMATION AND ACTIVITIES

- a. Protection units should develop joint press releases on cooperative fire protection issues to ensure that the interests of all affected agencies are adequately addressed.

REPLY TO
ATTENTION OF

DEPARTMENT OF THE ARMY
HAWTHORNE ARMY DEPOT
1 SOUTH MAINE AVENUE
HAWTHORNE, NV 89415-9404

JUN 01 2006

MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT

between the
Defense National Stockpile Center
and the
United States Army Joint Munitions Command

SUBJECT: Storage of the National Defense Stockpiled Inventory of Mercury at the
United States Army Ammunition Depot at Hawthorne Nevada

This agreement establishes the scope of materials management services the Joint Munitions Command (JMC) will provide to the Defense National Stockpile Center (DNSC) for the consolidated storage of mercury. Storage facilities for this mission will be provided at the United States Army Ammunition Depot at Hawthorne Nevada (HWAD). HWAD is a Government Owned, Contractor Operated (GOCO) facility. DNSC will retain management and control responsibilities of the mercury as an active commodity within the Strategic and Critical Materials Stockpile. The JMC will provide storage facilities, materials handling, and maintenance services on a reimbursable basis. Requirements for storage and support services will be identified, requested and funded by DNSC on Military Inter-departmental Purchase Requests (MIPR).

A. Materials handling services required by DNSC under this agreement shall include:

1. Repositioning of existing stocks to enable mercury storage at HWAD
2. Physical receipt and control of equipment necessary to maintain and manage the mercury inventory at HWAD
3. Physical receipt of palletized mercury at HWAD
4. Physical positioning of the mercury inventory within the designated warehouses
5. Recording and reporting stock locations
6. Initial and scheduled inspections of the mercury in storage
7. Release detection and remediation services

B. Facility support requirements shall include:

1. Assignment of dedicated warehouse space (initially determined to be 140,000 square feet)
2. Coordination support for facility reconfigurations and restorations as required for this specific mission (to be accomplished by the Sacramento, CA District Office of the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE))

3. Scheduled inspection, preventive maintenance and general repairs of DNSC occupied warehouses
4. Fire alarm system monitoring and maintenance
5. Fire emergency response support
6. Security alarm systems monitoring and maintenance
7. Physical security including installation perimeter security, scheduled surveillance of DNSC occupied warehouses and response support
8. Electrical power and including maintenance of the power distribution system
9. Maintenance of access roads and surrounding grounds

C. Installations support services requirements shall include:

1. Training for staff who will accomplish normal warehousing and storage tasks associated with handling the palletized mercury
2. Training for staff who will accomplish normal surveillance and inspections of mercury in storage
3. Training for staff and off base organizations that would or might participate in a release incident response.
4. All community notification and public relations actions

DNSC will provide written requests identifying specific storage support services as they are required to the Commander, HWAD with copies furnished to the Commander, JMC. Initial requests for services shall be provided under individual memorandum and shall include detailed Statements of Work (SOW) and associated Independent Government Estimates (IGE) of costs for the services requested. Requests shall be forwarded to the Commander, HWAD 120 days before the requested services are required.

JMC and HWAD will review all requests and provide DNSC with a planning estimate of costs for the requested services. Upon receipt of a planning estimate DNSC will provide a funded MIPR for the requested services to the JMC. DNSC shall provide technical assistance as requested by the HWAD and/or JMC to explain or modify the SOW as may be necessary to award services under the standing base operations contract.

HWAD will be responsible for identifying facility repair and restoration work required to maintain the integrity of warehouses storing DNSC mercury. JMC will identify those repairs that can be accomplished within the scope of the base operations contract. DNSC will provide a project specific MIPR to JMC for all repair and restoration projects that will be accomplished by the base operations contractor. Facilities repair and maintenance work determined by the JMC Contracting Officer to be beyond the scope of the existing base operations contract will be referred to the USACE. DNSC will be responsible for initiating and funding those actions and coordinating all related activity with JMC and HWAD.

Initial and recurring training of staffs and public relations support will be considered and funded in each specific MIPR. Special or unscheduled requirements for training and community relations actions will be identified to DNSC and funded separately.

DNSC will provide all specialized equipment and supplies required to maintain mercury in storage to HWAD. DNSC will transfer its existing inventories of related support equipment and supplies to HWAD prior to initiation of these support services. New, additional and/or subsequent requirements for equipment, supplies and materials to support mercury storage operations will be funded by DNSC and acquired by HWAD.

DNSC will provide HWAD with the current manuals and instructions that specify procedures for storage and maintenance of mercury when the agreement with annual requests for storage support. DNSC will provide HWAD with all updates to these instructions within 30 days of their implementation.

DNSC will accomplish annual surveillance of mercury storage operations at HWAD. This may include on site inspections and may occur more frequently if circumstances warrant.

This agreement is entered on May 31, 2006 and shall remain in force until the DNSC managed inventory of mercury is removed from the Hawthorne Army Depot.

CORNEL A. HOLDER
Administrator
Defense National Stockpile Center

JOHNNY M. SUMMERS, LTC, USA
Commanding Officer
Hawthorne Army Depot

Initial and recurring training of staffs and public relations support will be considered and funded in each specific MIPR. Special or unscheduled requirements for training and community relations actions will be identified to DNSC and funded separately.

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DNSC will provide HWAD with the current manuals and instructions that specify procedures for storage and maintenance of mercury when the agreement with annual requests for storage support. DNSC will provide HWAD with all updates to these instructions within 30 days of their implementation.

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This agreement is entered on May 31, 2006 and shall remain in force until the DNSC managed inventory of mercury is removed from the Hawthorne Army Depot.

CORNEL A. HOLDER
Administrator
Defense National Stockpile Center

JOHNNY M. SUMMERS, LTC, USA
Commanding Officer
Hawthorne Army Depot

Memorandum of Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot
and
Walker River Paiute Tribe

SUBJECT: AGREEMENT FOR EMERGENCY SUPPORT, TRAINING, AND FOR ADVANCE NOTICE OF TRAIN MOVEMENT AND UNUSUAL HAZARDS

This Agreement, entered into this 16th day of May 2006, between the Commander, Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD) as agent of the secretary of the Army under authority of Section 1856a, Title 42, United States Code and the Chairperson of the Walker River Paiute Tribal Council representing the Walker River Paiute Tribe (Tribe), is to secure an agreement for the protection of life and property from damage resulting from any accidents occurring during the transportation of ammunition and explosives and other materials and equipment via railroad/highway through the Walker River Paiute Reservation. This agreement is entered into in compliance with paragraphs 5c and 12c of the Right-of-Way Agreement Between Indian Plaintiffs and Army, which agreement was approved by all parties and by the federal district court for the district of Nevada in the consolidated cases United States v. Southern Pacific Transportation Co., and Walker River Paiute Tribe et al v. Southern Pacific Transportation Co., Civ. No.s R2707-BRT and R2708-BRT. Accordingly, it is agreed that:

- a. Upon request of the Walker River Paiute Tribe's designated representative, the Commander of HWAD or his/her designated representative will dispatch equipment and personnel from HWAD to the site of the accident, upon the Walker River Paiute Reservation, to render assistance in the resolution of a Railroad/Highway accident occurring during shipments to or from HWAD.
- b. Hawthorne Army Depot's designated contact for emergency response to rail accidents and highway accidents involving explosives is the HWAD Guard Operations Center (945-7555) or Emergency Response (945-7911). Both are manned 24 hours per day. The reporting Tribal official will provide the name and the phone number of their point of contact to the Guard Operations Center.
- c. The dispatch of personnel and equipment pursuant to this Agreement is subject to the following conditions:
 - (1) Any request for assistance under this Agreement will include a statement of the location and any observable condition that has resulted from the accident; what evacuation measures have been executed by emergency volunteers or law enforcement officers; and any applicable restrictions in route to the accident site.

- (2) Hawthorne Army Depot designated personnel will report to the Walker River Paiute representative an appraisal of the situation.
 - (3) Upon arrival at the site of any accident, HWAD designated personnel will take charge of the situation until such time as the emergency has ceased to exist.
 - (4) Personnel from the Walker River Paiute Tribe may be requested and permitted but not required to render direct assistance in the actual resolution of the accident. Tribe assistance from trained emergency volunteers and other emergency responders will consist primarily in the initial identification of the hazard and evacuation of personnel from the area but could involve other activities completed by emergency responders who are trained to handle the particular emergency.
- d. Hawthorne Army Depot's government transportation officer will provide if possible a 72 hour advance notice but at a minimum a 24 hour advance notice to the Tribe's designated representative or representatives of shipments by rail to and from HWAD. The notice will include the number of railcars expected and the hazard class of the material being transported. Shipments that involve unusual transportation requirements, i.e., extremely heavy shipments of battleship gun barrels or hazards that will necessitate either special security or safety will be coordinated with designated Tribal officials prior to movement through the Reservation. This advance notice could be via a telephone call, email, fax or any combination of these modes of notice or other means of notice determined by the Tribe and agreed by HWAD.
- e. To facilitate communications between the parties concerning the implementation of this agreement, HWAD and the Walker River Paiute Tribe agree that each party shall designate a liaison or liaisons who will be responsible for contact and coordination between the parties concerning matters covered by this Agreement and related inquiries that may arise from time to time. Such liaison shall be designated in writing by the Tribal Chairperson and the HWAD Commander. Such designation of liaison may subsequently be changed from time to time in writing. The Chairperson of the Tribe and the Commander of the HWAD shall represent the parties in signing any such letters designating liaisons.
- f. The U.S. Army will offer, through its operating contractor at HWAD at no cost to the Walker River Paiute Tribe, the opportunity to participate in training sessions held for emergency response employees at HWAD.

Hazmat training, per the Army rail right-of-way agreement, will be provided to the Tribal emergency response employees. This training will be conducted at Schurz.

Mercury transportation emergency response training will also be provided to Tribal emergency response personnel at Schurz prior to transport of mercury by truck to HWAD. This training will be a one time event, unless the mercury is removed from HWAD and then, the training will be provided again.

They will be trained in recognition of hazards and actions required in emergency situations resulting from railroad/highway transportation of Army hazardous material (ammunition and explosives). Other training opportunities, to be conducted at HWAD, will be made available to Tribal personnel.

HWAD understands that they are required per the Army Right-of-Way Agreement to conduct training for Tribal emergency responders on topics related to potential hazards and endangerment to the Tribal community associated with the transportation of hazardous materials to and from HWAD. These trainings can include identification and recognition trainings since dealing with transportation accidents could involve a higher level of response from the Tribal emergency responders.

All requests for emergency service training should be coordinated with the operating contractor's Fire Chief at (775) 945-7487.

- g. This agreement shall become effective upon the date signed and shall remain in effect for five years or may be amended by mutual written consent of the parties hereto.

FOR WALKER RIVER PAIUTE TRIBE:

Genia Williams
Tribal Chairperson

May 16, 2006
Date

FOR SECRETARY OF THE ARMY:

Johnny M. Summers
Lieutenant Colonel, U.S. Army
Commanding

May 25, 2006
Date

Memorandum of Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot and
Mineral County Office of Emergency Management

SUBJECT: AGREEMENT FOR MUTUAL AID

This Agreement entered into this 1st day of January 2010, between the Commander of the Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD), acting according to the authority of Section 1856, Title 42, United States Code and the Mineral County Office of Emergency Management, acting pursuant to NRS 277.180, to secure for each the benefits of mutual aid in the protection of life and property; firefighting; emergency medical services; hazardous materials incidents; rescues; technical rescue incidents; vehicle and machinery extrication; wildland fires; mass casualties accordingly, it is agreed that:

1. Upon request by a representative of Hawthorne Army Depot (HWAD) or designee, or by a representative of the Operating Contractor Fire & Emergency Services (FES), or by a representative of the Mineral County Office of Emergency Management (MCEOM) or designee, or by Mineral County Fire Department (MCFD), HWAD Fire & Emergency Services personnel and equipment will be dispatched 40 miles in each direction of HWAD property for which the MCFD normally provides emergency services as designated by the representative of the MCFD.
2. Upon request by a representative of the MCFD, equipment and personnel of the MCFD will be dispatched to any point within the area for which the HWAD FES normally provides emergency services as designated by the representative of HWAD FES.
3. The participating agencies will provide fire suppression equipment and mutual aid assistance within their own protection guidelines, safety limitations, and availability of resources, without unnecessary depletion of resources.
 - (a) Rapid Intervention Teams (RIT) consists of trained firefighters equipped to perform RIT tasks.
 - (b) These standards require that a minimum of two firefighters be prepared outside in full protective equipment, while other crew members are working in a hazardous atmosphere.
 - (c) Two members of the initial attack crew who are assigned for rapid deployment to rescue lost or trapped members.

NOTE: Mutual Aid firefighters will not be used to fight fires in the buildings or structures that contain explosives, radiological, or toxic chemicals.

**Memorandum of Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot and
Mineral County Office of Emergency Management**

4. Any dispatch of equipment and personnel pursuant to this agreement is subject to the following conditions.

(a) Any request for aid under this agreement will include a statement of the amount and type of equipment and personnel requested, and will specify the location to which the equipment and personnel are to be dispatched. A representative of the responding organization will determine the amount and type of equipment and number of personnel to be furnished.

(b) The responding organization will report to the officer in charge of the requesting organization at the location to which the equipment is dispatched and will be subject to the orders of that official.

(c) The responding organization will be released by the requesting organization when the services of the responding organization are no longer required, or when the responding organization is needed within the area where it normally provides fire protection.

(d) If a incident occurs involving aircraft owned or operated by the United States or military aircraft of any foreign nation within the area for which MCFD normally provides emergency services, the Fire Chief or designee of the HWAD FES will assume command on arrival of the scene.

5. Each party waives all claims against every other party for compensation of any loss, damage, injury, or death occurring as a consequence of the performance of this agreement except those claims authorized under section 2201, Title 15, United States Code.

6. Section 2201, Title 15, United States Code governs compensations to municipalities for direct costs and losses sustained while fighting fires on federal property.

7. All equipment used by HWAD FES in the execution of this agreement will, at the time of action hereunder, be owned by either the government or Operating Contractor of the Hawthorne Army Depot; and all personnel acting in behalf of the Operating Contractor under this agreement will, at the time of such, be an employee of the Operating Contractor.

Memorandum of Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot and
Mineral County Office of Emergency Management

8. All equipment used by the MCFD in the execution of this agreement will, at the time of action hereunder, be owned by Mineral County; and all personnel acting for the MCFD under this agreement will, at the time of such, be an employee or volunteer member of the MCFD.

9. This agreement shall be in effect for two (2) years from the date of signature. This agreement may be terminated by either party with sixty (60) days written notice.

Kimberly L. Gilbert-Mason
Lieutenant Colonel, U.S. Army
Commanding

1-21-2010

Date

Clifford Cichowlaz
General Manager
Day & Zimmermann Hawthorne Corporation

1-19-2010

Date

Ken Ramsey,
Director, Depot Protection
Day & Zimmermann Hawthorne Corporation

1/21/10

Date

Jerrie Tipton
Chairman, Board of Mineral County
Commissioner

1/13/2010

Date

Craig Nixon
Fire Chief, Mineral County
Fire Department

Jan 13, 2010

Date

Memorandum of Agreement
Between
Hawthorne Army Depot and
Mineral County Office of Emergency Management

Rob Mathias

Rob Mathias
Fire Chief, Day & Zimmermann Hawthorne Corporation
Fire & Emergency Services

1/4/2010
Date

Cherrie George

Cherrie George
Mineral County Clerk Treasurer

January 13, 2010
Date

Appendix E

General Landscape Guidance

Technical Manual No. 5-630: Natural Resources Land Management (1982) (on the enclosed CD)

General Landscape Plants Maintenance Guide (1997)

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Appendix E – Technical Manual No. 5-630: Natural Resources Land Management (1982) for the INRMP is on the enclosed CD.

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Appendix E

General Landscape Plants Maintenance Guide

As indicated in the text, the Facilities Management Division is currently reevaluating the ground maintenance program to assess the feasibility of returning the more highly-groomed cantonment areas to a xeric or desert landscape. L.L.S, Department of Defense Army (DoD), Technical Manual 5-630 provides additional detail regarding the care and maintenance of the cantonment area landscape. The following describes currently used maintenance procedures for fertilizer application, lawn preparation and care, and tree and shrub pruning.

Fertilizer

Generally, grass lawns will be fertilized by broadcasting ammonium sulfate (21-0-0) or equivalent at the rate of 5 pounds per square foot (lb/ffl) (about 200 pounds per acre) uniformly on dry foliage and then irrigating. Five pounds of ammonium sulfate contains about 1 pound of actual nitrogen. Fertilizer will be applied once every second or third month during the growing season of the predominant species of grass. Less frequent and smaller applications will be made in areas where maintenance (water and or mowing) is limited to the minimum needed to maintain an acceptable cover. Basically, a rate of 1 pound per 1,000 ft² of actual nitrogen per month is sufficient to promote good color and health in average turf maintained under moderately intense management. Equivalent fertilizers that will provide actual nitrogen at the rate of about 1 pound per 1,000 ft² are available and may be applied in the following quantities: ammonia sulphate (21-0-0) at 5 pounds per 1,000 square feet; ammonia phosphate sulphate (16-9-0) at 6 pounds per 1,000 square feet; and ammonia nitrate (33-0-0) at 3.5 pounds per 1,000 square feet.

Fertilizers are not generally applied to natural cover on land that has not been irrigated; however, in some areas, the natural cover can be improved and encouraged to prevent erosion by applying ammonia sulphate (21-0-0) at a rate of 5 pounds per 1,000 square feet in October and February.

Fertilizer can be applied at any time from early spring until mid-summer and from late September to late November. It should not be applied from July 15 to September 15, because there is a danger of stimulating a late, succulent growth that is subject to winter kill.

The feeding roots of most trees and shrubs extend beyond the end of the overhead branches for a considerable distance, depending on species, soil conditions, and management. The fertilizer will be applied from the trunk outward beyond the branches but at least 2 feet away from the tree trunk. To be effective, fertilizer must dissolve into the soil solution. Where surface irrigation is not available, holes (varying from 12 to 15 inches deep) will be drilled at spacings from 15 to 18 inches apart over the entire area. A complete fertilizer will be placed in the holes, and the holes will then be filled with water to dissolve the fertilizer.

top 2 inch of soil. If the weather is hot and windy, applications may be needed two or three times a day on bluegrass seedlings. The rate of applications must be correlated to the intake rate of the soil. It must be low enough so that water will penetrate to the depth desired without accumulation on the surface or runoff. When seedlings reach 1-inch in height, they will be watered only when grass indicates a need for moisture (when the grass begins to show a darker green color). The frequency of irrigation will vary with temperature, wind, soil, and precipitation; irrigation should not be performed on a calendar schedule.

Under some conditions (such as limited time, poor soil conditions, and high cost of establishment by seeding) a lawn may be planted successfully by using live and growing plant materials. Three common methods of vegetative planting are as follows:

- Sodding

- Sod strips are placed so as to completely cover the area as a green carpet (instant lawn@) this can be the most economical or practical way to establish turf on steep slopes.

- Sprigging

- Separate plant parts are planted, at spaced intervals, as sprigs, runners, cuttings, or stolons.

- Plugging

- Sod plugs (2 or 3 inches in diameter) are transplanted at intervals of 1 foot; plugging is often used to introduce new species without destroying existing turf.

Lawn Mowing

The Facilities Management Division maintains (waters, plants, feeds, and mows) all industrial, administrative, and common housing areas. Residents are responsible for maintaining the areas around their units.

During the establishment year and during the entire life of a lawn, mowing should be based on the height attained rather than on a fixed timetable. Bluegrass and fescue lawns should be allowed to grow about 3-2 inches before the first cutting and then clipped to a height of 2 to 2-2 inches. Subsequently, bluegrass and fescue lawns should never be cut closer than 2 inches and the amount that is cut should not exceed 1 to 1-2 inches. However, during the hot summer months, and again just before going into dormant season in the fall, bluegrass should not be clipped closer than 3 inches. Normally, all clippings should be left on the lawn.

Whenever the stand is sparse, the plants should be allowed to set seed and volunteer to fill out the following year. The grassed area should be cut to a height of 4 to 6 inches, usually twice a year, once during May, and again in late summer or early fall.

Lawn edges should be trimmed within 1 day of every second or third mowing. Spreading grass adjacent to curbs, sidewalks, flowerbeds, sprinkler heads, trees, or other objects in lawn areas should be cut as a substitute for machine edging when practicable.

The Hawthorne Army Depot Housing Brochure, Section IV, General Policies, and DA 210-2, Handbook for Family Housing Occupants, are provided to housing tenants, and contain

penetrate 6 to 10 inches. In all irrigations, the applications rate must be low enough so water will penetrate to the depth desired without accumulation on the surface or runoff.

Trees and shrubs should be irrigated deeply and only frequently enough to assure adequate moisture for continuing plant growth. Over watering will severely damage or kill the plant by drowning and/ or by rotting of the roots and root crowns. Roots must have oxygen as well as water.

The Facilities Management Division is responsible for operation and maintenance of the irrigation systems at Hawthorne Army Depot. All lawn irrigation systems should be checked for adequacy of irrigation pattern. Sprinkler heads that are putting water on the sidewalks and roads should be repaired/replaced with heads that put the water on the lawn where it is needed.

Instructions regarding irrigation schedules and practices are furnished occupants of quarters and family housing in DA pamphlet 210-2, Handbook for Family Housing Occupants, paragraph 6--2a, and the HW AD Housing Brochure (paragraph 2.3.2 of this plan provides the applicable guidelines).

Chemical Control of Vegetation

The following table provides information applicable to the use of herbicides at the Hawthorne Army Depot.

TABLE F-1

Herbicide Use at Hawthorne Army Ammunition Depot *Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan*

Name	Method	% Active Ingrid.
Pre-Emergence Control		
Aatrex	Hand sprayer	80%
Borocil	Hand sprayer	100%
Promitol	Broadcast	96.75%
Siamazine	Power sprayer	80%
Ureabor	Power sprayer	98%
Post-Emergence		
Weedar-64	Hand, power sprayer	49.3%
Weed-RHAP	Hand, power sprayer	65.4%
Trimac	Power sprayer	49.67%
Non-selective		
Roundup	Hand sprayer	41%

Whenever the stand is sparse, allow the plants to set seed and volunteer in order to fill out the following year. The grassed area should be cut to a height of 4 to 6 inches, usually twice a year, once during May and again in late summer or early fall.

Trim lawn edges every second or third mowing within one day of the mowing. Cut spreading grass adjacent to curbs, sidewalks, flower beds, sprinkler heads, trees or other objects in lawn areas as a substitute for machine edging when practicable.

The HW AD Housing Brochure, Section IV, General Policies, and DA 210-2, Handbook for Family Housing Occupants, are provided to housing tenants and contain guidance for managing and maintaining the grounds around their units for which they are responsible.

Weed Control

Weeds in tree plantings should not be permitted to grown rank or set seed. Control of weeds should be accomplished by hoeing or hand weeding at least once a month from March to October.

Pruning

Proper pruning should begin right after planting. Function is the prime principle of a good landscape, and proper and timely pruning can build the plant to do the job desired. First, remove all limbs and branches that obstruct walks and drives. Second, prune back to clear all doors, windows, and visual obstructions. Then go back and prune the plants for form, shape, size, vigor and beauty. Landscape pruning may be done - in fact should be done - as soon as the need is seen; not by season but by need. Evergreens, especially shrubs, in some spots should be encouraged to grow and branch to the ground. This not only gives a more healthy plant but in most cases, a much better looking plant. Pruning cuts should be near stem or branch so there will be no unsightly stubs or Acoat hangers@.

Prune to:

- Control habit of growth.
- Remove all dead, broken or diseased parts.
- Improve flowering or fruiting.
- Improve chances of survival.

Note:

Modified from Day and Zimmermann Hawthorne Corporation. 1997. A Hawthorne Army Ammunition Plant, Natural Resources - Land, Forest, and Wildlife Management. CDRL 560. Working Draft Report. January.

Appendix F

Erosion Control Measures

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Appendix F – Erosion Control Measures is pending from Hawthorne Army Depot. The existing version was not available, and HWAD has communicated that the updated Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan will have the most updated information. The erosion control measures from the SWPPP will be included in this appendix.

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Appendix G

Special Studies and Recovery Plans

Short-Term Action Plan for Lahontan Cutthroat Trout in the Walker River Basin
(2003) (on the enclosed CD)

Mount Grant Initial Conservation Assessment and Strategies (2003) (on the
enclosed CD)

Bi-State Action Plan – Past, Present, and Future Actions for Conservation of the
Greater Sage-Grouse Bi-State District Population Segment (2012) (on the
enclosed CD)

USFWS Post-delisting Monitoring Plan for the Bald Eagle (*Haliaeetus*
leucocephalus) in the Contiguous 48 States (2009) (on the enclosed CD)

Sage Grouse Initiative: Tracking Success (2013) (on the enclosed CD)

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Appendix G - The documents in this appendix are all on the enclosed CD with the INRMP:

- Short-Term Action Plan for Lahontan Cutthroat Trout in the Walker River Basin (2003)
- Mount Grant Initial Conservation Assessment and Strategies (2003)
- Bi-State Action Plan – Past, Present, and Future Actions for Conservation of the Greater Sage-Grouse Bi-State District Population Segment (2012)
- USFWS Post-delisting Monitoring Plan for the Bald Eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*) in the Contiguous 48 States (2009)
- Sage Grouse Initiative: Tracking Success (2013)

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Appendix H
2013 INRMP Environmental Assessment

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Appendix H – The INRMP Environmental Assessment is pending from Tetra Tech. The Environmental Assessment is in the draft stages and will be included in this appendix after it is finalized.

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Appendix I
INRMP Annual Updates (2013-2018)
(to be completed by HWAD)

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Appendix I – Annual INRMP Updates (2013-2018) will remain empty until HWAD inserts annual updates for the INRMP over the next 5 years. This tab will assist the depot in updating their future goals and projects.